

Research Unit

Image Sequence Analysis to Investigate Dynamic Processes

Progress Report Phase I (12/1995-2/1998)

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Preface

This report summarizes the results of the first phase of the research unit (“Forschergruppe”) “Image Sequence Processing to Study Dynamic Processes” founded in December 1995 after the funding by the German Science Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) became available. The operation of the research unit was in full gear with the delivery of all equipment and the filling of all positions in the summer of 1996. Only project C started later, because the position of the PhD student was filled not until October 1996. Thus this report covers only about one year of research. The principal investigators are grateful to report that within this short time period a close and fruitful collaboration has been established, significant results could already be achieved, and that a clear research strategy for the next three years has been worked out, which includes the incorporation of two more research groups.

Scope and General Research Strategy

The central theme of the research unit is the study of transport, exchange, and growth processes by

- developing and using visualization techniques that take image sequences and extract the biological or physical parameters of interest and make them visible, and by
- using image sequence processing techniques to tackle key scientific questions in various research areas that cannot be studied adequately without these techniques.

A close and interdisciplinary cooperation between applications and fundamental research in image analysis is the most distinct feature of the research unit. In the first phase of the research unit it has become evident that the interaction between basic research in image sequence processing and the different application areas was a key element for the achieved progress. The Interdisciplinary Center for Scientific Computing (Interdisziplinäres Zentrum für Wissenschaftliches Rechnen, IWR) at Heidelberg University with its rich history of groundbreaking interdisciplinary cooperation proved to be a stimulating environment for the research unit. The IWR was founded several years ago as a central institute of Heidelberg University with just such interdisciplinary activities in mind.

Usage of a Common Software Platform

All members of the research group use a common, portable, modular, and open software environment. This software package runs both on UNIX platforms and on PCs under Windows95/NT and incorporates data structures for image sequences, volumetric data and multigrid image processing. It also supports real-time image sequence acquisition with a number of frame grabbers.

The software is used for the development of the algorithms *and* for all application projects of the research unit for the acquisition, interactive evaluation, and analysis of image sequences. With the aid of a powerful scripting language that allocates image objects and defines operators on the basis of the built-in algorithms, the software can quickly be adapted to new experimental setups and be used for automatic batch processing of large quantities of image data. Newly developed algorithms are exchanged either via DLLs or shared libraries or workspaces using the scripting language.

Usage of Standard Hardware

Our research focuses on the development of effective algorithms running on standard hardware platforms. This approach is validated by the following facts. First, the algorithms for image processing become more and more complex, making it increasingly difficult to port algorithms to dedicated image

processing hardware. Second, instruction sets for pixel processing, e. g., VIS and MMX, are incorporated into general purpose hardware boosting the time-consuming low-level image processing. Third, the scientific community at large should profit from the progress gained by the work of this research unit.

Sharing of Equipment

The members of the research unit have shared and will continue to share a central pool of equipment for image sequence acquisition and image sequence analysis. This includes a cluster of computers suited for efficient sampling of image sequences, various cameras, the geometric and radiometric calibration setups, and other equipment used in several projects jointly to take image sequences. This approach ensures the effective usage of expensive equipment by different research groups.

Intensive Communication between Development and Applications

A weekly workshop seminar fosters the interdisciplinary cooperation and provides a forum to discuss progress on a continuous base among the members of the research group. This seminar is also used to discuss the development of the image sequence processing algorithms between the core project and the application areas. The status of the research unit was also reviewed in two internal workshops that took place in the Carl-Benz Haus in Ladenburg on November 16, 1996 and March 8, 1997.

International Collaboration

Actual topics in the research areas of the research unit were discussed in the weekly colloquium of the research unit. A complete list of all talks given in the colloquium from the winter semester 1995/1996 through the summer semester 1997 is given in appendix IV. The members of the research unit gave also a number of invited talks as summarized in appendix III. All members of the research unit have close contacts and cooperations to leading international research centers.

The progress made in the research was presented to and discussed with the international research community at the first workshop "Image Sequence Processing to Study Dynamical Processes" that took place from June 4-6, 1997 in Heidelberg. The program of the workshop is summarized in appendix V.

Acknowledgments

Financial support for this research unit by the German Science Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, DFG) is gratefully acknowledged. The principal investigators are also grateful for the constructive and detailed comments of the review committee. By reading this progress report and the renewal proposal the reviewers will find that their comments have been taken seriously and have considerably improved the cooperation and scientific outcome of the research unit. The close cooperation in project B with the Scripps Institution of Oceanography and the Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution including field measurements of air-sea gas transfer and short wind waves was made possible by grants of the US National Science Foundation (Coastal Ocean Processes, CoOP) and the US Office of Naval Research through the Marine Boundary Layer Accelerated Research Initiative (MBL/ARI).

We also would like to thank the administration of Heidelberg University for providing some matching funds in difficult times and the vice rector for scientific research, Prof. Jörg Hüfner, for his support of and interest in this research unit. Likewise, we are grateful for the advice and support of Prof. Willi Jäger, director of the IWR.

Finally the principal investigators would like to cordially thank all diploma and doctoral students that participated in this research unit. Their work was substantial for the achieved progress. With a lot of enthusiasm they picked up the ideas of this truly interdisciplinary research and took the extra effort to fill it with life by contributing much to the open-minded interdisciplinary cooperation. A complete list of all diploma theses and dissertations that were finished or started during the first phase of the research unit is given in appendix II.

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A Image Sequence Analysis

1 Introduction and Summary

This project is the core project of the research unit. Its task is to provide the image sequence processing algorithms required for the application projects B through D. In phase I of the research unit, emphasis was on the basic computer vision techniques for image sequence acquisition and low-level image sequence processing including

- shape from shading techniques (section 3),
- geometric and radiometric calibration of camera systems (section 4),
- analytic studies of the performance of low-level motion estimators (section 5),
- optimization of filters for spatiotemporal image processing (section 6),
- fast and accurate implementation of low-level motion estimators based on a tensor approach (section 7), and
- some preliminary studies of a new approach to 3-D reconstruction with a single moving camera (section 8).

Before going into the details of the performed research, we will discuss in section 2 why it was necessary to develop new image sequence processing algorithms at all although a huge body of research in image sequence analysis has been undertaken in the recent years.

2 Requirements for the Scientific Applications in the Research Unit

In the following sections, four areas will be identified in which the application areas of this research unit deviate from classical computer vision tasks and thus require the development of new concepts.

2.1 High Accuracy

In many typical computer vision tasks qualitative features are of more importance than precise quantitative measurements. This is well known from the remarkable capabilities of biological vision systems to perform tasks precisely with visual guidance — such as to take up an object — although the optical systems and the estimates of the 3-D position are not accurate. In the scientific applications of the research unit, the quantitative aspects are of more importance. The measurement of leaf growth (project D), the study of the modulation of short wind waves (project B), or of the dynamical changes in the surface flow at the ocean surface (B) or the detection and tracking of emission plumes in GOME image sequences (project C) require *accurate* estimates with *known* errors.

The accuracy demands for the applications in the research unit are high and require to estimate displacements between consecutive frames with an accuracy of at least a few hundredths pixels. For plant growth, it is for instance required, to detect size changes well below one permille. At this level of accuracy, the complete image formation process including the nonuniformity in the response of the sensor elements in the camera must be considered carefully. This is why one important research topic is also the geometrical and radiometric calibration of camera systems (section 4).

Although the theoretical background to analyze the systematic and statistical errors of measurements is well established and has a long tradition in physical and engineering sciences, it is a widely neglected area in computer vision and especially so in image sequence processing. This has much to do, of course, with the fact that early approaches were mainly empiric and thus did not allow a study

of the systematic and statistical errors of the extracted parameters such as the velocity and position of objects. How less care was generally taken with the accuracy of image sequence algorithms can best be read from two facts. First, the standard scenes used to check the algorithms were almost exclusively not calibrated sequences such as the famous Hamburg taxi scene. Secondly, only a handful of papers explicitly dealt with the analysis of the errors and uncertainties of image sequence processing algorithms (for references see section 5).

2.2 Extension to Multichannel Images

An important general characteristic for the applications in the research unit is that an adequate study of the dynamic processes involved requires the simultaneous acquisition of image sequences with many parameters. This general demand makes it necessary to set the image sequence processing techniques up in a way that they can also be used with multichannel images.

Again this is a field that has not been touched much in this generality. Of course, color image processing is commonplace in computer vision. This is not true, however, for image sequences. Again there are only a few publications in this area.

This field is however rapidly advancing driven by the extended capability of modern imaging sensors, especially the hyperspectral sensors that become more and more common for remote sensing. In the research unit, we have one project which is such a hyperspectral sensor with thousands of channels, the GOME instrument (project C). Thus we regard it as an important task of the research unit to incorporate multichannel images into the image sequence processing. This is more than just using many channels to determine a *single* velocity. Often the different channels show slightly different velocities, which are significant to characterize the underlying dynamical process. In the plumes from biomass burning, different tracers have for instance different life times. Or, if multiple tracers are used to study the transfer processes across the ocean surface, different diffusivities lead to different concentration patterns from which important clues about the underlying mechanisms can be drawn.

2.3 Active Vision and Adaptive Optics

Active vision is now a generally accepted paradigm of computer vision — again learnt from biological vision systems — that makes otherwise ill-defined or unstable algorithms well-defined and stable [Blake and Yuille, 1992]. The research in this field, however, is mainly restricted to mimic the common capabilities that can be found also in human vision: a moving camera and vergence control (see e. g., [Mertsching, 1996]). Zooming is already studied much more seldom.

In the context of this research unit, the tremendous technical possibilities of modern vision systems are of importance and ask for a broader application and understanding of active vision systems. In technical applications active vision systems may include an adaptive control of the focal length, the observation wavelength, the depth range that is observed, the illumination, and the polarization of the radiation to name only a few of the many possibilities. In the long term this approach may lead to a unification of the concepts of classical active vision and classical active optical systems.

For this research unit, these broader types of active vision concepts will be of significant importance on the long term. In the short term we will use controlled camera motion for 3-D measurements of plant leave growth (section 8).

2.4 Dynamically Changing Objects

Most of the research in image sequence processing has been performed with the motion of rigid bodies. Only recently, the motion of dynamically changing objects received more attracting because of its importance in medical applications.

The “objects” encountered in this research unit are of much more general nature. They do not just change their shape but new parts may gradually appear such as in studying the growth of plant leaves or roots (project D) or when new waves are generated by the wind at the ocean surface (project B). This is of course a much more general class of problems and the question arises how the motion *and* dynamics of such objects can be determined accurately. It is obvious that this requires more general approaches than the motion of rigid objects. The details of concepts how we want to tackle this combined problem of analyzing motion and the dynamics in a general way including all types of changes encountered in this research unit are described in the renewal proposal of the core project A.

Figure A.1: Refraction at an inclined surface with a surface slope $s = \tan \alpha$ as the base for the shape from refraction technique. The camera is far above the surface. Rays that are emitted by the light source under an angle γ are refracted into the direction of the camera. **b** Even for a slope of infinity (vertical surface, $\alpha = 90^\circ$), rays from the light source meet the camera. **c** Radiance map where the radiance in a telecentric illumination source varies linearly in x_1 direction (A.1).

3 Shape from Refraction with Multiple Light Sources

3.1 Shape from Shading for Specular Surfaces

Shape from shading techniques are an important paradigm for 3-D reconstruction in computer vision [Horn, 1977]. Traditionally, shape from shading techniques deal only with diffusely reflecting surfaces, ideally Lambertian surfaces. In project B, a surface reconstruction problem is encountered with a specular reflecting surface, the small-scale shape of the ocean surface. Although the solution of this problem in the core project is mainly a service for wave imaging in project B, we regard it as of more general importance for the research unit. The study of this complex shape from shading problem has deepened and will further deepen the understanding of the interaction of illumination system with optical surface properties, which will help us to optimize the setup of illumination system for any experimental task in the research unit. In the long term, it will help us extracting surface reflectance properties e. g., from plant leaves (see renewal proposal for the core project, section 3.2.6).

Wave slope imaging was previously performed only with a single light source on the base of a shape from refraction technique with an extended light source Jähne and Riemer [1990]. The work reported here is an extension of the work of Zhang and Cox [1994] who were the first to apply color vision to the wave slope imaging problem.

3.2 Shape from Refraction

For transparent specular surfaces, shape from refraction techniques can be used and are more advantageous than classical reflection-based shape from shading techniques because of (i) higher radiance, (ii) measurement of higher slopes, and (iii) significantly lower nonlinearities of the slope/radiance relationship. A shape from refraction technique requires a special illumination technique since — except for the small fraction of light reflected at the surface — no significant radiance variations occur. The base of the shape from refraction technique is a telecentric illumination system that converts a spatial radiance distribution into an angular radiance distribution. Then, all we have to do is to compute the relation between the surface slope and the angle of the refracted beam and to use a light source with an appropriate spatial radiance distribution.

The relation between the surface slope s and the tangent of the angle γ is approximately linear [Jähne et al., 1994] with an error of less than 10% for slopes up to 1 (see also (A.1)). This technique works for slopes up to infinity (vertical surfaces). In this limiting case, the ray to the camera grazes the surface (figure A.1b)

Figure A.1a illustrates the optical geometry for the simple case when the camera is placed far above and a light source below a transparent surface of a medium with a higher index of refraction. With a telecentric illumination source (light source in the focal plane of a lens with a focal length f), the position from which the camera receives light for a certain surface slope s can be related as [Jähne *et al.*, 1994]

$$\mathbf{x}/f = \frac{s}{s} \tan \gamma = s \frac{\sqrt{n^2 + (n^2 - 1)s^2} - 1}{\sqrt{n^2 + (n^2 - 1)s^2} + s^2} \approx \frac{s}{4} \left(1 - \frac{3}{32}s^2\right). \quad (\text{A.1})$$

If the radiance of the light source is varying with the position \mathbf{x} , we can infer the corresponding surface slope. Of course, we have again the problem that from a scalar quantity as the radiance no vector component such as the slope can be inferred. The shape from refraction technique comes, however, very close to an ideal setup. If the radiance, for instance, varies only linearly in x_1 direction, the radiance map in the gradient space is also almost linear (figure A.1c). A slight influence of the cross slope results from the non-linear terms with s^2 in (A.1) but becomes apparent only at quite high slopes.

3.3 Shape from Refraction with Multiple Illumination Sources

Intensity-based techniques with a single light source have several drawbacks. First they share the general problem of all shape from shading techniques that a scalar quantity only (the radiance) gives not sufficient information to retrieve a vectorial quantity, the surface slope. Secondly, absorption and scattering of light in dirt and bubbles or inhomogeneities in the light source cannot be compensated for.

Therefore we devised a new technique based on three light sources [Balschbach and Jähne, 1997]. With three degrees of freedom this technique can infer the full surface gradient (two components) and still be insensitive to light absorption. The basic idea is to take several images of the same scene with the same optical setup except for different illuminations. Since each of these illuminations suffers from the same additional effects listed above in a multiplicative way, they can be canceled out by dividing two images with different illuminations.

In a static scene, sequential images can be taken by moving the illumination source. This approach is, however, not possible for imaging of dynamical processes such as water surface waves. In this case it is required to take all exposures with the different illumination setups at the same time. Such multiple illuminations in a single exposure can most easily be realized by using color.

A unique color position coding can be achieved, for example, with the following color wedges

$$\begin{aligned} G(\mathbf{x}) &= (1/2 + x)E_0(\mathbf{x}) \\ R(\mathbf{x}) &= [1/2 - 1/2(x + y)]E_0(\mathbf{x}) \\ B(\mathbf{x}) &= [1/2 - 1/2(x - y)]E_0(\mathbf{x}), \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where x and y are the coordinates at the focal plane of the telecentric illumination system with $|x| \leq 1/2, |y| \leq 1/2$. These wedges are shown as individual components and composite color wedges in figure A.2. $E_0(\mathbf{x})$ is the spatially varying radiance without the color filters.

We now have three illuminations to determine two slope components. Thus, we can take one to compensate for unwanted spatial variation of E_0 . This can be done by normalizing the three color channels by the sum of all channels $G + R + B$:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{3G}{G + R + B} &= 1 + 2x \\ \frac{3(B - R)}{G + R + B} &= 2y. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.3})$$

Then the position on the wedge from which the light originates is given as

$$\begin{aligned} x &= \frac{3}{2} \frac{G}{G + R + B} - 1/2 \\ y &= \frac{3}{2} \frac{B - R}{G + R + B}. \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.4})$$

From these position values, the x and y components of the slope can be computed according to (A.1).

Figure A.2: *a* Color wedge produced by additive color mixing from the *b* green, *c* red, and *d* blue color wedges according to (A.2) for the shape from refraction technique for wave slope imaging.

Figure A.3: Demonstration of color ratio imaging used with the shape from refraction technique to measure the slope of water surfaces with a calibration target, a spherical lens. *a* Original color image; *b* intensity of the original image; watch the intensity fall off towards the edge of the lens (higher slopes); *c* color image normalized by *b*; *d* - *f* red, green, and blue channels of the original color image shown in discrete intensity steps; *g* and *h* *x*, *y* positions in the telecentric illumination system computed after (A.4). These quantities are according to (A.1) directly proportional to the *x* and *y* components of the surface slope.

Figure A.4: Demonstration of the suppression of intensity variations caused by bubbles and dirt at the bottom of the wind/wave facility with the 3-color shape from refraction technique: **a** Original image of the color wedge, **b** Color wedge normalized by total intensity.

Figure A.5: Example for the retrieval of the shape of short wind waves: **a** original color image of short wind waves with intensity variations (almost horizontal stripes) due to the illumination setup with multiple fluorescent lamps. **b** Reconstructed height. Reconstructed slope (surface gradient) in **c** x direction (along-wind) and **d** y direction (cross-wind).

How well the compensation works is shown in figure A.3. This target shows a constant curvature and thus — in first order — a linear decrease of the x and y components of the slope in x and y direction, respectively. Figure A.3d, e, and f show the significant intensity decrease towards the edge of the images, which even inverts the slope of the wedges. Without normalization it would lead to considerable errors in the slope values. Division by the sum of all color channels (figure A.3b) results in significantly better wedges (figure A.3c, g, and h).

Essentially, the normalization works well since now a position in the light source is no longer directly identified by the intensity but by a color, i. e., the ratio of intensities of differently colored illuminations. Figure A.4 demonstrates the suppression of intensity variation caused by bubbles and dirt at the bottom of the wind/wave facility and figure A.5 shows an example of the water surface slope and height images extracted from a raw color image.

4 Geometric and Radiometric Camera Calibration

On the one hand, it is one of the general principles of the research unit to use cheap and standard equipment wherever possible to allow for widespread application of the techniques and algorithms developed within the research unit. On the other hand, the accuracy demands for the applications in the research unit are high.

Static patterns caused by the nonuniformity in the dark current and sensitivity of the sensor elements cause a static pattern that limits the accuracy of motion estimation. High precision temperature measurements with IR cameras (projects B and D) and the measurement of faint intensity differences caused by absorption of trace gases in imaging spectrometers (projects B and C) require also the suppression of these static patterns.

Therefore a geometric and radiometric calibration of standard CCD cameras was regarded as an important task. The goal was to investigate to which degree the deficiencies of this equipment as compared to scientific-grade sensors could be compensated for and to which extent these techniques improve motion estimation.

4.1 Radiometric Calibration

The radiometric calibration study [*Sedig*, 1997] showed that CCD cameras are almost perfectly linear if the gamma factor is set to one. The radiometric responsivity, however, shows significant large-scale and small-scale spatial variations in the order of about 1%, which cannot be neglected and may show quite different spatial variations for different cameras (figure A.6a and b).

The fixed pattern noise without illumination is less serious. In the example shown in figure A.6c the amplitude of the patterns is well below one bit. Since these patterns are static, a simple two-point calibration significantly improves the image quality. All projects in the research unit benefit from this simple correction scheme. An easy to operate camera calibration setup is permanently installed and can be used on routine basis by all member of the research unit.

All the measurements discussed so far have been performed without any optical system and thus reflect only the properties of the CCD chip. The most serious distortion of a camera/lens system is the decrease in responsivity towards the edge of the field of view (figure A.6d). This effect is about 5 times higher than the nonuniformity of the CCD sensor elements. For absolute radiometric measurements it is required to correct this effect, which is very difficult to achieve. Fortunately most applications in the research unit require only a calibration relative to a given reference situation (see for instance the discussion about the differential optical absorption spectroscopy, DOAS, in project C).

4.2 Geometric Calibration

Schultz [1997] extended the classical photogrammetric techniques to calibrate the internal and external camera parameters to image sequences. This approach has the significant advantage that the degree of freedoms is significantly increased, especially if the motion is constraint.

One such setup utilizes a pendulum camera with only one degree of freedom for the motion (see sections 8 and D.3.8.2 and figure D.9). With such a setup all external camera parameters except for the rotation angle are the same for all images of a sequence.

Figure A.6: Examples for the radiometric calibration of standard CCD cameras: **a** Image of the relative responsivity for the JAI CV-M10 camera in a range of $\pm 3\%$. **b** same for the Pulnix TM740 camera. **c** Fixed pattern noise (without any illumination) for the JAI CV-M10 camera in a range of ± 0.5 bit. **d** Responsivity of a camera/lens system (JAI CV-M10 with Tamron $f=25\text{mm}$, 1:1.6) in a range of $\pm 15\%$. Note the strong decrease in sensitivity towards the edge of the field of view and the different effects of dirt on the class cover of the CCD sensor than in **a** and **b**.

5 Analytic Studies of Low-Level Motion Estimation

5.1 Motivation and Approach

With increasing mathematical foundation of computer vision, an exact study of the performance characterization of computer vision algorithms receives more and more attention. Recently, the DAGM-working group “Performance Characteristics of Pattern Recognition Algorithms” was founded [Förstner, 1997]. This is a local German activity embedded into similar European and international activities. This topic is of special interest for scientific applications and thus for the research unit since it is important to know to which extent the application of a certain algorithm introduces systematical or statistical errors into the data. In section 2 we have already discussed the requirements for image sequence algorithms in the research unit.

A substantial body of research is available for standard computer vision algorithms such as edge detection. However, only a few systematic studies of the performance characteristics of low-level motion estimators are available in the literature. Kearney *et al.* [1987] performed an error analysis of optical flow estimation with gradient-based methods, while Barron *et al.* [1994] used a set of computer-generated and real image sequences to compare various approaches to compute optical flow. Haglund and Fleet [1994] used a natural image and warped it to study the performance of phase-based and energy-based techniques. None of the above-cited papers includes an analytical study of the performance of different techniques. This is however one of the most promising and rigorous methods to characterize algorithms.

We started the investigation of this subject long before the foundation of the research unit [Jähne, 1993]. At that time the analysis was restricted to rather simple cases in spatiotemporal images mostly with only one space coordinate. Within the research unit, the techniques could be further generalized and also applied to 3-D spatiotemporal images and be verified by experiments with computer generated and real image sequences. These new results will be presented at the upcoming DAGM-workshop "Performance Characteristics and Quality of Computer Vision Algorithms" [Jähne, 1997b].

The basic requirement for an analytical study of low-level motion estimation is a unified approach that formulates the motion estimators as nonlinear differential operators in continuous spatiotemporal images. It has been shown that all known differential and tensorial methods contain terms of the form [Jähne, 1993]:

$$J_{pq}(\mathbf{x}) = \int w(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}', t - t') \partial_p g(\mathbf{x}', t') \partial_q g(\mathbf{x}', t') d^2 \mathbf{x}' dt' \quad (\text{A.5})$$

This operation can be performed as a cascade of linear convolution and (nonlinear) point operations:

$$B(\mathcal{D}_p \cdot \mathcal{D}_q), \quad (\text{A.6})$$

where B and \mathcal{D}_p are a smoothing filter and a derivative filter into the direction p .

The phase method, introduced by Fleet and Jepson [1990], deviates in as much from the previous methods that only normal velocities are determined from images filtered by a set of directional quadrature filters (q_+ and q_-). Alternatively Hilbert filters can be used once images are decomposed into directionpyramidal data structures [Jähne, 1993].

With this continuous formulation two significant advantages are gained over previous approaches.

- It is not required to make any specific assumptions about the types of gray value structures. Most importantly, it does not use Taylor expansions of the gray scale structure which give only approximate results. The following two classes of general continuous gray value structures are applied:

$$\begin{array}{ll} \text{planar wave, moving "edge"} & g(\mathbf{k}\mathbf{x} - \omega t) \\ \text{constant 2-D motion, moving "corner"} & g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{u}_0 t). \end{array} \quad (\text{A.7})$$

These elementary classes can be modified systematically by adding various types of noise and by including unsteady motion, motion discontinuities, and illumination changes.

- No errors introduced by the discretization of the operators are . In this way it is possible to distinguish principal flaws in an approach from errors in the implementation due to an inadequate numerical method. Often these two types of errors are mixed up in the literature.

5.2 Exactness and Bias by Noise

Under ideal conditions, i. e., a constant motion field, exact results are obtained with all techniques. If a spatially oriented gray value structure is encountered, only the velocity component in the direction of the gradient is obtained, but this value is also exact. It can be shown that errors in the estimation of optical flow are only introduced by an inadequate discretization of the partial derivative operators (compare section 6 below). Figure A.7 illustrates this basic fact with a simple numerical study. It shows the error in the motion estimate using a constantly moving random pattern. With the standard symmetric difference filter $1/2 [1 \ 0 \ -1]$, large deviations from the correct displacements up to 0.1 pixels/frame occur. With an optimized 3×3 Sobel-type filter [Schar et al., 1997], the error is well below 0.005 pixels/frame. Another interesting result is that an exact determination of the normal velocity with the phase method does not require a perfect Hilbert filter.

The different methods distinguish themselves in the estimation of the optical flow in noisy image sequences. We investigated this by adding isotropic zero-mean noise

$$g'(\mathbf{x}, t) = g(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{u}t) + n(\mathbf{x}, t).$$

assuming that the partial derivatives of the noise function are not correlated with themselves or the partial derivatives of the image patterns.

With the differential method two unfortunate things happen in noisy images. First, we always obtain a solution even in a local neighborhood with a constant gray value or a spatially oriented pattern. Thus

Figure A.7: Systematic error in the velocity estimate as a function of the interframe displacement measured with a moving random pattern. Derivatives computed with **a** the symmetric difference filter $1/2 [1 \ 0 \ -1]$ **b** an optimized Sobel filter [Schar et al., 1997] (figure from Jähne [1997b]).

Figure A.8: Systematic error in the velocity estimate with a moving random pattern using the least squares gradient method (**a**) and the tensor method (**b**) for velocities in x direction from 0 to 1.4 pixels/frame. The signal-to-noise ratio is 1 (from Jähne [1997b]).

it is no longer possible to distinguish constant neighborhoods from edges and corners. Second, the obtained estimate is erroneous. It is biased towards lower values. This is also verified by experiments as shown in figure A.8a. If the variance of the noise is about the squared magnitude of the gradient, the estimated values are only about half of the true values.

If otherwise the model assumptions of a constant motion are met in the local neighborhood, the coherency measures directly reflect the signal to noise ratio.

5.3 Unsteady Motion and Motion Discontinuities

An accelerated motion can be modeled by

$$g'(x, t) = g(x - ut - 1/2at^2). \quad (\text{A.8})$$

It is obvious that this modified model will influence only the temporal derivatives. A careful analysis shows that an accelerated motion field or a spatially inhomogeneous motion field generally causes two effects:

First, there is a general bias that occurs always and is proportional to the square of the acceleration and the spatial gradient of the motion. This term plays only a role at spatial motion discontinuities. Because of the inertia of the moving objects, the acceleration is normally so small that the bias associated with the acceleration is not significant.

A second effect is associated to the uneven distribution of the spatial derivatives in a local neighborhood. Since with all methods the terms are weighted in the one or other way with the square magnitude

of the gradient, the estimate of the velocity of that parts in the neighborhood with steep gradients have more weight. In the worst case the estimate gives a velocity which is not the velocity in the center of the neighborhood but shifted to the value at the edge of the neighborhood, i.e., at a earlier or later time or left or right from the center. These simple arguments give an easy estimate of the upper limit of the error in the velocity estimate.

With the tensor method it is also possible to study the decrease in the coherency. It turns out that the coherency is not sensitive to *gradual* changes in the velocity.

It is obvious that with a motion discontinuity in a local neighborhood simple motion estimators give no useful velocity estimate. Thus it is the most important task to detect those areas. With differential methods it is only possible to use the residual error between the modeled spatiotemporal gray value structure and the true spatiotemporal structure. Motion discontinuities also effect the coherency measures. They can lead to a significant drop in the coherency. However, the decrease in the coherency depends on the angle between the velocity vectors. In the case of perpendicular vectors, the coherency can drop down to zero. For small directional changes of the velocity, however, the coherency drop becomes insignificant.

In any case, a motion discontinuity at a straight line between two regions with random variations in the mean square gradient will not appear as a straight line in the optical flow image. It will rather become a wiggly line because of the bias caused by weighting. The deviation from the true discontinuity can be as much as half the mask size of the averaging filters. Here we have reached a point in the analysis of motion that cannot be solved on the base of local information alone. At this point, global information must be considered, such as the smoothness of boundaries.

5.4 Illumination Change

From a phase-based method we would expect that global illumination changes are entirely suppressed since only the phase and not the amplitude of the signal is used for the determination of displacements. This is indeed the case for global illumination changes; they are directly proportional to the gray value. Thus the phase method suppresses global illumination changes under very general assumptions. The tensor method does not directly suppress illumination changes. However, global illumination changes that occur everywhere in the image at the *same* time, constitute an oriented structure with infinite velocity and can thus be distinguished from any real motion and be filtered out by an appropriate velocity filter.

6 Filter Optimization

6.1 General Approach for First-Order Derivative Filters

The analytical studies of motion estimators discussed in section 5 pointed out the importance of optimization of discrete filter operations, especially first-order derivative filters.

The first question is what optimum form such a filter should have. At first glance, we expect that an optimum derivative filter in the direction p should have a transfer function that goes with ik_p . A careful analysis of the usage of derivative filters for motion estimation shows, however, that they only enter the nonlinear motion operators as ratios of filters in different direction. Thus we can multiply the transfer function of derivative filters in different directions with any *common* scalar and non-zero function. In order to yield an isotropic response this function should be isotropic, i.e., depend only on the magnitude of the wave number. This yields the following general ansatz for a first-order derivative filter in the direction p :

$$\hat{D}_p(\tilde{\mathbf{k}}) = (ik_p)\hat{B}(|\tilde{\mathbf{k}}|). \quad (\text{A.9})$$

This ansatz allows for a wide range of classes of derivative filters. If \hat{B} is the transfer function of an isotropic smoothing operator, it results in a class of regularized first-order filters.

6.2 Nonlinear Optimization Strategy

In order to achieve an effective filter, we started with separable filters. Each derivative filter is composed of a one-dimensional derivative filter that is smoothed in all other coordinate direction. This best known filter of this type is the Sobel operator. Under consideration of the symmetry of the cross smoothing,

Figure A.9: Magnitude of the angle error in degree for the gradient vector in the direction of the largest error (22.5°) for normalized wave numbers \tilde{k} from 0-0.6: **a** Sobel filter, **b** 3×3 -filter of Farid and Simoncelli [1997], **c** nonlinearly optimized 3×3 -filter, **d** 5×5 -filter of Farid and Simoncelli [1997], **e** nonlinearly optimized 5×5 -filter, **f** nonlinearly optimized 5×5 -filter with additional optimization of all free parameters. Please note the different scaling of the y axes.

we leave the coefficients free to be optimized. For 3×3 and 5×5 filters this leads to the convolution masks

$${}^3D_x = \frac{1}{2} [1 \ 0 \ -1] * \begin{bmatrix} p_1 \\ 1 - 2p_1 \\ p_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad {}^5D_x = \frac{1}{12} [-1 \ 8 \ 0 \ -8 \ 1] * \begin{bmatrix} p_1 \\ p_2 \\ 1 - 2(p_1 + p_2) \\ p_2 \\ p_1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.10})$$

and the transfer functions

$$\begin{aligned} {}^3\hat{D}_x &= \sin(\pi\tilde{k}_x) (1 - 2p_1(1 - \cos(\pi\tilde{k}_y))) \\ {}^5\hat{D}_x &= (4/3 \sin(\pi\tilde{k}_x) - 1/6 \sin(2\pi\tilde{k}_x)) (1 - 2p_1(1 - \cos(2\pi\tilde{k}_y)) - 2p_2(1 - \cos(\pi\tilde{k}_y))) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A.11})$$

The derivative filters into the other directions can be formulated analogously. A similar approach has been used by *Simoncelli* [1994] and *Farid and Simoncelli* [1997]. Our approach differs by the formulation of the error function. While *Simoncelli* [1994] applied a linear error functional, we use a nonlinear one by minimizing the angle error of the gradient vector. For a 2-D derivate filter this resulted, for example, into

$$\left\| w(|\mathbf{k}|) \left(\arctan \frac{\tilde{k}_y}{\tilde{k}_x} - \arctan \frac{\hat{D}_y(p_i)}{\hat{D}_x(p_i)} \right) \right\|_n \rightarrow \min. \quad (\text{A.12})$$

An arbitrary isotropic weighting function $w(|\mathbf{k}|)$ allows for adjusting the optimization for certain wave number range. For 3-D filters, the equations become significantly more complex but still can be handled [*Scharr et al.*, 1997]. The nonlinear optimization was computed both with the Euclidian and the maximum norm.

6.3 Results

Figure A.9 shows the residual errors in the direction of the gradient for 3×3 and 5×5 filters optimized for the weighting function

$$w(\tilde{\mathbf{k}}) = \cos^2(\pi\tilde{k}_x/2) \cos^2(\pi\tilde{k}_y/2), \quad (\text{A.13})$$

Figure A.10: 3D visualization of an xt image cube. The upper front corner on the right hand side has been cut out to show the internal gray value structure of the image cube. The sequence shows the temperature distribution of the ocean surface acquired with the Amber Radiance 1 infrared camera (subproject B).

corresponding to wave number distribution as it occurs in slightly smoothed images. The optimized filters show about 20 to 40 times lower error margins in the mean. While the widely used Sobel filter has a directional error at $\tilde{k} = 0.6$ of about 6° , the error is well about 1° at $\tilde{k} = 0.6$ and well below 0.2° for $\tilde{k} < 0.5$ for the optimized filter. They are also significantly better than the corresponding filter of *Farid and Simoncelli* [1997], which still shows an error up to 3° . The filters are also significantly better than the directionally corrected derivative filters based on a recursive implementation of the Canny filter [*Lanser and Eckstein*, 1991].

The optimization of the first-order derivative filters was a key point for the improvement of the low-level displacement estimators from errors in the order of 1/10 pixels/frame to well below 0.01 pixel/frame (compare section 5 and figure A.7). It is amazing to see that this degree of accuracy can be achieved with a simple separable 3×3 derivative filter which can be computed with the same efficiency as the standard Sobel filter. Given the tremendous success of this new approach to filter optimization and its significant importance to extract accurate motion information for *all* applications in the research unit, we will continue and extend this work as outlined in section 3.2.2 of the renewal proposal of the core project A.

7 Tensor-Based Low-Level Motion Estimation

For many applications of the research unit the accuracy of low level motion estimation is a crucial factor in contrast to the more qualitative requirements of standard computer vision applications. Investigating dynamic processes the displacement vector field (DVF) has to be computed with high accuracy, since subsequent computations of higher order properties, such as divergence and convergence, suffer from errors in the DVF. The tensor approach, which has successfully been used in 2-D images for orientation analysis, has been extended to motion analysis in space-time images [*Haußecker and Jähne*, 1996 and 1997]. Using the 3-D *structure tensor*, dense displacement vector fields can be computed with subpixel accuracy. The approach is based on the detection of linear symmetries and the corresponding orientation angle within a local spatiotemporal neighborhood.

A major challenge during phase I was an efficient and fast implementation of the structure tensor technique in order to apply it to extended image series on all available computer systems. A versatile implementation could be realized using only standard low-level image processing operators that can be optimized and adapted to the image content. In addition to the displacement vector field the implementation of the structure tensor technique yields a measure of certainty as well as a measure for the type of motion quantifying the presence of an aperture problem. This allows the technique to automatically adapt to local spatiotemporal image structures without additional heuristic parameters. After implementing the technique extensive performance studies have been carried out. They include

a variety of test sequences as well as real scientific applications of several subprojects. Among the applications are growth studies in plant leaves (subproject D), displacement vector fields of the ocean surface from IR image sequences (subproject B), phase speed of water surface waves (subproject B) and 3-D reconstruction with a single moving camera (subproject D). Meanwhile we have also applied the structure tensor technique to the study of transport and erosion processes in river sediments (see figure A.17) in a cooperation with the Federal Waterway Engineering and Research Institute (Bundesanstalt für Wasserbau, BAW), Karlsruhe [Beringer, 1998; Spies, 1998].

7.1 Computing Displacements in Spatiotemporal Images

The displacement of gray value structures within consecutive images of a sequence yields inclined image structures with respect to the temporal axis of spatiotemporal images. Figure A.10 shows an example of a 3D space-time image. A sequence of infrared images of the water surface has been stacked to build a cube. The relation between the orientation angle and the optical flow is given by

$$\mathbf{f} = - \begin{bmatrix} \tan \varphi_x \\ \tan \varphi_y \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

where $\mathbf{f} = (f_x, f_y)$ denotes the optical flow on the image plane and the angles φ_x and φ_y define the angles between the plane normal to the lines of constant grey value and the x and y axes, respectively [Jähne, 1997a]. This basic property of spatiotemporal images allows to estimate the optical flow from a 3D orientation analysis, searching for the direction of constant gray value in $\mathbf{x}t$ -space.

In order to determine local orientation *Bigün and Granlund* [1987] proposed a tensor representation of the local grey value distribution. Using directional derivatives, *Kass and Witkin* [1987] came to a solution that turned out to be equivalent to the tensor method. Searching for a general description of local orientation *Knutsson* [1989] concluded that local structure in an W -dimensional space can be represented by a symmetric $W \times W$ tensor. *Rao* [1990] used a similar tensor representation for 2D texture analysis. One possible realization of *Knutsson's* tensor is the *structure tensor*, \mathbf{J} :

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \nabla g(\mathbf{x}') \nabla^T g(\mathbf{x}') d^W \mathbf{x}'. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

The components of \mathbf{J} are given by

$$J_{pq} = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} h(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}') \frac{\partial g(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial x_p} \frac{\partial g(\mathbf{x}')}{\partial x_q} d^W \mathbf{x}'. \quad (\text{A.16})$$

With $g(\mathbf{x})$ we denote the spatiotemporal image structure and $\partial g(\mathbf{x})/\partial x_q$ represents the partial derivation along the direction of the x_q -axis. The information within a local neighborhood U around the central point $\mathbf{x} = (x, y, t)$ is weighted by a window-function $h(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}')$. In practical applications the size of the local neighborhood U represents the area and time (in numbers of images) over which the orientation information is averaged.

The structure tensor contains the entire information about the geometrical distribution of gray values within the local spatiotemporal neighborhood. The orientation of iso-gray value lines within a 3D spatiotemporal neighborhood U can mathematically be formulated as the direction $\bar{\mathbf{n}}$ being as much perpendicular to all gray value gradients ∇g in U as possible, i. e.

$$S = \int_U \left(\bar{\mathbf{n}}^T(\mathbf{x}') \nabla g(\mathbf{x}') \right)^2 d^W \mathbf{x}' \rightarrow \text{minimum}, \quad \bar{\mathbf{n}}^T \nabla g = n_x \frac{\partial g}{\partial x} + n_y \frac{\partial g}{\partial y} + n_t \frac{\partial g}{\partial t}. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

It can be shown that this expression is minimized if the vector $\bar{\mathbf{n}}$ is given by the *eigenvector* of the tensor \mathbf{J} to the *minimum eigenvalue* [Rao, 1990]. The search for local orientation therefore reduces to an *eigenvalue analysis* of the structure tensor \mathbf{J} .

The structure tensor proved to be a very elegant approach to low-level motion estimation that incorporates several advantages relevant to the research unit:

Versatility. The structure tensor approach neither does depend on the shape of the greyvalue structure of the images nor on the spatial distribution of the displacement vector field. This allows this technique to be applied to a variety of applications without a priori information of the image content.

Multidimensionality. The structure tensor approach is independent from the dimensionality of the vector space and therefore yields the same solution for multidimensional image structures without change. Within the research unit 2D xt images can be evaluated as well as 3D image sequences and the same technique can be extended to 4D volumetric image sequences. Furthermore the computational costs do not explode with increasing dimensionality since the necessary computations consist of *separable* filter operations that can be individually optimized.

Multichannel images. Multichannel images that are frequently encountered in the application projects of the research unit do not have to be treated separately. The structure tensor can be computed from the individual components. The following steps can either be applied to the components separately or to a linear combination of the components. In cases where the components encode the multispectral information of a single displacement vector field this fusion of information helps to eventually fill in gaps and to overcome the aperture problem.

7.2 Practical Implementation

Regarding the structure tensor technique the main task of subproject A during phase I was to develop an efficient and fast implementation in order to apply this technique to extended image sequences. The implementation had to be efficient enough to use it in all subprojects on all available computers, even on those with low memory and slow processors. In close cooperation with the application projects of the research unit an implementation has been developed that allowed the structure tensor technique to be applied to a variety of image sequences. This feedback of the applications to the core project A led to a very versatile algorithm that can be used even from non-experienced users. Instead of the need for a priori knowledge of parameters the structure technique itself extracts parameters necessary to compute higher order properties of the displacement vector field. These parameters include a measure of overall certainty (*coherency measure*) and a measure to quantify the presence of an aperture problem (*edge measure*). These normalized features proved to be well suited as an input for local regularization schemes in order to compute a local estimation of the displacement vector field.

Without going into detail the basic properties and advantages of the practical implementation for 3D xt sequences will be outlined in the following sections.

7.2.1 Computing the Structure Tensor

The implementation of the tensor components can be carried out very efficiently by standard image processing operators. Identifying the convolution in (A.16) with a 3D spatiotemporal smoothing of the product of partial derivatives, each component of the structure tensor can be computed as

$$J_{pq} = \mathcal{B}(\mathcal{D}_p \cdot \mathcal{D}_q), \quad (\text{A.18})$$

with the 3D spatiotemporal smoothing operator \mathcal{B} and the differential operator \mathcal{D}_p in the direction of the coordinate x_p . Using a binomial operator the smoothing can be performed very efficiently on a multigrid data structure [Haußecker, 1995]. This allows reducing the data and therefore the computations of all following steps by a factor of 4. The computation of the pyramidal structure could be accelerated — a reduction of computational costs from the order of N^2 to the order of $\text{ld}N$ — by a special multigrid structure exploiting the features of transfer functions of binomial filters.

Another critical point is the choice of an appropriate differential operator. It can be shown that derivative filters optimized for a minimum deviation from the correct direction of the gradient vector reduce the error by more than an order of magnitude as compared to standard differential operators ([Schar, 1997], see section 6).

7.2.2 Eigenvalue Analysis

A standard procedure in numerical eigenvalue analysis is the *Jacobi transformation* [Press et al., 1992]. The Jacobi method is absolutely foolproof for all real symmetric matrices which the structure tensor can be assured to be. This is very advantageous, because it does not depend on the image content. In order to speed up the whole eigenvalue analysis, a major decrease in computation time can be achieved by preselecting interesting image regions. One possible method that proved to accelerate the computation without losing important information is to analyze the *trace* of the matrix, $\text{trace}(\mathbf{J}) = J_{xx} + J_{yy} + J_{tt}$, for each point before starting the Jacobi transformation. Since the trace of a matrix is invariant under orthogonal similarity transformations this can be done in advance after computing the structure tensor.

Figure A.11: Illustration of the two principal types of motion and their manifestation in the eigenvalues of the structure tensor. The eigenvalues E_1, \dots, E_3 are represented by the length of the 3 principal axes of an ellipsoid. **a** Distributed spatial structure and constant motion. **b** Spatial orientation and constant motion (aperture problem).

The case of constant gray value corresponds to $\text{trace}(J) = 0$ and these areas of no apparent orientation can be excluded from the eigenvalue analysis by just adding up the diagonal elements and thresholding the result.

7.2.3 Computing Displacements

If all eigenvalues of the structure tensor are either zero or of the same magnitude, no apparent linear motion is present in the local neighborhood. These cases correspond to a uniform brightness, isotropic noise or fast accelerations.

If only one of the three eigenvectors has an eigenvalue larger than zero an image structure showing a local spatial orientation moves with a constant velocity. This is the well known *aperture problem* in optical flow computation. The eigenvector with nonzero eigenvalue points normal to the plane of constant grey value in 3D space and can be used to compute the normal optical flow f^\perp (see figure A.11b).

If an isotropic gray value structure moves with a constant velocity no aperture problem is present in the spatiotemporal neighborhood. The orientation of the 3D iso-gray-value line yields the two components f_x and f_y of the optical flow f . These can be computed from the eigenvector to the smallest eigenvalue pointing into the direction of the line (see figure A.11a).

These possible cases show that the structure tensor method is able to distinguish between different types of motion and to simultaneously compute the relevant motion parameters. The aperture problem cannot be solved in general, since it constitutes a physical shortcoming, but it can be identified by the eigenvalues of the structure tensor. This identification is very important in order to interpret the result of the motion analysis appropriately. If it could not be identified the projected motion f^\perp would be treated as the real motion f which can lead to tremendous errors.

7.2.4 Coherency and Type Measures

For practical applications of the structure tensor technique it was necessary to find normalized measures to quantify the type of motion in a local neighborhood in order to automatically adapt to the image content. Analyzing the possible classes of motion and the corresponding eigenvalues the two following measures proved to be useful:

$$\text{coh} = \left(\frac{\lambda_l - \lambda_s}{\lambda_l + \lambda_s} \right)^2 \quad \text{and} \quad \text{edge} = \left(\frac{\lambda_l - \lambda_m}{\lambda_l + \lambda_m} \right)^2, \quad (\text{A.19})$$

with λ_l , λ_m , and λ_s denoting the largest, medium, and smallest eigenvalue of the structure tensor, respectively. Table A.1 shows the values of coh and edge for different classes of motion. For both types of apparent motion, i. e., aperture problem and no aperture problem, coh is equal to one. If no displacement can be computed it is identical zero. With increasing noise level coh approaches zero for all different types of motion. Only if an aperture problem is present edge reaches its maximum value of coh . For all other types of motion it is equal to zero. The edge measure is normalized between 0.0

and coh since it is not possible to detect the presence of an aperture problem more reliably than the overall certainty.

Motion type	coh	edge
Constant grey value, no motion	0	0
Spatial orientation and constant motion (moving edge)	1	1
Distributed spatial structure and constant motion	1	0
No coherent motion (motion discontinuities, fast accelerations, ...)	0	0

Table A.1: Coherency and edge measure for different types of motion.

7.2.5 Local Regularization

For all image points with a high coherency measure, coh, and a simultaneously low edge measure, edge, i. e. $\text{coh} - \text{edge} \approx \text{coh}$, the 2D displacement vector field \mathbf{f} can be computed. In order to get an estimate of \mathbf{f} in the presence of an aperture problem we assume \mathbf{f} to be constant within a local neighborhood $U' > U$, with U denoting the local neighborhood of the structure tensor computation. For every point suffering from the aperture problem the projected displacement f^\perp is related to \mathbf{f} by $f^\perp = \mathbf{f}^T \bar{\mathbf{n}}$, where $\bar{\mathbf{n}}$ is the normal vector perpendicular to the edge (figure A.12a and b).

For M points in the neighborhood this results in the linear equation system

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_1^\perp \\ \vdots \\ f_M^\perp \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} n_{x,1} & n_{y,1} \\ \vdots & \vdots \\ n_{x,M} & n_{y,M} \end{bmatrix} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} f_x^{est} \\ f_y^{est} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{A.20})$$

for the estimated displacement \mathbf{f}^{est} . For $M > 2$ the system is over determined and can be solved by the "pseudo inverse":

$$\begin{bmatrix} f_x^{est} \\ f_y^{est} \end{bmatrix} = d \begin{bmatrix} N_{yy}N_{xf} - N_{xy}N_{yf} \\ N_{xx}N_{yf} - N_{xy}N_{xf} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

with

$$N_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^M n_{i,k}n_{j,k}, \quad N_{if} = \sum_{k=1}^M n_{i,k}f_k^\perp, \quad \text{and} \quad d = (N_{xx}N_{yy} - N_{xy}^2)^{-1}. \quad (\text{A.22})$$

For practical implementation the sum in (A.22) can be replaced by a 2D smoothing of the point-wise products with the 2D binomial operator \mathcal{B} : $N_{ij} = \mathcal{B}(n_i \cdot n_j)$ and $N_{if} = \mathcal{B}(n_i \cdot f^\perp)$. The determinant d plays an important role, since (A.21) is only solvable if the denominator of d is $\neq 0$. The denominator of d is zero only if all normal vectors $\bar{\mathbf{n}}$ within U' are linearly dependent from each other. Only for changing directions of $\bar{\mathbf{n}}$ within U' (A.20) yields more information than one single value of f^\perp .

Since d^{-1} is normalized between 1.0 for distributed edges in all directions and 0.0 for parallel edges, it can be used as a *measure of orthogonality* to quantify the certainty of the computation of \mathbf{f}^{est} .

Figure A.12c and d show the result of this *back projection technique*. The moving ring pattern of figure A.13c suffers from the aperture problem over the entire ring area. However, the directions of the edges change within a local neighborhood. The projected DVF $\mathbf{f}^\perp = f^\perp \bar{\mathbf{n}}$, shown in figure A.12c is used to compute the estimated DVF \mathbf{f}^{est} in figure A.12d which corresponds to the real displacement with high accuracy.

Although the assumption of a constant displacement vector field within a local neighborhood constitutes a very crude approximation of real displacement vector fields in some cases it gives very accurate estimates for smoothly varying displacement vector fields and proved to be very useful in some applications of the research unit. In growth studies of plant leaves as well as in temperature images of the ocean surface mainly line-shaped structures are visible. Therefore almost all areas contributing to the displacement vector field suffer from the aperture problem. The smoothness of the displacement vector field is guaranteed by the physical properties of the observed objects and therefore the local regularization technique could be successfully applied. This example demonstrates how knowledge of the physical properties allows to significantly improve low-level motion estimation.

Figure A.12: Illustration of the local regularization technique in order to overcome the aperture problem within a local neighborhood of distributed local orientation. **a** Aperture problem. **b** Projection of the real displacement on locally distributed edges. **c** Displacement vector field $f^+(\mathbf{x})$ computed with the structure tensor. **d** Result of the regularization technique $f^{est}(\mathbf{x})$.

Figure A.13: Results of the structure tensor technique for different test patterns. The intensity of the arrows quantifies the coherency coh. The measures coh, edge and coh - edge are scaled from black (0.0) to white (1.0). **a** Spatially distributed noise moving with constant velocity $\mathbf{f} = (-1.0, -1.0)$ pixels/frame. **b** Diamond shaped object moving with constant velocity $\mathbf{f} = (-1.0, 0.0)$ pixels/frame. **c** Ring pattern moving with constant velocity $\mathbf{f} = (-1.0, -1.0)$ pixels/frame. **d** Ring pattern moving with constant velocity $\mathbf{f} = (-1.0, -1.0)$ pixels/frame with distributed additive noise, $LNP = 0.5$ (A.23).

For further improvement we plan to extend this technique to motion discontinuities and to a linear model of the displacement vector field $\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}_0 + \mathbf{A}\Delta\mathbf{x}$ within a local neighborhood. The matrix \mathbf{A} contains the four possible types of spatial displacement variations of a surface element: rotation, dilation, stretch and shearing.

Although the mathematical formalism of this approach is similar to the differential least squares approach in optical flow computation there are significant differences. The least squares approach uses the prerequisite of constant or linearly changing displacement vector field throughout the entire image area to compute displacement vectors. It is 'blind' to areas of ideally oriented structures where the real 2D displacement can be computed. The local regularization technique is only applied to image areas that are identified to suffer from the aperture problem. It uses the available information f^\perp which has been computed with high accuracy in order to estimate the DVF in a local neighborhood.

7.3 Results

Performing comparative analytical performance studies of low-level motion estimators (see section 5) *Jähne* [1997b] showed that the structure tensor technique yields exact results under ideal conditions, that it is quite insensitive to inhomogeneous and accelerated motion and additionally is not biased by noise. In order to check these results a variety of performance tests with computer generated test sequences, laboratory calibration sequences and real application sequences have been carried out.

7.3.1 Test Sequences

Figure A.13 shows four different computer-generated test patterns together with the coherency measure, coh , the edge measure, edge , and the computed DVF. The spatially distributed noise pattern moving with constant motion in figure A.13a has a high value for the coherency and simultaneously a low value for the edge measure. However, some areas show edge-like structures that are due to random nonuniformities in the noise pattern. The diamond shaped pattern in figure A.13b clearly exhibits a high coherency along the object border which splits up into the edges and corners, respectively.

A moving ring pattern is shown with (figure A.13c) and without (figure A.13d) additional noise. While noise does not change the resulting DVF at points of sufficiently high coherency, the coherency drops all over the entire image showing the strongest decrease in areas of low spatial gray value variations. In these areas the noise locally gets dominant over the image pattern. It is important to note that these areas can be identified and that the DVF can be accurately computed within the remaining areas.

7.3.2 Local Noise Portion

Defining the *local noise portion* (LNP) as the ratio between the noise variance σ_n^2 and the local variance $\text{var}_B(g_n) = B(g_n)^2 - (Bg_n)^2$ of the noisy image g_n

$$LNP = \frac{\sigma_n^2}{\text{var}_B(g_n)} = \frac{\sigma_n^2}{\text{var}_B(g) + \sigma_n^2}, \quad (\text{A.23})$$

we get a normalized measure quantifying the presence of noise within a local neighborhood. A value of $LNP = 0.5$ means that the noise variance lies in the same order as the local variance $\text{var}_B(g)$ of the noise-free pattern g . The local noise portion (LNP) proved to be a more appropriate measure of the noise influence than the classical signal to noise ratio (SNR), defining the ratio of the squared signal amplitude to the noise variance. For local filter operations, such as the structure tensor, only the signal variation within the area of influence of the filters contributes to the quality of the result rather than the signal amplitude within the entire image area. Furthermore the signal to noise ratio is hard to compute for real images, because it is usually not clear how the signal amplitude is defined.

7.3.3 Moving Calibration Pattern

Computer-generated test sequences always constitute optimal examples missing all errors superimposed by the camera and image acquisition system (section 4). A variety of accuracy tests performed with computer-generated test sequences confirmed the results of *Jähne* [1997b] (see section 5). In order to compare the displacement vector fields computed by the structure tensor technique with real displacements of objects observed by a camera system the geometric calibration setup (see section 4) was used.

A calibration pattern was moved vertically along a linear positioning table. At a series of equidistant positions a single frame was acquired. Figure A.14b shows a frame of the calibration sequence together with the coherency, edge and corner measures of the structure tensor technique. This example clearly illustrates how the grid structure of the target shows up in the coherency measure which additionally splits up in the edge and corner measures showing the lines and crossing points, respectively.

For each frame the geometric positions of the crossing points have been computed by the subpixel matching algorithm of the geometric calibration procedure (section 4). The averaged displacements agree very well with those computed by the structure tensor technique. The deviation is less than 0.01 pixels/frame (table A.2). While the geometric calibration procedure fits the positions of the crossing points of the grid, the structure tensor technique computes displacements for each pixel close to the crossing points with a high coherency, coh , and simultaneously low edge measure, edge . The corresponding variances of the displacement in table A.2 have been computed from these points, respectively. This example illustrates that the theoretical accuracy of the structure tensor technique to detect displacements of less than 0.01 pixels/frame can be reached with real image data.

Figure A.14: Calibration pattern used to compare the displacement vector field of the structure tensor technique with the real displacement computed with the geometric calibration procedure. **a** Original image of the calibration pattern. **b** Coherency measure, *coh*. **c** Edge measure, *edge*. **d** Corner measure, *coh - edge*.

Table A.2: Comparison of interframe displacements within a series of 7 images computed with the structure tensor and the subpixel matching of the geometric calibration procedure (see section 4).

frame number		1	2	3	4	5	6	7
structure tensor	f_y	0.2079	0.2076	0.2076	0.2077	0.2083	0.2094	0.2104
	$\text{var}(f_y)$	0.0037	0.0037	0.0038	0.0039	0.0038	0.0038	0.0039
subpixel matching	f_y	0.2095	0.2117	0.2114	0.2106	0.2100	0.2168	0.2147
	$\text{var}(f_y)$	0.00011	0.00007	0.00006	0.00006	0.00001	0.00010	0.00009

7.3.4 Application Examples

The structure tensor technique has been applied to a variety of application examples from project B (IR sea surface temperature images and wave slope images), project D (optical leaf growth analysis) and various standard scenes of computer vision, including the Hamburg Taxi scene and infrared images of pedestrians. It proved to work well without any specific adaptation to the image content. Figure A.15 shows examples of such sequences. As a nice detail the pedestrian in figure A.15a is about to lift his right leg which is clearly visible in the DVF. A detailed description of the results from the structure tensor technique can be found in the reports of the application subprojects. In figure A.15 only a qualitative overview is given.

A more quantitative performance study of the tensor technique has been carried out for the infrared sea surface temperature images (controlled flux technique, CFT, subproject B), since it is difficult to verify the result by the displacement vector field only. Figure A.16 illustrates the test procedure. After computing the displacement vector field frame #4 of the sequence has been shifted (warped) by the computed displacement with subpixel accuracy for every pixel. This warped image constitutes an estimate for the real consecutive frame #5 of the sequence (motion compensation), which can be checked by a cross correlation of frame #5 and the warped image. Figure A.16 exhibits that the remaining differences in between the two images correspond to less than 1 pixel/frame. This constitutes an upper limit for the error since the warping algorithm itself imposes additional errors that cannot be separated from errors in the computed displacement.

As a result of the success of the structure tensor technique in the research unit the same technique has been applied in a cooperation with the Federal Waterway Engineering and Research Institute (Bundesanstalt für Wasserbau, BAW), Karlsruhe, to study erosion processes in river sediments [Beringer, 1998; Spies, 1998]. Figure A.17 shows an example of a sand grain moving along a cavity within the sediment and the corresponding displacement vector field detected by the structure tensor technique.

Figure A.15: Results for different kinds of sequences. **a** IR image of a pedestrian (64×64 pixels). **b** Hamburg taxi scene (128×128 pixels). **c** IR image of the ocean surface (128×128 pixels). **d** Growing leaf of a castor-oil plant (512×512 pixels). The arrows visualize the computed displacement vector field. The intensity of the arrows quantifies the coherency coh. A black arrow symbolizes high certainty. It shows that the coherency is correlated with image structures and drops when no structures are present. Black dots show areas with high coherency but no apparent motion.

Figure A.16: Motion compensation of CFT images.

Figure A.17: Application example: Detection of erosion processes in river sediments.

Figure A.18: Image sequence of a plant leaf taken with a camera mounted on a pendulum: **a** and **b** first and last image of the sequence, **c** and **d** space-time slice at the upper and lower marked lines in **a** and **b**, respectively.

8 3-D Reconstruction with a Single Moving Camera

8.1 Principle

The principle of continuous space-time images can also be applied to 3-D reconstruction. This means that a single moving camera continuously taking images replaces a stereo camera setup. This direction of research was initiated almost a decade ago by the work of *Bolles et al.* [1987] who introduced epipolar-plane image analysis, as a method to extract structure from motion with a camera moving along a linear path with a viewing direction orthogonal to the travel direction. Later this work was extended to more general camera movements [*Baker and Bolles*, 1989].

This approach has significant advantages over a stereo or multi-camera setup for 3-D reconstruction. First, a single camera is sufficient. This is a major advantage if expensive cameras such as infrared and scientific-grade cameras are required. Second, the differential errors in the geometrical and radiometric calibration between two or more cameras are avoided. Third, the correspondence problem is avoided. The disparity indicating depth in a stereo camera setup is replaced by depth-dependent orientations of gray value structures in spatiotemporal images. Forth, occlusions no longer pose an intractable problem. Occlusions are no longer just regions of missing correspondence between two stereo images but become *events* in spatiotemporal images.

8.2 Preliminary Results

The pendulum camera has been built (compare the discussion in section D.3.8.2) and some first image sequences have been taken (figure A.18 and A.19). The images nicely demonstrate that different depths show up as different orientations in spatiotemporal slices. They also show that occlusions are singular events in the spatiotemporal slices. Given the high accuracy of the tensor-based motion estimators (section 7), we expect that a depth reconstruction technique based on spatiotemporal image processing will be much more accurate than standard stereo techniques. Section 3.2.6 of the renewal proposal for the core project outlines further details about this technique we intend to perform in phase II of the research unit.

Figure A.19: Occlusion detection in 3-D reconstruction from space-time images of a moving camera demonstrated with a crumpled sheet of paper. **a** and **b** first and last image of the sequence, **c** and **d** space-time slice at the upper and lower marked lines in **a** and **b**, respectively.

References

- [1] Baker, H. H., and R. C. Bolles, 1989. Generalizing epipolar-plane image analysis on the spatiotemporal surface, *Int. J. Comp. Vision*, 3, 33-49.
- [2] Balschbach, G., and B. Jähne, 1997. Neigungsmessung der wellenbewegten Wasseroberfläche mittels Farbbildverarbeitung, Abstract accepted for Workshop Farbbildverarbeitung, 25.-26.9.97, Erlangen.
- [3] Barron, J. L., D. J. Fleet, and S. Beauchemin., 1994. Performance of optical flow techniques, *Int. J. Computer Vision*, 12 (1), 43-77.
- [4] Beringer, O., 1998. Diploma thesis, Univ. Heidelberg, in preparation.
- [5] Bigün, J. and G. H. Granlund, 1987. Optimal Orientation Detection of Linear Symmetry, Proc. First Intern. Conf. on Comp. Vision, ICCV, London, June 8-11.
- [6] Blake, A., and A. Yuille, eds., 1992. *Active Vision*, MIT Press, Cambridge, MA
- [7] Bolles, R. C., H. H. Baker, and D. H. Marimont, 1987. Epipolar-plane image analysis: an approach to determining structure from motion, *Int. J. Comp. Vision*, 1, 7-55.
- [8] Farid, H., and E. Simoncelli, 1997. Optimally Rotation-Equivariant Directional Derivative Kernels, In *7th Int'l Conf Computer Analysis of Images and Patterns*, Kiel.
- [9] Fleet, D. J., and A. D. Jepson, 1990. Computation of component image velocity from local phase information, *Int. J. Comp. Vision*, 5, 77-104.
- [10] Förstner, W, 1997. Performance Characteristics of Pattern Recognition Algorithms, Draft for a DAGM Working Group, May 1997.
- [11] Haglund, L., and D. J. Fleet, 1994. Stable estimation of image orientation, In *Proceedings ICIP'94, Austin 1994, Vol. III*, pages 68-72, IEEE Computer Society Press, Los Alamitos.

- [12] Haußecker, H. and B. Jähne, 1995. Effiziente Filterverfahren auf Mehrgitter-Datenstrukturen, Bildverarbeitung 95': Forschen, Entwickeln, Anwenden, Symposium, 29. 11. -01. 12. 95, pp. 43-57, Technische Akademie Esslingen, R. J. Ahlers, Hrsg.
- [13] Haußecker, H., 1996. Lokale Orientierung als Basis für die Texturanalyse, 3. Heidelberger Bildverarbeitungsforum: Texturanalyse, 02. Juli 1996, Forschungszentrum ABB AG, Heidelberg.
- [14] Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, 1996. A tensor approach for local structure analysis in multi-dimensional images, Proc. *3D Image Analysis and Synthesis '96*, Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, 18.-19. November 1996, B. Girod, H. Niemann, H.-P. Seidel (Hrsg), Proc. in Artificial Intelligence 3, infix, Sankt Augustin, pp. 171-178.
- [15] Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, 1997. A tensor approach for precise computation of dense displacement vector fields, Proc. *Mustererkennung 1997*, Braunschweig, 15-17. September 1997, F. Wahl and E. Paulus (eds.), Informatik Aktuell, Springer, Berlin, in press.
- [16] Horn, B. K. P., 1977. Understanding image intensities, *Artificial Intelligence*, 8, 201-231.
- [17] Jähne, B., 1993. *Spatio-Temporal Image Processing, Theory and Scientific Applications*, Lecture Notes in Computer Science, Vol. 751, Springer, Berlin.
- [18] Jähne, B., 1997a. *Digital Image Processing — Concepts, Algorithms, and Scientific Applications*, 4th completely revised edition, Springer, Berlin, in press.
- [19] B. Jähne, 1997b. Performance characteristics of low-level motion estimators in spatiotemporal images, Proc. *Workshop Performance Characteristics and Quality of Computer Vision Algorithms*, Braunschweig, 18-19. September 1997, W. Foerstner (ed.), in press.
- [20] Jähne, B., H. Haußecker, F. Hering, G. Balschbach, J. Klinke, M. Lell, D. Schmundt, M. Schultz, U. Schurr, M. Stitt, and U. Platt, 1996. The role of active vision in exploring growth, transport, and exchange processes. Proc. *Aktives Sehen in technischen und biologischen Systemen*, Workshop der GI-Fachgruppe 1.0.4. Bildverstehen Hamburg, 3-4. December 1996, B Mertsching (Hrsg), Proc. in Artificial Intelligence 4, infix, Sankt Augustin, pp. 194-202.
- [21] Jähne, B., J. Klinke, and S. Waas, 1994. Imaging of short ocean wind waves: a critical theoretical review, *J. Optical Soc. Amer. A*, 11, 2197-2209.
- [22] Kass, M. and A. Witkin, 1987. Analyzing Oriented Patterns, *Comp. Vision Graphics and Image Proc.*, 37, pp. 362-385.
- [23] Kearney, J. K., W. B. Thompson, and D. L. Boley, 1987. Optical flow estimation: an error analysis of gradient-based methods with local optimization, *IEEE Trans. PAMI*, 9 (2):229-244.
- [24] Knutsson, H., 1989. Representing Local Structure using Tensors, 6th Scandinavian Conf. Image Analysis, Oulu, Finland, pp. 244-251.
- [25] Lanser, S. und W. Eckstein, 1991. Eine Modifikation des Deriche-Verfahrens zur Kantendetektion, In *13. DAGM Symposium Mustererkennung 1991*, B. Radig (ed.), Springer, Berlin, p. 151-158,
- [26] Mertsching, B. (ed.), 1996. Aktives Sehen in technischen und biologischen Systemen, Workshop der GI-Fachgruppe 1.0.4 Bildverstehen, Hamburg, Dezember 1996, infix, Sankt Augustin.
- [27] Press, W. H., S. A. Teukolsky, W. T. Vetterling and , B. P. Flannery, 1992. Numerical recipes in C: The Art of Scientific Computing, Cambridge Univ. Press.
- [28] Rao, A. R., 1990 *A Taxonomy for Texture Description and Identification*, Springer.
- [29] Scharr, H., S. Körkel, and B. Jähne, 1997. Numerische Isotropieoptimierung von FIR-Filtern mittels Querglättung, Proc. *Mustererkennung 1997*, Braunschweig, 15-17. September 1997, F. Wahl und E. Paulus (eds.), Informatik Aktuell, Springer, Berlin, in press.
- [30] Schultz, M., 1997. *Geometrische Kalibration von CCD-Kameras*, Diploma thesis, Univ. Heidelberg.
- [31] Sedig, U., 1977 *Radiometrische und spektroradiometrische Kalibrierung von CCD Kameras*. Diploma thesis, Univ. Heidelberg, in preparation.

- [32] Simoncelli, E. (1994). Design of multidimensional derivative kernels, *First IEEE Int. Conf. on Image Processing (ICIP'94)*, Austin, Texas.
- [33] Singh, A, 1991. *Optic flow computation: a unified perspective*, IEEE Computer Society Press, Los Alamitos, CA.
- [34] Spies, H., 1998. Diploma thesis, Univ. Heidelberg, in preparation.
- [35] Zhang, X. and C. S. Cox, 1994. *Exp. Fluids*, 17, 225.

B Wind Waves, Turbulence, and Exchange Processes at the Ocean Surface

1 Introduction and Summary

Despite intensive research in recent years, knowledge about small-scale air-sea interaction processes such as the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer and the dynamics of short wind waves and their influence on the exchange processes is still poor and many basic questions are open [*Liss and Duce, 1997, Jähne and Haußecker, 1998*].

The mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer are still not known. Thus no physically based modeling of the transfer rate is available. The state of the art is an empirical relation between the wind speed and the transfer rate although it is known that the gas transfer rate significantly depends on a number of other parameters such as the wave field — especially all forms of wave breaking —, the viscoelastic properties of surface films, and the buoyancy of the air and water flow close to the interface. Likewise not much is known about the dynamics of short wind waves that forms the small-scale shape of the ocean surface.

On the one hand, the poor knowledge can be attributed to the complex turbulent processes at a free surface undulated by waves that are also influenced by the physicochemical properties of the surface layer. On the other hand, inadequate experimental techniques are a major obstacle for further progress. Conventional techniques proved to be inadequate and it is only for the advent of sophisticated imaging techniques that gradually an experimental insight into these processes is gained, which will certainly also spur further theoretical progress. This is why small-scale interaction processes have become one of the subjects in this research unit.

Phase I of this research unit saw two significant highlights. First direct field measurements of the gas exchange rate (sections 3.1–3.3) and short wind waves (section 2.1) became finally possible with imaging techniques. Secondly, laser-induced fluorescence techniques were used to measure concentration fields in the aqueous viscous boundary layer and to study the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer (section 4).

Using the first field data a detailed comparative study of wave number spectra taken in different laboratory facilities and the field was performed [*Jähne and Klinke, 1997a, 1997b*]. We also performed a first analysis of the modulation of short wind waves by long waves [*Weiss, 1997*] using image sequence processing techniques developed in the central project (A) of the research unit. Input from the central project with shape from shading techniques from computer vision made it also possible to improve the wave slope imaging techniques significantly.

The work in air-sea gas transfer concentrated on two subjects: field measurements of the gas transfer rate (section 3) and laser-induced fluorescence techniques (LIF) to study the mechanisms of air-sea gas transfer in the laboratory (section 4). Field measurements of air-sea gas transfer rates were performed using active and passive thermography. Measuring the spatiotemporal temperature distribution on top of the aqueous mass boundary layer, heat patterns could be observed that directly revealed the horizontal structure of surface-near turbulence. Together with a physical modeling of the underlying transfer processes this passive technique allowed to compute transfer rates directly from the surface temperature distribution. It could be demonstrated that the independent active heat spot-tracking and the passive statistical method deliver consistent results [*Haußecker, 1996; Haußecker and Jähne, 1997*]. The data acquired during the 1995 MBL/CoOP Pacific cruise show a clear wind speed dependence that is consistent with previous field and laboratory measurements.

Two techniques for concentration profile measurements were developed and successfully used in the annular Heidelberg facility and — in cooperation with Dr. Hanratty and Dr. Duke — in a linear air/water flume at the University of Illinois, Urbana/Champaign (UIUC). It was not possible to use the oxygen quenching [*Duke and Hanratty, 1995*] and the fluorescent indicator technique [*Münsterer and Jähne, 1997*] simultaneously since the latter influenced the quenching technique. The concentration profiles show enormous fluctuations and reveal — in agreement with the thermographic techniques —

Figure B.1: Left: The wave imaging buoy on the stern of the R/V New Horizon, ready for deployment. Right: buoy in operation

that surface renewal seems to be the dominant process for air-water gas transfer. With regard to the influence of waves it could clearly be verified that the stress-modulation theory of *Back and McCready* [1988] is not correct.

2 Short Wind Waves

The measurements of short wind waves in the field are performed in close cooperation with the research group of the PI at Scripps Institution of Oceanography (Dr. Klinke). The partition of the work was as follows. All sea-going operations (instrument design, construction, and measurements) were performed at the Scripps Institution of Oceanography and have been funded by the US Office of Naval Research (ONR) as part of the Marine Boundary Layer Accelerated Research Initiative (MBL-ARI). The work performed in the research unit focuses on the development of new image sequence processing algorithms and the development of new wave imaging techniques.

We describe the fieldwork here in section 2.1 followed by a survey of the image sequence algorithms that are required and will be used in the second phase of the research unit to analyze the dynamics of short wind waves (section 2.2). A novel multi-illumination wave imaging technique developed within the first phase of the research unit is described in project A section 3.

2.1 Analysis of Recent Results on Wave Number Spectra

During the MBL/CoOP (Marine Boundary Layer/Coastal Ocean Processes) West Coast experiment in April/May 1995 off the Coast of California, a free-drifting wave imaging buoy (figure B.1) was successfully deployed. For the first time ever, image sequences of two wave slope components were taken in the field. Previously only measurements with scanning laser slope gauges were available [*Hara et al.*, 1994, *Hwang et al.*, 1996]. With this technique it is also possible to compute 2-D wave number spectra. But the resolution is much less and no direct image of the water surface slope is obtained. The images taken with our instrument covered a sector of about 15×19 cm with 30 frames/sec. About 20,000 images were collected during the MBL cruise. Unfortunately, the data that could be evaluated were restricted to a narrow wind speed range of 4-6 m/s.

Figure B.2 shows the overall similarity in the spectral shape of the lab and field data with regard to the wave number dependence. There is one noticeable difference. The angular dispersion of the field

Figure B.2: Comparison of wave number saturation spectra $B(k)$ from the Delft wind/wave facility at 100 m fetch and wave number spectra obtained from the New Horizon: **a** 2-D wave number spectra (field data averaged over 12 runs of 5 s long image sequences with 150 images each) at about 5 m/s wind speed. **b** Omnidirectional spectra (lab data with wind speeds of 4, 5, and 6 m/s; field data 12 runs of 5 s averages with 150 images each at a wind speed of about 5 m/s).

data is much wider and not symmetric with regard to the wind direction. This asymmetry, however, may have been caused by a swell system propagating obliquely to the main wind direction.

In previous field investigations, *Hara et al.* [1994] and *Hwang et al.* [1996] found significantly higher spectral densities at low wind speeds ($u_* = 0.03 - 0.21$ m/s) than observed in the laboratory. As one possible explanation *Hwang et al.* [1996] offered the fluctuating component of the wind field, which is high in the field but low in the laboratory. This comparison was, however, based only on the early set of laboratory measurements from *Jähne and Riemer* [1990] taken in the larger wind/wave flume of Delft Hydraulics at 100 m fetch.

Meanwhile more laboratory wave number spectra are available [*Jähne and Klinke*, 1997a]. The data collection in figure B.3 shows that the 100 m Delft data have the lowest spectral densities. Especially the spectral densities in the Heidelberg facility with unlimited fetch are a factor of 2–4 higher at low wind speeds and thus are much closer to the field data. This suggests another explanation for the higher spectral densities of short waves at low wind speed under oceanic conditions. Since the pioneering experiments of *Cox* [1958] it is known that steep short gravity waves generate parasitic capillary waves without applying wind. Under oceanic conditions there are other sources for short gravity waves than the wind at low wind speed, it is natural that parasitic capillary waves should be produced more frequently. This explanation is also supported by laboratory data. When irregular gravity waves with a JONSWAP-type of spectrum were superimposed to wind waves, the spectral densities at low wind

Figure B.3: Comparison of field with laboratory data: shown is the dependence of the spectral density at selected wave numbers with the friction velocities for the conditions as indicated in the legend.

speeds are also higher in the laboratory than with pure wind waves (figure B.3). At wind speeds higher than 5–8 m/s ($u_* > 0.2 - 0.3$ m/s), the influence of background waves seems no longer to be significant. There are, however, no field data yet available to support this conclusion.

The u_* -dependence of the spectral densities strongly varies with wave number. The exponent of the friction velocity dependence of the spectral densities at intermediate friction velocities increases from approximately 2 for the 3 cm waves to almost 3 for $\lambda = 8$ mm. At higher friction velocities and $\lambda = 8$ mm the increase in spectral density saturates and varies almost linearly with u_* . From figure B.3 we extracted a mean friction velocity exponent by fitting the data for $u_* > 0.2$ m/s. The values for the wavelengths $\lambda = 12.5$ cm and $\lambda = 6.3$ cm were obtained from figure 10 of *Jähne and Riemer* [1990]. Figure B.4 shows a comparison of these data with results from radar measurements as listed in table 4 of *Masuko et al.* [1986]. In order to allow a comparison, the radar wavelengths for 50° and 60° incidence angles were converted to the surface Bragg wave number k_b . Although the scatter of the radar data is quite significant at larger Bragg wave numbers, they follow the trend of a steeper increase towards higher wave numbers. Two reasons for the scatter at higher wave numbers may be the increased influence of surfactants and the fact that a single wind speed exponent does not exist. Rather, the wave spectra measurements indicate that the increase in spectral density slows down at higher wind speeds, resulting in a wind speed exponent that is different for different wind speed ranges.

2.2 Required Image Sequence Algorithms

So far it is the state of the art to use only standard Fourier transform techniques to determine wave number spectra from image sequences. This approach shows, however, two significant disadvantages.

- The wave number resolution is limited, especially for large wavelength. For an image sector of $15 \text{ cm} \times 19 \text{ cm}$ that has been used in the field the maximum wavelength that can be analyzed with sufficient resolution is about 5 cm. Thus the range of wave numbers that can be determined in this way is restricted to a wavelength range between 2 mm and 5 cm. An adequate analysis of the dynamics of the short waves needs to cover the whole range of short gravity waves up to at least one meter wavelength down to the shortest capillary waves with a wavelength of only a

Figure B.4: Wind speed exponent as function of Bragg wave number. Data with error bars are from our optical wave measurements, symbols represent radar backscatter measurements from the literature. From Jähne and Klinka [1997a].

few millimeters. This is also the range of wavelength that is of interest for radar remote sensing. In the 1 m wavelength range a single optical observation with stereo photography is available [Banner *et al.*, 1989]. Technically it will be not feasible to extend the image sizes of the wave slope imaging instruments in the field. Therefore it is required to develop new image sequence processing algorithms that overcome the limitations of the classical uncertainty relation.

- In the power spectrum all phase information is lost. The phase information is of importance for any study of the modulation of short wind waves by long wind waves. Such measurements have not been feasible (except indirectly with radar instruments), because no wave image sequences were available. In a preliminary study, we performed a first analysis of the modulation of short wind waves by long waves [Weiss, 1997]. The results from measurements taken in the large Delft wind/wave flume show a maximum modulation at intermediate wind speeds, an increase of the modulation depth towards shorter wavelengths, and a clear deviation from a sinusoidal modulation with the phase of the long wave. As an example of the preliminary results, the modulation of short wind waves at 5 m/s by the dominant gravity wave is shown in figure B.5. The spectral densities are maximal shortly after the crest of the long wave. There also the highest wave numbers occur.

The research plan for phase II of the research unit in projects A and B outlines how we intend to overcome the limits of the classical Fourier analysis. Here we only list the required algorithms in order to point out the relation of this project to the other projects.

Scale Space Analysis. This will be the central tool to separate image sequences into different scales. For wave images this means that we can separate the different interacting wave numbers.

Determination of local wave number, frequency and phase. Then it is possible to measure the local wave number and the local amplitude of a single wave using Hilbert filters [Jähne, 1997].

Determination of the local phase speed. The extension of these analysis techniques to image sequences will provide a way to overcome the limited wave number resolution of Fourier transform based techniques. The key point is the determination of the velocity of the individual wave components by the structure tensor based motion analysis techniques developed in phase I in the core project A. For waves with wavelengths comparable with or larger than the image sector, it will no longer be possible to determine a local wave number. If however sufficiently long image sequences are taken, the local frequency can be measured. From the local frequency, ω , and the amount and direction of the phase speed, c , obtained by the image sequence analysis the local wave number, k , of the wave is simply given by $k = c(\omega/|c|^2)$.

Figure B.5: Modulation of short wind waves at 5 m/s and 100 m fetch in the large wind/wave flume of Delft Hydraulics by the dominant gravity wave. The upper graph shows the spectral densities of various wave number ranges (int1: 0.94-1.57 cm, int2: 0.57-0.94 cm, int3: 0.35-0.57 cm) as a function of the phase of the long wave (the crest of the wave is at a phase of $\pi/2$). The lower graph shows a contour plot of the along-wind spectral density as a function of the wave number and the phase of the long wave. From Weiss [1997].

3 Field Measurements of Air-Water Gas Transfer

3.1 The Controlled Flux Technique: Active and Passive Thermography

In order to reliably measure air-sea gas transfer velocities in the field with a high spatial and temporal resolution a new technique has been developed called the *controlled flux technique*, CFT [Libner, 1987; Jähne et al., 1989; Haußecker et al., 1995; Haußecker, 1996]. The basic idea of this technique is to apply a known and controllable flux density, j , of a tracer across the interface forcing a concentration difference between water surface and bulk, ΔC , to establish according to

$$k = \frac{j}{\Delta C} \quad (\text{B.1})$$

with the *transfer velocity* k . This takes place within a time span given by the time constant t_* for the transport across the boundary layer which is in the order of seconds:

$$t_* = \frac{D}{k^2}. \quad (\text{B.2})$$

D denotes the diffusion constant of the tracer in water. The local transfer velocity can be determined by simply measuring the concentration difference ΔC across the aqueous viscous boundary layer.

Using *heat* as a proxy tracer for gases (B.1) has to be replaced by

$$k_h = \frac{j_h}{\rho c_p \Delta T} \quad (\text{B.3})$$

with the heat flux density j_h , the density of water ρ , the specific heat c_p and the temperature difference ΔT between water surface and bulk.

Heat proves to be an ideal tracer for several reasons. First the temperature at the water surface can be measured instantaneously and remotely using an infrared detector. Secondly, heat allows to apply a known and controllable flux density by using infrared radiation. Infrared radiation penetrates the air-sided boundary layer without significant attenuation shorting the high air-sided resistance for heat transfer. The heat is absorbed in the first few ten μm at the water surface. Thus infrared radiation provides a heat source right at the top of the water-sided viscous boundary layer. Therefore the CFT directly measures the water-sided heat transfer velocity.

A disadvantage of the CFT is that the transfer velocity of gases, k_g , must be extrapolated from the transfer velocity for heat, k_h , according to [Jähne, 1980]

$$k_g = \left(\frac{Sc_h}{Sc_g} \right)^n k_h \quad (\text{B.4})$$

with the *Schmidt number* $Sc = \nu/D$ relating the kinematic viscosity, ν , to the diffusion constant, D , of the tracer. The large difference in the Schmidt number (7 for heat, 600 for CO_2) casts some doubts whether the extrapolation to so much higher Schmidt numbers is valid. Laboratory experiments in wind/wave flumes showed, however, that the extrapolation is correct within about 10% provided the uncertainty in the diffusion coefficient of the gas is less than 5% and the Schmidt number exponent n is known with an error less than ± 0.02 [Jähne et al., 1989].

Experimental problems arise from the fact that only the surface temperature T_s is directly accessible and not the temperature difference ΔT across the viscous boundary layer. Practical implementations use different active and passive methods to estimate either the temperature difference ΔT or the time constant t_* of the heat transfer.

In a first realization [Libner, 1987; Jähne et al., 1989] used an extended infrared radiator to heat up the water surface and a point-measuring IR-radiometer. Switching on and off the heat flux periodically they could infer the time constant t_* from the frequency response of the surface temperature T_s . This technique proved to work well in laboratory measurements. However, it could not be used in the field due to the tremendous amount of radiation needed to heat up a footprint of several square meters at the ocean surface.

A major improvement of the CFT technique could be achieved by replacing the radiometer by an imaging infrared camera with a temperature resolution of 0.025 K (AMBER Radiance 1). Then instead of an extended radiator an infrared laser could be used because the laser spot could be tracked within the image area [Haußecker et al., 1995]. Now local measurements within an area of a few centimeters in diameter were possible.

Figure B.6: Two examples of infrared images of the ocean surface showing **a** the active and **b** the passive controlled flux technique.

The work in air-sea gas transfer during phase I of the research unit concentrated on field measurements using active and passive thermography for in situ measurements of air-sea gas transfer rates and to simultaneously study the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer. Two independent techniques have been developed and successfully applied during field experiments. Both techniques use extended image sequences of the ocean surface temperature with and without artificial heating. The *active technique* estimates the time constant t_* of heat transfer from the temporal decay of a heated spot at the ocean surface (see figure B.6 a). Measuring the spatiotemporal temperature distribution on top of the aqueous mass boundary layer, heat patterns could be observed that directly revealed the horizontal structure of surface-near turbulence (see figure B.6 b). Together with a physical modeling of the underlying transfer processes the *passive technique* allowed to compute transfer rates directly from the surface temperature distribution without artificial heating. It could be demonstrated that the independent active heat spot-tracking and the passive statistical method deliver consistent results [Haußecker, 1996; Haußecker and Jähne, 1997]. In the following sections the two techniques will be introduced in more detail.

3.2 Active Thermography: Heat Spot Tracking

The basic idea of the active technique is to apply *linear system theory* to the aqueous heat boundary layer which is possible since the underlying transport equation is linear in the tracer concentration (temperature for heat transfer). After disturbing the stationary mean temperature difference across the interface by a short and local surface temperature increase the system's response in terms of the dynamics of the relaxation process of the surface temperature is investigated.

A CO₂ infrared laser is used to heat up a small patch at the ocean surface. Tracking the heated area yields an image sequence of a decaying spot of increased surface temperature. Figures B.7 and B.8 show a series of infrared images acquired during measurements in the Delft Hydraulics wind/wave flume and the tracked spots, respectively. The laser was fired alternating between two vertical positions (in cross wind direction). It can be observed in figure B.7 how the spots slowly decay while drifting away with the surface velocity. In order to track individual spots the *structure tensor* technique (see section 7) developed in the core project A of the research unit has successfully been applied. The displacement vector field of the water surface surrounding a heat spot was used to estimate to position of the spot in the consecutive frame. With this technique even heat spots on the very inhomogeneous ocean surface (see figure B.6 a) can be reliably tracked. Figure B.8 shows a sequence of a single spot and an averaged sequence. All individual sequences have been corrected for the center of the spot before averaging.

The heat transfer rates can be estimated from the *temporal decay* of the increased surface temperature T_s , which can be obtained by integrating the temperature over the area of the heat spots in the images (see figure B.9). Haußecker et al. [1995] showed that the decay curves can be predicted by a simple *surface renewal model*. Using the classical model of Higbie [1935], Danckwerts [1951] and Münnich and Flothmann [1975] the Reynolds equation for heat reads

$$\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial t} = D_h \frac{\partial^2 T_s}{\partial z^2} - \lambda(T_s - T_b), \quad (\text{B.5})$$

Figure B.7: Four consecutive images of a decaying laser spot (Delft Hydraulics wind/wave flume, The Netherlands). The wind is blowing from left to right.

Figure B.8: Sequence of individually tracked laser spots. Top row: single decaying laser spot. Bottom row: averaged sequence of 20 decaying laser spots.

with the diffusion constant for heat in water, D_h , the statistical renewal rate, $\lambda = t_*^{-1}$, and the bulk temperature, T_b . This equation is linear in T_s and has the analytical solution

$$T_s(t) = T_0 \frac{h}{\sqrt{h^2 + 4D_h t}} \exp[-\lambda t], \quad (\text{B.6})$$

where h and T_0 denote the penetration depth and the initially increased temperature, respectively. This corresponds to a diffusional square-root dependency enhanced by an exponential decay due to the statistical renewal. Fitting the decay curve (B.6) to the data yields the time constant t_* and the parameters T_0 and h .

This technique proved to work well in a variety of laboratory measurements including the large Delft Hydraulics wind/wave flume and the large annular Heidelberg flume [Reinelt, 1994; Haußecker et al., 1995]. For field data, however, the decay curves could not be fitted with the anticipated analytical relationship under some conditions. In order to understand the difference in the behavior of the decay curves in the lab and in the field extensive numerical simulations of the transfer processes in the aqueous heat boundary layer have been carried out [Haußecker, 1996]. The simulation combined a local, depth-dependent laser heating, fluxes of latent, sensible and radiative heat transfer, a velocity gradient in the boundary layer and a surface renewal model for heat transfer. In cooperation with the core project A of the research unit the simulation was implemented in the image processing software *heurisko*. This rather unusual technique was possible because the underlying differential equation could be transformed into basic image processing operators. In this way the capability of *heurisko* handling huge spatiotemporal data sets could be exploited demonstrating the versatility of the image processing software.

From the result of the numerical simulation theoretical decay curves have been computed incorporating the radiometrical properties of the AMBER Radiance 1 infrared camera (see figure B.9). It showed that the decay curves could be perfectly fitted with the analytical relation (B.6) for conditions of short time constants t_* and correspondingly fast decay. For long time constants and high values of heat

Figure B.9: Theoretical (simulation) and measured (ocean, R/V New Horizon and lab, Delft Hydraulics) decay curves.

flux across the surface the fit did not converge. The same was true for the field data. This proved that the heat spots have to be tracked until they are totally decayed — which is not possible if they drift out of the image before being decayed — in order to extract the time constant t_* reliably. This was an important result during phase I, because it demonstrated that the instrumental setup has to be modified in order to follow the heated spots over a longer period.

As another result of this technique active thermography was also applied in subproject D in order to determine the spatially resolved heat capacity (water content) and transpiration rate of leaves. The physical background and technical expertise of subproject B has been successfully transferred to subproject D in order to get a whole new kind of insight into the spatial distribution of these physiologically relevant parameters (see section 5 in project D).

3.3 Passive Thermography: Statistics of the Sea Surface Temperature Distribution

At the ocean surface natural heat fluxes such as latent heat transfer j_l , sensible heat transfer j_s and longwave emission of radiation j_r cause the surface temperature to decrease or increase depending on the meteorological conditions. The net heat flux $j_n = j_l + j_s + j_r$ results in a temperature difference across the interface of $\Delta T = j_n / (\rho c_p k_h)$ according to (B.3). The average temperature drop at the surface is known as the *cool skin* of the ocean [Saunders, 1967]. The high temperature resolution of modern infrared cameras allows to resolve the temperature fluctuations at the ocean surface under natural flux conditions (figure B.10).

Haußecker [1996] developed a method to estimate the heat transfer velocity k_h from the temperature distribution within these images provided a known flux density j_n . The spatial distribution of the sea surface temperature directly reveals the structure of surface turbulence. Again the classical surface renewal model proved to perfectly fit the measured surface temperature distribution. Between two consecutive renewal events a temperature difference establishes according to [Soloviev and Schlüssel,

Figure B.10: Infrared images of the ocean surface acquired during the MBL/CoOP West Coast experiment in April/May 1995. The images are temperature calibrated and clearly show a decreasing temperature contrast with increasing wind speed (note the different temperature scales). During this run the wind changed within a time span of 90 minutes while the net heat flux stayed constant.

Figure B.11: **a** Schematic course of the sea surface temperature for both a purely periodical and a statistical surface renewal. **b** Comparison of three different renewal statistics given the same mean live span t_* of a surface element.

Figure B.12: Comparison of three different theoretical temperature distributions with a measured histogram of the ocean surface temperature averaged over 4 minutes. The three theoretical distributions are results of a simple surface renewal model given different renewal statistics with the same time constant t_* (mean life span of a surface water element). The statistics are 1: exponential distribution, 2: log-normal distribution and 3: periodical renewal. The measured distribution falls close to the theoretical histogram given a log-normal renewal statistic [Haußecker, 1996].

1994]

$$\Delta T(t) = \alpha j_n \sqrt{t}, \quad \text{with} \quad \alpha = 2(\rho c_p \sqrt{\pi D_h})^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.7})$$

The surface temperature T_s is statistically reset to the bulk temperature T_b by large eddies sweeping down the surface water and replacing it by bulk water. Depending on the statistical nature of the renewal the temporal course of the temperature of a certain water surface element can be illustrated as shown in figure B.11 a . Given the temporal temperature change (B.7) Haußecker [1996] computed the theoretical, statistically averaged surface temperature distribution $h(T_s)$ at the ocean surface as

$$h(T_s) = \frac{2}{(\alpha j_n)^2} (T_s - T_b) \int_{t(T)}^{\infty} \frac{p(\tau)}{\tau} d\tau, \quad t(T) = \left(\frac{T_s - T_b}{\alpha j_n} \right)^2, \quad (\text{B.8})$$

with the probability distribution $p(\tau)$ for the time in between two consecutive surface renewal events. For a log-normal distribution

$$p(\tau) = \pi^{-0.5} (s\tau)^{-1} \exp\left(-\frac{(\ln \tau - m)^2}{s^2}\right) \quad (\text{B.9})$$

with $s = 0.9$, the theoretical distribution $h(T_s)$ perfectly fits to the measured data (figure B.12). Probability distributions suggested by other authors, such as periodical renewal and exponential probability do not allow to fit the data. A comparison of the different probability distributions is shown in figure B.11b. Although all three distributions correspond to the same mean life span t_* of a surface element they show different distributions around t_* . The log-normal distribution was first proposed by Rao *et al.* [1971] for statistical fluctuations in a turbulent air-flow. It was chosen by Haußecker [1996] because it seemed to reflect what can be observed in real image sequences. Surface renewal events obviously happen. They appear as randomly distributed sudden temperature increases at different sizes ranging from small, almost circular patterns up to the entire image area being washed away. The time in between two surface renewals does not seem to be periodical. The exponential distribution also does not seem to be appropriate since it predicts a maximum for instantaneous renewals which means that the water surface should be continuously renewed with only a few longer periods that allow a cool skin to establish.

Fitting the numerically evaluated theoretical distributions $h(T_s)$ with the function

$$h(T, \sigma) = a \sqrt{T - T_1} \exp\left(-\frac{(T - T_2)^2}{2\sigma^2}\right), \quad T_2 > T_1, \quad (\text{B.10})$$

Haußecker [1996] found a quantitative relationship between the width σ of the temperature distribution $h(T_s)$ and the time constant t_* :

$$t_* = 1.643 \cdot 10^7 j^{-2} \sigma^2. \quad (\text{B.11})$$

Figure B.13: *a* Photograph of the CFT ocean-instrument (splash proof cover removed). *b* Research vessel R/V Oceanus, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, used during the recent 1997 CoOP cruise.

Figure B.14: Photographs of the CFT instrument mounted on the bows of two different research vessels. *a* R/V New Horizon, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, during the 1995 MBL/CoOP cruise. *b* R/V Oceanus, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution, during the recent 1997 CoOP cruise.

Using (B.2) the heat transfer rate can be estimated as

$$k_h = 2.467 \cdot 10^{-4} j \sigma^{-1}. \quad (\text{B.12})$$

As far as transfer mechanisms are concerned, all CFT measurements clearly support the surface renewal model. The data fit to theoretical dependencies such as decay curves and temperature distributions predicted by the surface renewal model. Surface renewal is also directly observable in the infrared images showing surface patches being washed away statistically even under low wind speed conditions. Furthermore the surface velocity field derived from infrared images (using the *structure tensor technique*, core project A) clearly shows convergence and divergence zones which violates the two-dimensional continuity equation right at the water surface. This corresponds to the fact that convective vertical mixing across the aqueous mass boundary layer takes place.

3.4 Results

The CFT field instrument (figure B.13) has been used on two research cruises so far. During the MBL/CoOP West Coast experiment in April/May 1995 aboard the R/V New Horizon it was used for the first time. The cruise took place along the California coast up to Monterey bay focusing on the variability of surface conditions around the channel islands. Figure B.14 a shows a photograph of the instrument mounted at the tip of a massive 20 feet long boom on the bow of the R/V New Horizon. With the ship steaming slowly into the wind at a speed of approximately 1 knot (0.5 m/s) disturbances from the ship could be minimized. Figure B.15 shows the temporal course of wind speeds during one run and the corresponding CFT transfer velocities (computed from the passive statistical technique) normalized to a Schmidt number of 600. This run shows an extraordinary meteorological condition. Within a period of only 1.5 hours the wind dropped from initially 10 m/s to almost zero before picking

Figure B.15: Wind speeds and gas transfer velocities computed with the Controlled Flux Technique (CFT) during the 1995 MBL/CoOP West Coast experiment (yearday 133) within a time span of 90 minutes. The transfer velocities are normalized to Schmidt number 600 and averaged over 4 minutes each. It clearly shows that the CFT transfer velocities are correlated with the intermittent wind speed demonstrating the capability of this technique to instantaneous measurements.

Table B.1: Measurement conditions during the recent 1997 CoOP North Atlantic cruise (Gulf stream transections between Cape Cod and the Bermuda islands).

yearday	position	wind [m/s]	SST [°C]	condition
188	39° 12.12,N 069° 22.76,W	0.0 – 0.9	23.2	smooth sea, high humidity
188	39° 12.86,N 069° 27.12,W	0.7 – 1.9	22.3	smooth sea, high humidity
189	41° 10.83,N 068° 04.20,W	4.0 – 4.3	23.5	foggy, low contrast
190	37° 06.27,N 068° 00.58,W	1.0 – 3.1	27.7	clear sky, high contrast
191	37° 08.18,N 068° 02.50,W	6.3 – 8.3	28.0	scattered clouds, high contrast
192	36° 59.53,N 068° 36.27,W	1.5 – 2.7	25.5	heavy rain
193	37° 59.04,N 071° 01.73,W	2.0 – 4.7	24.2	clear sky, high contrast
194	39° 29.78,N 071° 48.55,W	4.7 – 4.9	23.7	clear sky, high contrast
194	39° 58.54,N 072° 00.06,W	2.5 – 4.1	21.9	clear sky, medium contrast
194	39° 54.83,N 071° 48.30,W	4.5 – 5.3	24.4	clear sky, sunshine
195	40° 59.75,N 071° 00.77,W	4.9 – 5.8	20.2	foggy, low contrast
196	40° 15.18,N 070° 09.58,W	4.9 – 6.3	21.6	clear sky, low contrast
197	39° 48.38,N 070° 01.58,W	4.7 – 5.8	24.2	clear sky, medium contrast
198	39° 11.64,N 069° 24.75,W	6.7 – 8.4	25.3	clear sky, medium contrast

up again and climbing up to 12 m/s. The strong correlation between wind speed and transfer velocity clearly demonstrates the capability of the CFT technique to fast measurements even under intermittent meteorological conditions.

Figure B.16 shows a collection of field data of transfer rates measured by a variety of investigators during the last 20 years together with CFT data from the special run on yearday 133 during the 1995 MBL/CoOP Pacific cruise. Although the data cannot directly be compared the CFT data show a clear wind speed dependence that is consistent with previous field and laboratory measurements. Please note that all CFT transfer rates are acquired within 1.5 hours. All other data are measured from mass balance techniques and therefore average over several days in order to get one single transfer rate. At very low wind speeds (below 3 m/s), where almost no field data were available before, the CFT transfer rates are significantly higher than the laboratory data. This indicates that the residual turbulence by background waves and turbulence — which is not present in laboratory facilities — has some influence on gas transfer in the field.

Figure B.16: Summary of gas exchange field data normalized to a Schmidt number of 600 and plotted vs. wind speed. Sources of data: ^{14}C : [Broecker et al., 1985, 1986; Cember, 1989], $\text{SF}_6/{}^3\text{He}$: [Watson et al., 1991; Wanninkhof et al., 1993], ^{222}Rn : [Emerson et al., 1991; Glover and Reeburgh, 1987; Kromer and Roether, 1983; Peng et al., 1974, 1979; Smethie et al., 1985], heat: [Haußecker, 1996], empirical relationships: [Liss and Merlivat, 1986; Wanninkhof, 1992].

During the recent CoOP East Coast experiment from July 1 to July 18, 1997, the CFT instrument was used for the second time in the field. Figure B.13b and Figure B.14b show the research vessel R/V Oceanus at sea and the instrument mounted on a boom at the bow of the ship, respectively. The cruise started from coastal waters at Martha's Vineyard sound south of Cape Cod, MA, leading to several Gulf stream transections halfway to the Bermuda islands. Since the end of the cruise no data has been evaluated so far, but the conditions encountered look very promising (see table B.1).

Although no measurements at very high wind speeds could be performed there is a large variability in physicochemical surface conditions ranging from coastal waters with high surfactant concentrations up to very clean, deep blue waters close to the Bermudas. Crossing the Gulf Stream the sea surface temperature climbed from 20°C up to 28°C . This should give an interesting insight into the variability of the air-water gas transfer rate with these parameters that have been simultaneously measured during the cruise by the research groups of Dr. Erik Bock and Dr. Nelson Frew, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution.

4 Studies of Air-Water Gas Transfer using Laser-Induced Fluorescence Techniques

Two techniques for concentration field measurements within the aqueous viscous boundary layer were developed and successfully used in the annular Heidelberg facility and — in cooperation with Dr. Hanratty and Dr. Duke — in a linear air/water flume at the University of Illinois, Urbana/Champaign (UIUC). [Wolff et al, 1991] and [Jähne, 1991] introduced two different approaches. Wolff et al., [1991] developed a technique utilizing the quenching of the fluorescence of a dye by oxygen. Jähne, [1991b] introduced a technique using the chemical reaction of an acid or alkaline gas at the water surface with a fluorescent indicator. Both techniques were used in this project.

Figure B.17: Schematic representation of the vertical concentration profiles at the air-water interface, when HCl is absorbed by a buffer solution.

4.1 Fluorescence Indicator Technique

This method uses a fluorescent pH indicator that is set to its buffer point. That means that equal concentrations of both ionic forms of a molecule, here denoted with HR and R⁻ are present. The transfer is initiated by injecting traces of alkaline or acid gases into the air space of a gas-tight wind-wave facility. The measuring principle is explained by using HCl (figure B.17). HCl is transported to the interface where it instantaneously dissociates into H₃O⁺ and Cl⁻ ions. Therefore, the HCl concentration at the water surface is zero and the flux density of HCl into the water is given by

$$j_a = k_a [\text{HCl}], \quad (\text{B.13})$$

where k_a is the air-sided transfer velocity and [HCl] the HCl concentration in the air space. Reproduced Cl⁻ ions are transferred via diffusion and convective mixing into the bulk of the water whereas the H₃O⁺ ions instantaneously react with the fluorescent indicator generating RH from R⁻. The reaction is a sink for R⁻ and a source for HR right at the water surface. For the transport further down in the bulk of the water, both HR and R⁻ behave as inert tracers and the flux density of the two species is given by

$$j_w = k_w \Delta[\text{HR}] = -k_w \Delta[\text{R}^-], \quad (\text{B.14})$$

where k_w is the transfer velocity in the water. Since the flux density in the air space and the water space must be equal, we can estimate the HCl concentrations necessary to produce a significant concentration change for the fluorescent molecules. From (B.13) we get

$$[\text{HCl}] = \frac{k_w}{k_a} \Delta[\text{R}^-]. \quad (\text{B.15})$$

According to Jähne and Haußecker [1998], k_a is about 500 times larger than k_w . In our experiments typically a fluorescent dye concentration of 10⁻⁵ M is used. Therefore the maximum possible concentration change of the R⁻ ions is 5 × 10⁻⁶ mol/l. This concentration change is already caused by 10⁻⁸ mol/l HCl gas concentration in the air space. This corresponds to a concentration of 0.2 ppm. Thus, low concentrations can be handled even in our large gas-tight circular wind-wave facility.

The concentration changes in R⁻ and HR can be measured when one of the components is much more fluorescent than the other one. We have directly measured the relation between the fluorescence intensity and the concentration of the fluorescein doubly charged anion and found that over a wide range the fluorescence intensity is linear with the concentration of the fluorescein doubly charged anion [Münsterer and Jähne, 1997].

4.2 Fluorescence Quenching Technique

This technique uses a fluorescent dye with a relatively long lifetime to be sensitive to quenching by oxygen. The fluorescence intensity is described by the Stern-Volmer equation and is inversely proportional to the concentration of dissolved oxygen:

$$\frac{I_0}{I} = \frac{\tau_0}{\tau} = 1 + K c \quad , \quad (\text{B.16})$$

Figure B.18: Experimental setup at the circular wind/wave facility at the University of Heidelberg for LIF measurements in the boundary layer. **a** For combined oxygen quenching/fluorescein experiments with imaging CCD-cameras and laser optics at a flat water surface. The complete optical setup is tilted approximately 6° to the horizontal to minimize shading of the measuring section by deeper wave troughs in the foreground. **b** With a wave following device for measurements at a wavy water surface. A line array camera is mounted on the other side of the flume picturing the point where the laser beam hits the water surface. This line array camera drives a scanning mirror in the optical path of the imaging CCD camera, which includes a *f*-theta lens.

where I is the fluorescence intensity, I_0 the fluorescence intensity at concentration 0, τ the fluorescence life time, K the quenching rate, and c the concentration of dissolved oxygen in water. A suitable fluorescent dye is pyrene butyric acid (PBA).

4.3 Experimental Setup

4.3.1 Experimental Setup at the Circular Heidelberg Facility

The circular wind/wave facility at the Institute for Environmental Physics at the University of Heidelberg consists of a 30 cm wide and 70 cm high gas-tight annular channel with an outer diameter of 4 m. A rotating paddle ring driven by 24 small DC motors generates the wind. The channel is filled up to a height of 25 cm. In addition, the facility is equipped with a moving transparent bed in order to adjust the bulk velocity of the water body independently of the wind speed.

Measurements at a wavy interface in the Heidelberg flume are complicated since the waves can reach peak-to-peak heights of 10 cm even for moderate wind speeds. To keep the water surface, i. e., the measuring section, in the imaging range of 4 by 4 mm an optical wave follower was designed with a scanning mirror in the optical path (figure B.18b).

To avoid optical distortions caused by the scanning mirror in the optical path of the imaging CCD a so called *f*-theta objective was used. With this lens and a number of other tricky construction details, the optical resolution of the whole optical system could be kept better than $25 \mu\text{m}$ for scanning heights of $\pm 50 \text{ mm}$. The optical wave follower generally worked well at low and medium wind speeds keeping the measuring section with about one millimeter at the water surface. It failed however at high wind speeds with steep and breaking waves.

For comparing the two laser-induced-fluorescence techniques, the oxygen quenching and the fluorescent indicator technique, a combined setup was built. The goal was to be able to visualize a two-dimensional concentration field with fluorescein and a one-dimensional oxygen concentration profile

at the same time at the same place. The combined laser and imaging optical arrangement was mounted on a single base plate. Figure B.18a shows the experimental setup. The PBA fluorescence was stimulated by a focused nitrogen laser beam at 337 nm wavelength with a spot diameter of 200 μm . The pulse rate of the laser was 15 Hz. By averaging over the width of the laser beam, each exposed field resulted in a one-dimensional profile. Horizontal averaging further reduced the noise level. Juxtaposed sequential profiles resulted in a space-time image. The optical resolution of the imaging system for the oxygen profiles was measured to be in the order of 24 μm in the vertical dimension.

The fluorescence spectra of fluorescein and PBA were separated using a dichroic mirror in the imaging optical path. To avoid distortions by the much brighter fluorescein fluorescence it was also necessary to block any remaining fluorescent light with two blue low-pass filters in front of the CCD camera.

Fluorescence for the fluorescein experiment was stimulated by the focused beam of an argon ion laser piercing the water surface perpendicularly from above. To investigate a two dimensional area the beam is scanned, resulting in a light sheet 6 mm wide and 60 μm deep. The spatial resolution of the optical system was measured to be approx. 16 μm .

For the experiments a stock solution of PBA and fluorescein in a NaOH solution was prepared. This stock solution was then diluted in the flume to give concentrations of 2×10^{-5} M for each of the dyes. In the flume HCl was added to titrate the solution to the fluorescein buffer point at pH 6.5 .

Although we could solve all optical problems for simultaneous measurements with both techniques, we finally had to use them one after the other since it turned out that the Cl^- ions generated by the absorption of the HCl gas used for the fluorescent indicator technique also quenched the PBA fluorescence. This chemical cross-talk between both techniques could unfortunately not be avoided.

4.3.2 Experimental Setup at the Facility of the University of Illinois

The channel at the Department of Chemical Engineering of the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign was built for studying mass transfer in two phase flows and flowing liquid films that are important in the field of chemical engineering. This channel has a length of 11 m and a cross section of 30.48 cm by 2.54 cm. The average water height is approximately 1 cm. These dimensions result in a fully developed wave field in the measuring section which is 4 m from the air inlet.

The experimental setup for LIF measurements in this facility is shown in figure B.19a. The fluorescence was excited with an 1.7 W Ar^+ ion laser at a wavelength of 488 nm. A laser light sheet was produced by a scanning mirror with a frequency of 100 Hz. The laser penetrated perpendicularly into the flume through a glass window at the bottom. The fluorescence was imaged through a window at the channel side with an optical system using two achromatic lenses. The complete optical setup was tilted 9° to the horizontal. This was necessary to minimize shading of the measuring section by deeper wave troughs in the foreground.

The channel at the University of Illinois offered the possibility of combining the *fluorescein* technique with a technique taking image sequences of the wave slope simultaneously. Here we used for the first time the color imaging slope gauge (CISG), a multi-illumination shape from refraction technique that has been developed in the core project A (see section 3). The CISG used here imaged a field of 25 \times 15 mm at a rate of 60 Hz. The laser beam penetrated the bottom of the flume at an angle of 34° against the vertical (figure B.19b). This was necessary to avoid shading of the imaging slope gauge setup.

4.4 Mean Concentration Profiles

Mean fluorescein and oxygen concentration profiles were measured at a flat surface-film covered surface in the Heidelberg facility. Three mean profiles obtained with this technique at a flat high shear interface are shown with normalized concentration values in figure B.20a. As expected the boundary layer thickness decreases with increasing friction velocity.

Figure B.21 also shows oxygen concentration profiles measured with oxygen micro-probes by *Chu and Jirka* [1992] and *Prinos et al.* [1995] and compares the profiles with theoretical curves from small eddy and surface renewal models. Although these authors also measured mean concentration profiles a comparison with the LIF results is difficult due to the different methods for creating turbulence. Both micro-probe experiments were carried out at a practically no-shear interface.

Nevertheless a simple comparison of the profile shapes shows the advantages of the non-intrusive fluorescence method. The spatial resolution is much higher and it is possible to measure instantaneous concentration fields. The oxygen micro-probes are restricted to point measurements which are later combined to a mean profile. The profiles measured with the indicator and oxygen quenching show a

Figure B.19: Experimental setup for the experiments at the wind/wave facility of the Department of Chemical Engineering at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign (UIUC). **a** For LIF measurements alone. The complete optical setup is tilted approximately 9° to the horizontal to minimize shading of the measuring section by deeper wave troughs in the foreground. **b** For combined wave slope/LIF imaging. In this setup the argon ion laser pierced the bottom window of the facility under an oblique angle to make room for the optical setup for wave slope imaging. From [Münsterer, 1996].

Figure B.20: Fluorescein concentration profiles measured at a smooth interface at the IUP for different wind speeds as indicated. **a** Normalized with respect to concentration. The plot shows the decrease of the boundary layer thickness with increasing friction velocity. The profiles were averaged over more than 410000 single profiles. **b** Same but normalized also with the boundary layer thickness and compared to the theoretical predictions of surface renewal and small eddy models. From [Münsterer, 1996].

Figure B.21: Oxygen concentration profiles measured at a smooth interface at the IUP for different friction velocities as indicated. Also shown are results of oxygen micro-probe measurements by Chu and Jirka [1992] and Prinos et al. [1995] (open symbols). The profiles are not fully comparable because Chu and Jirka measured theirs in a grid-stirred tank whereas Prinos measured theirs in a jet-agitated vessel. From [Münsterer, 1996].

Figure B.22: Fluorescein concentration profiles measured at a wavy interface at the facility at the University of Illinois. All profiles are normalized with concentration difference and boundary layer thickness. The profiles show a change in Schmidt number exponent for the wavy conditions. They seem to be much closer to the predictions of the surface renewal model. (SR: surface renewal model, K: small eddy model). From [Münsterer, 1996].

reasonable agreement with the model predictions for a Schmidt number exponent of $n = 2/3$ (figure B.20 and B.21). Because of the faster decay of the concentration at large dimensionless depths, the experimental data with both techniques are in favor of the surface renewal model.

Mean concentration profiles for wavy interfaces were computed from the measurements at the University of Illinois (UIUC) and the IUP. At the IUP a wave follower was used. The profiles measured at different conditions at the UIUC are shown in figure B.22. The profiles obtained at the higher friction velocities agree very well with the predictions of the surface renewal model for a Schmidt number exponent of $1/2$. This is consistent with the observation of a fully developed wave field with 3-dimensional waves. At the facility of the UIUC so called pebble waves develop at these wind speeds.

In conclusion the mean boundary layer profiles do not only agree with previous measurements of the Schmidt number exponent but they also allow for the first time distinguishing different models of the turbulence in the boundary layer. Both for smooth and wavy surfaces they are in favor for surface renewal models. This means that turbulent eddies significantly larger than the mass boundary layer are most significant for the mass transfer process.

Figure B.23: Comparison of rms concentration fluctuations at different distances from the water surface. The same arguments used for the mean profiles apply to the comparability of the concentration fluctuations measured by LIF with those measured with oxygen micro-probes. From [Münsterer, 1996].

Figure B.24: Sequence of images recorded at the wind/wave facility of the UIUC with the wind coming from the right. The images were taken 1/180s apart at a friction velocity of $u_{*w} = 1.5$ cm/s. The images are transferred into the frame of reference attached to the undulated water surface. The sequence shows a larger eddy sweeping through the boundary layer transporting high concentration fluid into the bulk. After the first eddy a second one can be seen. Both of these eddies reduce the boundary layer thickness down to almost nil indicating that surface renewal plays a significant process for air-water gas transfer at a wavy surface. From [Münsterer, 1996].

4.5 Mechanisms of the Transfer Process

The oxygen quenching technique offers the possibility of measuring root mean square (rms) fluctuations, c' , of the oxygen concentration in time. This is not possible with the fluorescein technique because the influence of air-side controlled HCl flux fluctuations is superimposed to the surface concentration changes. Directly measuring c' gives an additional possibility of testing mass transfer models. The small eddy model deliberately uses the assumption that the concentration fluctuations are null at the surface. No such assumption is made for the surface renewal model. Following the physical arguments of the surface renewal model a non-zero value of c' at the interface can be expected.

Measuring c' values with the oxygen quenching technique has some difficulties that mainly originate in the bad signal-to-noise ratio of the measured concentration profiles. With careful simulations, Münsterer [1996] could verify that no systematic errors were introduced by the high noise level.

Figure B.23 shows a comparison of the c' values calculated from the oxygen quenching results with those measured by Chu and Jirka [1992] and Prinos et al. [1995] using oxygen micro-probes. Two facts are of significance: First, the fluctuations are quite large in general. Secondly, the fluctuations

Figure B.25: Local boundary layer thickness plotted versus local wave slope. The measurements were performed at a friction velocity of $u_* = 1.41$ cm/s in the facility at the UIUC. The plot shows no correlation between the boundary layer thickness and the wave slope on a local level for the channel at the UIUC. The plot also shows the significant fluctuations of the local boundary layer thickness. The error bars denote the standard deviation from the mean value for a wave slope range of 0.04.

decrease significantly towards the interface. Both effects are consistent with the surface renewal theory. Figure B.24 indeed shows that surface renewal effects can be observed directly in the measured concentration profiles.

4.6 Correlation with Wave Slope

With regard to the influence of waves it could clearly be verified that the stress-modulation theory of *Back and McCready* [1988] is not correct. This theory postulated that the waves induce a stress modulation at the water surface, which in turn cause direct rolls directly correlated to the phase of the waves that enhance gas transfer. If this hypothesis is correct, there should be a direct correlation between the wave slope and the gas transfer rate or the mass boundary layer. Figure B.25 shows that this is not the case.

4.7 Conclusions

The results from the LIF studies reported here constitute a significant progress in the understanding of the mechanisms of the transfer across the free air-water interface. Nevertheless, this is certainly only the beginning of an exciting new way to study these processes, and we still have a long way to go. Although the techniques were very successful they require further improvements. It is especially important to extend them to measure not only vertical cross sections but also horizontal cross section through the boundary layer. The ultimate long-term goal is, of course, to take 3D image sequences of various physical and chemical parameters in the mass boundary layer. An important step in this direction are area- and depth-resolved measurements of the concentration fields. Some initial ideas in this direction are outlined in section 5.2.

Another important issue is to try to use less reactive gases than HCl and NH₃. One of the problems of these gases is that their transfer across the interface is controlled by the air-sided transfer processes. Preliminary studies to use CO₂ are very promising (see section 5.3). Thus it is obvious that the continuation of the LIF studies will be one central task in the second phase of the research unit (see renewal proposal).

Figure B.26: Simple experimental setup of an imaging IR prism spectrometer to test out the IR-DOAS technique to measure profiles of trace gas concentrations in the annular wind wave flume.

5 Development of New Measuring Technology

5.1 Gas Exchange Measurements by Imaging Differential Absorption IR Spectroscopy

The new techniques developed in phase I to study the mechanisms of air-water gas transfer (see sections 3.2 and 3.3) require only short measuring times of a few minutes. In order to set these studies in relation to mean fluxes and the Schmidt number dependence of the gas transfer rate still simultaneous measurements of the transfer velocities of several gases are required. The trouble is that conventional mass balance methods require too long measuring times, especially in the new planned facility with 1.2 m water depth.

Therefore we developed a new technique - and studied its feasibility - that measures the gas transfer rate of several gases and volatile species simultaneously with a temporal resolution of a few minutes only. Traditionally, the gas transfer rate is measured by loading the water with gases and by measuring the temporal changes of the concentrations of the gases dissolved in water. The changes in the air and water concentrations, c_a and c_w , are related by a system of two coupled first-order differential equations to the transfer velocity k of the gas across the air-water interface [Jähne, 1980]:

$$\begin{aligned} V_a \frac{\partial c_a}{\partial t} &= kA(c_w - \alpha c_a) - \mathcal{G}_a c_a \\ V_w \frac{\partial c_w}{\partial t} &= kA(\alpha c_a - c_w) \end{aligned} \quad (\text{B.17})$$

with

- V_a, V_w volume of the air and water space in the facility
- \mathcal{G}_a flush rate of the air space
- A area of the water surface
- α dimensionless (Ostwald's) solubility

When the air space is flushed with a large rate so that $\alpha c_a \ll c_w$, then the water concentration decays exponentially with a time constant $\tau_w = V_w/kA = h_w/k$, where h_w is the effective height of the water space in the facility. Since the transfer velocities are typically between 0.05 and 0.50 m/h, the time constant for the measurement is between 0.5 and 5 h in the current facility with a water depth of 0.25 m. In the new larger facility with 1.2 m water depth, the measurements become prohibitively slow with time constants between 2 and 20 hours.

However, if the gas concentration in the air space can be measured in situ, a much faster technique is possible. From (B.17), it can be derived that the time constant for the air concentration to come into equilibrium between the source by gas exchange across the water surface and the sink by flushing the air space is given by: $\tau_a = V_a/\mathcal{G}_a$. This time constant is in the order of minutes. The transfer velocity can be determined with this method by

$$k = \frac{c_a}{c_w} \frac{\mathcal{G}_a}{A} \quad \text{when} \quad \alpha c_a \ll c_w. \quad (\text{B.18})$$

Figure B.27: Low-resolution IR-spectra in the 3–5 μm range taken with a preliminary setup using the Radiance1 IR-camera and a CaF_2 prism as an imaging spectrometer (see figure B.26): **a** methane, **b** pentane, **c** CO_2 at different concentrations as indicated.

From the work in subproject C we learnt that differential absorption spectroscopy (DOAS) is a powerful technique to measure the concentration of several gases simultaneously. In order to check this technique, a simple imaging IR spectrometer was setup using the Radiance1 IR camera with a CaF_2 prism as a dispersive element (figure B.26). The camera observed a hot wire. The spectrum between 3–5 μm was spread in horizontal direction over 35 pixels, while in vertical direction the spatial resolution is still resolved so that profiles can be measured. The optical path for the absorption spectroscopy was 30 cm. Figure B.27 demonstrates that it is possible to measure carbon hydrate gas concentrations and CO_2 concentrations with this technique. These gases show strong absorption peaks in the 3–5 μm wavelength range.

Figure B.28 shows a test run to demonstrate the feasibility of the new technique for gas exchange measurements. Within a time period of two hours — less than the time constant for the decay of the gas concentration in water — six sequences of measurements with four wind speeds were performed, in total 24 measurements.

5.2 Area- and Depth-Resolved Mass Boundary Visualization by Fluorescence Spectroscopy

In phase I two laser-induced fluorescence techniques were developed and used to measure vertical concentration profiles in the aqueous mass boundary layer. In addition, we used passive thermography to study the horizontal structures of the heat boundary layer. In phase II we intend to use a spectroscopic measurement which enables us to perform both area- and depth-resolved measurements of the mass boundary layer. The new technique is again a spectroscopic technique. It is a blend of ideas originating from the differential absorption technique of subproject C and multi-labeling techniques, as they will be used in subproject E and F.

The idea is as follows. The fluorescence spectrum of fluorescein excited at 488 nm peaks at 510 nm and extends beyond 600 nm (figure B.29a). A second dye is used to attenuate light in this wavelength range. A possible candidate is bromophenol blue with a maximal absorption at 589 nm (figure B.29b).

Figure B.28: Demonstration of the DOAS technique to measure the air-water gas transfer rate with a time constant of less than a minute by measuring the CO_2 gas concentration using imaging IR-spectroscopy while the air-space in the wind/wave facility was flushed with a rate of about $1 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$ during a gas evasion experiment. The wind speed was varied periodically between 0, 2.3, 3.7 and 5.3 m/s. The slow decay of the envelope of the curves reflects the slow time constant of the loss of the gas concentration in the water body.

a

b

Figure B.29: **a** Absorption and emission spectrum (excited at 488 nm) of fluorescein ([Haugland, 1996]); **b** absorption spectra of the bromophenol blue sodium salt dissolved in water with an absorption maximum at 589 nm [Green, 1990]

With this double-dye technique, the shape of the observed fluorescence spectrum depends on the path length the light travels through the water before it is measured. If the fluorescence is excited from the air space, the path length directly corresponds to the distance from the water surface and the spectrum of the observed fluorescence is given by

$$I(z) = \exp(-\alpha(\lambda)z) c_f(z) f(\lambda), \quad (\text{B.19})$$

where $\alpha(\lambda)$ is the wavelength-dependent absorption coefficient of the absorbing dye solution, c_f the concentration of the fluorescent dye and $f(\lambda)$ its fluorescence spectrum. The totally observed fluorescent intensity is given by integration over the depth:

$$I(z) = \int_0^{z_{\max}} \exp(-\alpha(\lambda)z) c_f(z) f(\lambda) dz. \quad (\text{B.20})$$

If both $\alpha(\lambda)$ and $f(\lambda)$ are known, (B.20) constitutes a linear inverse problem to determine the depth-dependent concentration, $c_f(z)$, of the fluorescent dye. It is of the same nature as retrieving the ozone profile or the tropospheric ozone concentration from the GOME absorption spectra (see subproject C) and optimizing the labeling of chromosomes with multiple fluorescent dyes (subproject F). The number and the quality (resolution and noise level) of spectral sampling essentially determines the height resolution with which the vertical concentration profile can be retrieved. The technique is very flexible. With the concentration of the absorbing dye, the height range and resolution can be adapted to the expected thickness of the boundary layer.

5.3 Measurement of the CO₂ Gas Exchange Rate by Laser-Induced Fluorescence

The LIF techniques based on fluorescence pH-indicators used in phase I required reactive and toxic gases such as HCl and NH₃. We had chosen them, because the fast dissociation reactions for HCl and NH₃ make the systems rather simple. The question is whether the usage of these toxic gases can be avoided. A good candidate is CO₂. However, the hydration reaction of CO₂ is slow and thus chemical reactions and transport processes cannot be decoupled in the easy way as with HCl and NH₃. The CO₂ is transported across the aqueous mass boundary layer with a time constant that is — except for very low wind speeds — significantly faster than the rate constant for the dissociation of CO₂ (CO₂ + H₂O \rightsquigarrow HCO₃⁻ + H⁺), which is in the order of one minute at 20°C [Kern, 1960]. Thus only a small fraction of the CO₂ is converted into HCO₃⁻ while it is transported across the aqueous mass boundary layer.

However, from the pioneering LIF experiments of Asher and Pankow [1989] with grid-stirred turbulence it is known that the absorption of CO₂ in water can cause changes in the pH-value of the mass boundary layer that can be detected with fluorescent indicators. Thus we performed some simple experiments to study whether this technique is also feasible in large wind/wave tunnel studies. The basic question was if the technique works with sufficiently low concentrations. First we studied the invasion of CO₂ into deionized water with a 10⁻⁵ molar fluorescein solution close to its buffer point (close to pH 7). Under this conditions an increase of the CO₂ concentration in the air space to a few permille produced sufficient changes in the fluorescent intensity. For evasion experiments it was required to use significantly higher concentrations in water. The deionized water almost had to be saturated with CO₂. Since then the pH value is decreased to about 4, a fluorescence indicator with a pK value close to 4 had to be chosen. 2,7-dichlorofluorescein proved to be a suitable choice.

References

- [1] Asher W, and J. F. Pankow, 1989. Direct observations of concentration fluctuations close to a gas-liquid interface, *Chem. Eng. Sci.*, 44, 1451–1455.
- [2] Back, D. D., and M. J. McCreedy, 1988. STEP — a temperature profiler for measuring the oceanic thermal boundary layer at the ocean-air interface, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 93, 5143–5152.
- [3] Banner, M. L., I. S. F. Jones, and J. C. Trinder, 1989. Wavenumber spectra of short gravity waves, *J. Fluid Mech.*, 198, 321–344.
- [4] Broecker, W. S., T. H. Peng, G. Östlund, M. Stuiver, 1985. The distribution of bomb radiocarbon in the ocean, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 99: 6953–70.

- [5] Broecker, W. S., J. R. Ledwell, T. Takahashi, L. M. R. Weiss, L. Memery, T. H. Peng, B. Jähne, K. O. Münnich, 1986. Isotopic versus micrometeorologic ocean CO₂ fluxes: A serious conflict, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 91: 10517–27.
- [6] Cember R., 1989. Bomb radiocarbon in the Red Sea: A medium-scale gas exchange experiment, *J. Geo. Res.*, 94: 2111–23.
- [7] Cox C., 1958. Measurements of slopes of high frequency waves, *J. Mar. Res.*, 16:199–225
- [8] Chu C.R. and H. Jirka, 1992. Turbulent gas flux measurements below the air-water interface of a grid-stirred tank, *Int. J. Heat Mass Transfer*, 35, no. 8, 1957–1968
- [9] Danckwerts P. V., 1951. Significance of liquid-film coefficients in gas absorption, *Industrial and Engineering Chemistry* 43: 1460–1467.
- [10] Duke, S. R., and T. J. Hanratty, 1995. Measurements of the concentration field resulting from oxygen absorption at a wavy air-water interface, *Air-Water Gas Transfer*, Selected Papers, 3rd Intern. Symp. on Air-Water Gas Transfer, edited by B. Jähne and E. Monahan, AEON, Hanau, pp. 627–635.
- [11] Emerson S., P. Quay, C. Stump, D. Wilbur, M. Knox, 1991. O₂, Ar, N₂, and Rn-222 in surface waters of the subarctic ocean: Net biological production, *Global Biogeochem. Cycles*, 5:49–69.
- [12] Glover D. M., W. S. Reeburgh, 1987. Radon-222 and radium-226 in southeastern Bering Sea shelf waters and sediment, *Cont. Shelf Res.*, 5: 433–456.
- [13] Green F.J., 1990. *The Sigma-Aldrich Handbook of Stains, Dyes and Indicators*, Aldrich Chemical Company, Inc., Milwaukee, Wisconsin.
- [14] Hara, T., E. J. Bock, and D. Lyzenga, 1994. In situ measurements of capillary-gravity wave spectra using a scanning laser slope gauge and microwave radars, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 99, 12,593–12,602.
- [15] Haugland R.P., 1996. *Handbook of Fluorescent Probes and Research Chemicals*, Molecular Probes, Inc., Eugene, Oregon.
- [16] Haußecker H., S. Reinelt, B. Jähne, 1995. Heat as a proxy tracer for gas exchange measurements in the field: principle and technical realization, *Air-Water Gas Transfer*, Selected Papers, 3rd Intern. Symp. on Air-Water Gas Transfer, edited by B. Jähne and E. Monahan, AEON, Hanau, pp. 405–413.
- [17] Haußecker, H., 1996. *Messung und Simulation von kleinskaligen Austauschvorgängen an der Ozeanoberfläche mittels Thermographie*, PhD thesis, Univ. Heidelberg.
- [18] Haußecker, H. and B. Jähne, 1997. Heat as a proxy tracer for gas transfer measurements in the field: principles and results from the joint CoOP/MBL Pacific cruise, submitted to *J. Geophys. Res.*
- [19] Higbie, R., 1935. The rate of absorption of a pure gas into a still liquid during short periods of exposure, *Trans. Am. Inst. Chem. Eng.* 31: 365–389.
- [20] Hwang, P. A., S. Atakturk, M. A. Sletten, and D. B. Trizna, 1996. A study of the wavenumber spectra of short water waves in the ocean, *J. Phys. Oceanogr.*, 26, 1266–1285.
- [21] Jähne B., 1980. *Zur Parameterisierung des Gasaustausches mit Hilfe von Laborexperimenten*. PhD thesis, Univ. Heidelberg
- [22] Jähne, B., P. Libner, R. Fischer, T. Billen, E. J. Plate, 1989. Investigating the transfer processes across the free aqueous viscous boundary layer by the controlled flux method. *Tellus*, 41B:177–95.
- [23] Jähne, B., 1991. From mean fluxes to a detailed experimental investigation of the gas transfer process, *Air-Water Mass Transfer*, selected papers from the 2nd International Symposium on Gas Transfer at Water Surfaces, September 11–14, 1990, Minneapolis, Minnesota, S. C. Wilhelms and J. S. Gulliver, eds, pp. 244–256, ASCE, New York, 1991.
- [24] Jähne, B., 1997. *Digital Image Processing — Concepts, Algorithms, and Scientific Applications*, 4th completely revised edition, Springer, Berlin, in press.
- [25] Jähne, B. and H. Haußecker, 1998. Air-Water Gas Exchange, *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 30, in press (invited review paper).

- [26] Jähne, B., and J. Klinke, 1997a. Short wind waves, In *Drag at the Ocean Surface*, edited by I. Jones and Y. Toba, Cambridge University Press, in press.
- [27] Jähne, B. and J. Klinke, 1997b. Wave Number Spectra of Short Wind Waves — A Comparative Study of Laboratory and Field Results, submitted to *J. Physical Oceanogr.*.
- [28] Jähne, B., and K. Riemer, 1990. Two-dimensional wave number spectra of small-scale water surface waves, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 95, 11,531–11,546.
- [29] Kern, D. M., 1990. The hydration of carbon dioxide, *J. Chem. Education*, 37, 14–23.
- [30] Kromer B., W. Roether, 1983. Field measurements of air-sea gas exchange by the radon deficit method during JASIN (1978) and FGGE (1979), "Meteor" *Forsch. Ergebnisse*, A/B 24: 55–75.
- [31] Libner, P., 1987. The controlled flux method: a new fast and local method for investigating exchange processes at the air-water interface, PhD thesis, Univ. Heidelberg.
- [32] Liss, P. S., and R. A. Duce (eds.), 1997. *The sea surface and global change*, Cambridge Univ. Press, Cambridge, UK.
- [33] Liss, P. S., L. Merlivat, 1986. Air-sea gas exchange rates: Introduction and Synthesis, *The Role of Air-Sea Exchange in Geochemical Cycling*, edited by P. Buat-Menard, Reidel, Boston: 113–129.
- [34] Mammen, T. C., and N. Bosse, 1990. STEP — a temperature profiler for measuring the oceanic thermal boundary layer at the ocean-air interface, *J. Atmos. Oceanic Technol.*, 7, 312–322.
- [35] Masuko H., K. Okamoto, M. Shimada, and S. Niwa, 1986. Measurement of microwave backscattering signatures of the ocean surface using X band and K_a band airborne scatterometers, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 91, 13,065–13,083.
- [36] Münnich, K.O. and D. Flothmann, 1975. Gas exchange in relation to other air-sea interaction phenomena. *SCOR workshop on Air-Sea Interaction Phenomena*, Miami 8–12 Dec, 1975.
- [37] Münsterer, T., and B. Jähne, 1997. LIF measurements of concentration profiles in the aqueous mass boundary layer, submitted to *Experiments in Fluids*, May 1997.
- [38] Peng, T. H., T. Takahashi, W. S. Broecker, 1974. Surface radon measurements in the North Pacific Ocean station PAPA, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 79: 1772–1780.
- [39] Peng T. H., W. S. Broecker, G. G. Mathieu, Y. H. Li, A. E. Bainbridge, 1979. Radon evasion rates in the Atlantic and Pacific Oceans as determined during the GEOSECS program, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 84: 2471–2486.
- [40] Prinos P., M. Atmane and J. George, 1995. Gas Flux Measurements and Modelling below an Air-Water Interface, *Air-Water Gas Transfer*, Selected papers from the 3rd Int. Symp. on Air-Water Gas Transfer (eds. B. Jähne and E.C. Monahan), AEON Verlag & Studio, Hanau, Germany
- [41] Rao K. N., R. Narasimha, B. Narayanan, 1971. The bursting phenomenon in a turbulent boundary layer, *J. Fluid Mech.*, 48:339–52.
- [42] Reinelt S., 1994. Bestimmung der Transfargeschwindigkeit mittels CFT mit Wärme als Tracer, Diploma thesis, Univ. of Heidelberg.
- [43] Saunders P. M., 1967. Aerial measurements of sea surface temperature in the infrared, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 72:4109–17.
- [44] Smethie W. M., T. T. Takahashi, D. W. Chipman, J. R. Ledwell, 1985. Gas exchange and CO₂ flux in the tropical Atlantic Ocean determined from 222-Rn and pCO₂ measurements, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 90: 7005–22.
- [45] Soloviev A. V., P. Schlüssel, 1994. Parameterization of the cool skin of the ocean and of the air-ocean gas transfer on the basis of modelling surface renewal, *J. Phys. Ocean.*, 24:1339–46.
- [46] Wanninkhof R., J. R. Ledwell, W. S. Broecker, M. Hamilton, 1987. Gas exchange on Mono lake and Crowley Lake, California, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 92:14,567–80.

- [47] Wanninkhof R., 1992. Relationship between gas exchange and wind speed over the ocean, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 97:7373-81.
- [48] Wanninkhof R., W. Asher, R. Weppernig, H. Chen, P. Schlosser, C. Langdon, R. Sambrotto, 1993. Gas transfer experiment on Georges Bank using two volatile deliberate tracers, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 98: 20237-48.
- [49] Watson A. J., R. C. Upstill-Goddard, P. S. Liss, 1991. Air-sea exchange in rough and stormy seas, measured by a dual tracer technique, *Nature*, 349: 145-47.
- [50] Weiss. H., 1997. *Modulation von Windwellen*, Diploma thesis, Univ. of Heidelberg.
- [51] Wolff, L.M., Z.-C. Liu, T.J. Hanratty, 1991. A fluorescence technique to measure concentration gradients near an interface. *Air-Water Mass Transfer*, selected papers from the 2nd International Symposium on Gas Transfer at Water Surfaces, September 11-14, 1990, Minneapolis, Minnesota, S. C. Wilhelms and J. S. Gulliver, eds, pp. 210-218, ASCE, New York, 1991.

C Analysis of global gas emissions for multispectral image sequences

1 Introduction

Nitric oxides (NO and NO₂) play an important role in the anthropologically caused changes of atmospheric chemistry. They are major components in the so-called photosmog and are also responsible for high ozone concentrations in cities.

Burning of fossil fuel and biomass burning (e.g. clearing of large areas of forest in the tropics) could be identified as principal sources for NO_x [Hegg *et al.*, 1990]. For an exact determination of the emitted amount of NO_x those events have to be identified and measurements have to be performed within the plumes of NO_x. Especially for the case of biomass burning it is extremely difficult to use ground based measurement techniques, because in general the location of such events is not known beforehand. Moreover the contents of NO_x in a biomass burning plume that may have a size up to several thousand kilometers can hardly be determined using punctual ground based measurements. Only satellite based measurements allow global data acquisition that can be used to analyze the large scale effects of biomass burning.

In the present work satellite data has been evaluated to measure the NO_x contents globally. To do this it was necessary to

- develop an algorithm that calculates the amount of NO₂ and other trace gases from the spectra. The algorithm should be fast enough to process the data in *real time* (650 MB of data every three days). This has been achieved by using a new fitting method (see section 3.2) and a fast interpolation scheme known from image processing (see section 3.3).
- construct global NO₂ maps from the data. For this task it has to be taken into account that the satellite covers the earth's surface only every three days and also leaves gaps in the coverage that have to be interpolated in space and time domain (see section 3.4).
- handle the data that comes from the GOME satellite on a continuous base and to integrate the algorithms in the image processing software used by the research unit.

2 The Satellite Instrument

In April 1995, the ERS-2 satellite has been launched by the *European Space Agency* (ESA). The satellite carries besides other instruments the *Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment* (GOME) (figure C.1), an instrument that allows to measure trace gas concentrations in the atmosphere. It consists of a high-resolution spectrometer that covers a spectral range from 290 nm to 790 nm with a spectral resolution of 1024 pixels. Applying the *Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy* (DOAS) [Platt, 1994; Stutz, 1996], information about trace gases in the atmosphere (e.g. NO_x, O₃, O₄) can be obtained.

2.1 Data Acquisition

The GOME instrument looks in nadir view to the earth (perpendicular to the earth's surface) and measures a spectrum every 1.5 seconds. Using a scanning mirror the instrument takes three pixels perpendicular to the direction of flight and one backscan pixel at the end of the scanning period (see figure C.1). To control spatial resolution the width of those pixels can be modified, by changing the integration time, to 120 km, 240 km, 360 km, 480 km and 960 km whereas their height is constantly 40 km. Only for pixels larger or equal to 360 km the pixels are adjacent and global coverage of the

Figure C.1: Instrumental setup. The GOME spectrometer looks perpendicular to the earth's surface and scans a strip of three pixels perpendicular to it's direction of flight. It covers a range from 290 nm to 790 nm with a spectral resolution of 1024 pixels.

Figure C.2: Mode of the satellite's earth coverage (schematically). Orbits adjacent in time are not adjacent in space but leave a gap of the size of two orbits. Only every three days global coverage is achieved.

earth's surface is achieved. For the other cases the image formation algorithm has to fill in the gaps caused by non-adjacent pixels or missing pixels due to defective data transfer (see section 3.4).

2.2 Earth Coverage

The satellite scans the earth in orbits that are spatially not adjacent to each other but leave a gap of the size of two orbits. So after cycling the earth every day it has covered only 1/3 of the surface and scans on the following day the left adjacent orbit (figure C.2). Only every three days total coverage is obtained.

This results in the fact that in images constructed as a mean over three days portions of the image are taken at different times, comparable to interlaced TV images. To analyze motion temporal interpolation has to be applied to synchronize the orbits and interpolate the pixels to the same point in time (see section 3.4).

3 Analysis Algorithms

3.1 DOAS Technique

The DOAS (*Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy*) technique [Platt, 1994] is a well established method to calculate the concentration of trace gases c_i along a lightpath l through an absorbing layer from the absorption spectrum of the light. It's basic idea is founded on *Lambert-Beer's law*:

$$I(\lambda) = I_0(\lambda) \times \exp\left(-\sum_i \sigma_i(\lambda) S_i\right) \times A(\lambda) \quad (C.1)$$

where $I(\lambda)$ describes the measured and $I_0(\lambda)$ the initial light intensity. The sum in the exponential runs over all trace gases i in the lightpath l whose slant column density $S_i = c_i \times l$ has to be calculated. The absorption cross sections $\sigma_i(\lambda)$ are well known and are characteristic for each trace gas. The factor $A(\lambda)$ describes additional attenuation by the optical system and by *Rayleigh* and *Mie* scattering in the atmosphere. So far (C.1) can be transformed into a linear equation with respect to S_i by taking the logarithm of both sides:

$$\ln I(\lambda) = \ln I_0(\lambda) + \ln A(\lambda) - \sum_i \sigma_i(\lambda) S_i \quad (C.2)$$

The essential observation that leads to DOAS and allows to calculate S_i without the knowledge of $I_0(\lambda)$ and $A(\lambda)$ is that those quantities contain only low frequencies with respect to λ whereas the absorption cross sections $\sigma_i(\lambda)$ contain both low and high frequent proportions. They can thus be split into these contributions $\sigma_i = \sigma_i^{low} + \sigma_i^{high}$. If all low frequent proportions are modelled by a polynomial (C.2) becomes

$$\ln I(\lambda) = \sum_j a_j \lambda^j - \sum_i \sigma_i^{high}(\lambda) S_i \quad (C.3)$$

which is linear in the unknown quantities a_j and S_i and can be solved by a linear least squares method. The results of such a procedure are showed in figure C.3. It can be seen that both the evaluation of the GOME satellite data and the CO₂ spectra taken from the experiments in subproject B can be handled very well with the DOAS technique.

In practice additional difficulty is introduced by the fact that the reference measurements have to be performed with a different setup than the GOME instrument itself. The inherent uncertainty in the wavelength calibration of the diverse instruments causes a slight mismatch of the wavelengths at which the reference absorption cross sections and the light intensity measured by the satellite are sampled. The problem is further complicated by possible changes in the wavelength calibration of the GOME instrument due to thermal dilatation of the spectrograph during an orbit. Those effects have to be corrected by a wavelength remapping.

This can be done by introducing an additional polynomial in the argument of the absorption cross section $\sigma(\lambda) \rightarrow \sigma(\sum_k b_k \lambda^k)$ leading to a non-linear problem.

The goal of this work is to solve this equation as fast and as accurate a possible as for the evaluation of a total coverage a total of $O(10^4)$ spectra have to be evaluated in three days. The main problems are that the number of unknown parameters is large (typically 20 - 30) and that the absorption cross sections $\sigma(\lambda)$ that are known as discrete samples have to be evaluated at intermediate grid points due to the dispersion relation. So this work consists of

- the adaptation of a new fitting algorithm taking into account that most of the parameters in (C.3) are linear and only those describing the dispersion relation are non-linear (see section 3.2).
- the application of a fast interpolation algorithm that combines both interpolation accuracy and speed (see section 3.3).

3.2 Fitting Algorithm

To minimize the number of fit parameters in the non-linear fit an algorithm of *Ottoy and Vansteenkiste* [] has been adapted. In each step of the fit (C.3) is solved with respect to the linear parameters a_i and S_i using a linear least squares method (normal equations). After substituting the result in (C.3) the

Figure C.3: Example of a fitting process using the DOAS technique on both a GOME spectrum and CO₂ spectrum taken in the wind wave facility in Heidelberg. The deep blue curves show the fit results, respectively the applied reference spectra. To better evaluate to goodness of fit the residual (difference between fit and original data) has been overlaid as a cyan curve. Additionally the polynomial used in (C.3) to model the low frequent proportions of the spectrum has been plotted as a red curve in the first figure of each column. It can be seen that the consideration of such a polynomial is essential as the reference spectra only model the differential contributions.

Figure C.4: Normalized convolution has been used for interpolation in space domain. On each pyramid level the missing information is filled in from besides what results in partial information at those points. Full information is interpolated in the normalization step by dividing the original image by the image mask. The selection of the pyramid level on which the division is performed determines the size of the gaps in the image that can be closed.

non-linear iterative step has only to be performed on the remaining b_k non-linear parameters whereas in a normal method all parameters would have been treated a non-linear. This results in a reduction of the non-linear parameters of approx. 50% what causes a faster convergence than with the direct method.

3.3 B-Spline Interpolation

In the non-linear version of (C.3) the absorption cross sections have to be evaluated at arbitrary wavelengths λ due to the unknown dispersion relation. As they are only known as discretely sampled spectra this implies the need for an interpolation algorithm.

The most suitable interpolation algorithm is the *B-spline interpolation*. B-splines of order n , $\beta^n(\lambda)$, are piecewise continuous polynomial functions that form a base for all piecewise continuous polynomial functions. The signal may thus be decomposed in B-splines and so be evaluated at arbitrary wavelengths

$$\sigma(\lambda) = \sum_{i=-\infty}^{\infty} c_i \beta^n(\lambda). \quad (\text{C.4})$$

Unser et al. [1991] showed that the decomposition can be done very fast using a recursive filter scheme and also describes an algorithm that calculates the evaluation at intermediate grid points with only 4 additions and 4 multiplications for B-splines of order 3. As an additional advantage once the decomposition has been performed the derivatives of the signal with respect to λ - that are required during the fitting algorithm - can be computed *exactly* using forward differences on the decomposition coefficients c_i [Jähne, 1991].

3.4 Image Interpolation in Space and Time Domain

3.4.1 Interpolation in Time Domain

As described in section 2.2 global coverage is achieved only every three days. Therefore a three days image consists of data points taken at different times that have to be corrected.

To correct this a B-spline interpolation in time direction on each single day layer has been used. To generate a full image synchronized with the second day subimage, the first day subimage is predicted using the sequence of first day images for one day in positive time direction and the third day subimage in negative time direction. Those subimages are then overlaid to construct an interpolated full image synchronized with the second day subimage. By cycling the day index full images can be generated for every day.

3.4.2 Interpolation in Space Domain

To fill in gaps in the time corrected images caused by defective or non adjacent pixels (see section 2.1) interpolation in space domain is required. In contrast to the case of missing information in time domain missing information in space domain is distributed non uniformly in the image. So B-spline

Table C.1: Comparison of the fit coefficients S_i between the new DOAS algorithm and an older DOAS-algorithm [Stutz and Platt,]. Both algorithms worked on the same measured data and the same reference spectra.

Reference spectrum	new algorithm	old algorithm	deviation
Fraunhofer	0.996	1.005	0.9%
NO ₂	1.205×10^{16}	1.220×10^{16}	1.25%
O ₃	2.915×10^{19}	2.980×10^{19}	2.23%
O ₄	0.273	0.275	0.7%

interpolation - that relies on information available on a regular grid - cannot be used. Instead the images are interpolated using *normalized convolution* (see figure C.4, [Jähne, 1991]).

For each concentration image $g(x)$ a mask image $m(x)$ is constructed that contains 1 for pixels containing information and 0 else. The interpolation is done by constructing a pyramid over the image and by dividing the masked image $m(x)g(x)$ by the image mask on a certain pyramid level. This is equivalent to convoluting both maps with a smoothing filter $B(x)$ and a subsequent division:

$$g_{ipol}(x) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} m(x')g(x')B(x-x')dx' \bigg/ \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} m(x')B(x-x')dx' \quad (C.5)$$

The pyramid level on which the division takes place has to be chosen such that the gaps are filled in but to avoid loss of detail due to blurring. For the computation of the images in figure C.6 the first pyramid level has been chosen.

4 Results

4.1 Retrieval of Trace Gas Concentrations

Applying the algorithms in sections 3.2 and 3.3 to the satellite data an new DOAS algorithm has been developed and integrated in the standard image processing software used by the research group. To verify the algorithm its results have been tested against an older DOAS algorithm currently used by the group of atmospheric physics of Prof. Platt. The results are shown in figure C.5 and table C.1. In spite of minor divergences both algorithms yield the same result, the deviations are likely due to different interpolation techniques and will be object of further research.

The algorithm could be sped up significantly: the evaluation of a full GOME orbit (approx. 1950 spectra) takes 2 : 05 h with the old algorithm and 0 : 20 h with the new algorithm resulting in an increase of speed by a factor of 6. So the evaluation of a total coverage consisting of 36 orbits every three days takes 12 h and can be performed in real time.

4.2 Image Generation

Parallel to the development of the retrieval algorithm, the image generation algorithms have been developed and implemented. The visualization algorithms explained in section 3.4 have been tested on pre-evaluated NO₂ data by the ESA. Results can be seen in figure C.6 showing the difference between the global NO₂ distribution in summer and winter time.

5 Interchange of Algorithms

- The normalized convolution has been implemented together with the botany subproject D to work on pyramids.
- The DOAS algorithm has been used to evaluate the CO₂ measurements in subproject B (see figure C.3).
- For most image processing algorithms the standard image processing software *Heurisko* has been used.
- The data visualization software developed in this work is also used in the research group of atmospheric physics at the University of Heidelberg.

NO₂ evaluation of a GOME orbit, sep. 13th 1996

Figure C.5: Comparison between the new DOAS algorithm and an older DOAS algorithm [Stutz and Platt, 1996]. The evaluation covers a total orbit of GOME data so sun zenith angles from -80° to $+80^\circ$ occur. Both evaluations correlate well, divergences can be explained by the usage of a different subsampling algorithm and will be object of further research.

References

- [1] Balzer, W. and Loyola, D. *Product Specification of the GOME Data Processor*, ER-PS-DLR-GO-0016, Iss./Rev.3/B, Deutsche Forschungsanstalt für Luft- und Raumfahrt, Deutsches Fernerkundungsdatenzentrum, 1996
- [2] European Space Agency, Bednarz, F. *Global Ozone Monitoring Experiment, GOME, Users Manual*, ESA Publications Division, 1995
- [3] Hegg, D.A., Radke, L.F., Hobbs, P.V., Rasmussen, R.A., and Riggan, P.J. Emissions of Some Trace Gases from Biomass Fires, *J. Geophys. Res.*, 95, 5669–5676, 1990
- [4] Jähne, B. *Digital Image Processing: Concepts, Algorithms and Scientific Applications*, Springer Verlag, 1991
- [5] Ottoy, J.P. and Vansteenkiste, G.C. A computer algorithm for non-linear curve fitting, Department of Applied Mathematics, University of Gent, Coupure Links 533, 9000 Gent, Belgium
- [6] Platt, U. *Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy (DOAS), Air Monitoring by Spectroscopic Techniques*, M.W. Sigrist, Ed., John Wiley & Sons, Inc., 1994
- [7] Stutz, J. *Messung der Konzentration troposphärischer Spurenstoffe mittels Differentieller-Optischer-Absorptionsspektroskopie, Eine neue Generation von Geräten und Algorithmen*, PhD thesis, Universität Heidelberg, 1996
- [8] Stutz, J. and Platt, U. Numerical analysis and error estimation of Differential Optical Absorption Spectroscopy Measurements with Least-Squares Methods, *Appl. Optics*, 35, No. 30, 6041–6053, 1996
- [9] Unser, M., Aldroubi, A. and Eden, M. Fast B-Spline Transforms for Continuous Image Representation and Interpolation, *IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, 13, No. 3, March 1991

Figure C.6: NO₂ maps generated from operational ESA data. The maps are corrected in the time domain; for the spatial interpolation a first order pyramid has been used. Figure (a) shows the NO₂ distribution from July 28, 1996, figure (b) from February 20, 1997.

D Time and Space-Resolved Measurements of Growth in Plants

1 Summary

This project aims to set up a multi-channel imaging system to monitor dynamic processes in growing plant organs. To achieve this in the medium term, several techniques visualising the relevant quantities have to be developed in the first hand. Growth distribution analysis provides the framework for the entire project. A 2D-method has been developed during the first phase of the research unit on the base of the structure tensor algorithm developed for motion analysis in the central project. An experimental set up was developed, which allows to acquire image sequences of growing leaves during day and night without disturbance of the plant's physiology and with sufficient contrast to analyse growth spatially at a temporal resolution of approximately 15 minutes. The structure tensor algorithm and a normalised convolution method were combined to obtain growth maps. These were successfully evaluated versus standard techniques. As a first botanical application, diurnal variations in growth distribution were studied in dicot leaves, already with unique results. In preparation of the 3D-technique needed for full analysis of a freely moving leaf, a camera mount was developed, which allows to sample image sequences needed for 3D-reconstruction of the leaf as the base for further growth analysis.

Transpiration was chosen as the first physiological quantity to be visualised. A passive thermography method was developed, in which the difference in the surface temperatures between the leaf and Tetenal-coated brass plates could be proofed to be closely related to transpiration rate. The temperature difference closely mimicked the dynamic change in transpiration rate in experiments, in which CO₂-concentration or light conditions were varied to change transpiration rates. Additionally, an active thermography technique was established, which allows to determine the distribution of heat capacities on the leaf. A combination of these two techniques will allow to analyse local transpiration rates on the leaf by IR-imaging.

In preparation for future applications, two set ups for root growth analysis were developed. These are presently investigated for their usability with algorithms developed in the central project for particle motion analysis. Imaging of calcium concentration in living plants was prepared for by developing the set up and by implementing the image acquisition routines needed in the software package.

2 Introduction

Growing plant organs are very dynamic systems. Growth itself is a dynamic process and is accompanied by differentiation of physiological function. These processes are interconnected, but very little is known about this, on part due to technical problems of the analysis. In the medium term, this project aims to establish a multichannel approach to combine (1) spatially and temporally resolved analysis of growth rate distribution and (2) analysis of physiological and biochemical functions. Both of these can be visualised in image sequences. This aim should be approached in three steps listed in the last proposal. First, growth analysis has to be addressed and evaluated and then physiological measurements can be based on these. This approach has been followed, but due to the shortening of the funding period priorities were given to the following topics: (1) The development of a method for analysis of growth rate distribution in dicot leaves, as this would provide a novel tool, which will open an entirely new field of research on plant growth. (2) Spatially-resolved thermographic analysis of the leaf surface temperature was envisaged as a novel approach to determine the distribution of gas exchange on a leaf. (3) Two additional topics - root growth analysis and imaging of cytoplasmic free calcium concentrations with transgenic plants expressing Aequorin - were studied with lower priority, in order to prepare future applications planned during the second grant period.

Figure D.1: 100 images of a sequence of *Ricinus* (approx. 8 h) stacked to a cube. The cube is cut in the x - t and y - t plane (time pointing into the plane). The principal axis of growth is from left to right. It can be seen how the features along the principal axis become oriented at larger angles toward the tip of the leaf.

3 Leaf Growth Analysis

3.1 Botanical objectives

Environmental and genetic constraints limit leaf growth. The overall growth rate of a leaf is determined by the integral growth rate over the entire leaf blade, but the underlying mechanisms are localised processes. For example, it has been shown for roots that the decline in growth rate in response to temperature is due to a decline in growth intensity while the constant length of the growth zone stays constant. Contrary, the decline in response to drought is due to a shortening of the growth zone without changes in the local intensities of growth rate of the remaining expansion zone [Silk, 92]. Similar experiments are difficult to perform for dicot leaves, though they represent the major number of plant species, due to technical problems analysing areal expansion of the leaf blade. Image sequence analysis provides an interesting alternative in this context.

3.2 Approach

As proposed, the first step to address analysis of dicot leaf growth with image sequence analysis was the development of a 2D-technique for the estimation of the distribution of growth rate on *Ricinus* leaves. Introductory experiments already showed that this approach will not be sufficient in all cases: (1) A 2D-approach requires the leaf to be fixed at a defined focal plane relative to the camera during image acquisition (see below). Control experiments showed that the final leaf size changed by as much as 30%, when the leaf was clamped [Heckenberger, 96]. (2) Preliminary image sequences of growing castor bean plants showed considerable 3D-distorsion in a regular manner during the diurnal course of leaf growth.

Nevertheless the 2D-approach was taken for several reasons. (1) algorithms were already available at the start of the project and significant improvements of these were envisaged within the framework of the research unit. (2) Classical techniques for leaf growth analysis, mainly developed for monocot leaves, also only offer an integrated measure along a single axis of growth without spatial resolution. Spatial resolution along the main growth axis would already allow botanical reasoning for differences in leaf growth. A full 3D analysis of growth and motion is necessary when dicot leaf growth shall be investigated under most undisturbed conditions, but significant progress could be claimed by a 2D-method with spatial resolution along the main axis. Additionally, it was expected that areal information could be obtained at those sites that remain in the focal plane.

3.3 Basic Principle of the 2D-Analysis

The 2D approach is based on the following assumption: When the leaf is fixed in a plane perpendicular to the direction of view of the camera the projected area is directly proportional to the true area of the leaf. The proportionality can be gained from adequate calibration techniques, which need to be accurate and easy to handle for practical purposes. Such procedures were developed during the first phase in project A and immediately introduced in our image acquisition protocol.

From a sequence of images it is then possible to get a map of the local motion of features on the leaf surface by appropriate low level image processing as provided by project A. Leaf growth will lead to local changes in velocity. For example if the base of the leaf is fixed the tip moves at a certain speed which corresponds to the integrated growth rates of all points in-between. For this reason the divergence (spatial derivative) of the displacement vector field (DVF) is calculated as a direct measure of growth.

The principle of the technique is that a stack is built from the images of a sequence. Inside this stack the displacement of structures is analysed by evaluating the local orientations of grey value structures relative to the temporal axis. If a feature is not moving, it will have a trajectory in the 3D-stack of images, which is parallel to the time axis. An angle relative to the time axis indicates that the local features moves (see Figure D.1).

3.4 Development of the 2D-Analysis

The 2D-analysis of growth distribution required (1) a suitable set up to obtain image sequences and (2) the software implementation. A set up had to be designed, which meets the botanical and image-analytical criteria. On the one hand, the physiology of the plant has to be disturbed as little as possible. On the other hand, image sequences must be acquired suitable for analysis with the algorithms developed in the central project has to be guaranteed. This is an example for the necessity of close interaction of central project and the experience present in application projects. The development of the set up and the algorithms proceeded partly in parallel. This situation required a modular design of the software, which allows easy implementation of e.g. improved versions of low level image sequence processing like the structure tensor without changes in the user interfaces. This task should not be underestimated, since it requires clear and congruent design of software interfaces, on which the interaction between the central project and the software development in this project is based. Application-specific design of the software is also needed. This includes the specific adaptations to botanical objects and the development of a handy user interface.

3.5 Development of the Experimental Set Up

3.5.1 Classical Growth Analysis - Set Up for Evaluation

One important task during the development of the growth analysis was the evaluation of the output from this method with classical methods used in botanical research. Previously experiments on the dynamics of growth were carried out in the Institute of Botany during a Ph.D. thesis. As a variation of the classical set up using a linear voltage distance transducer (LVDT) the core of this set up is a rotary position transducer with a pivot. At the one end of the pivot the leaf was attached via a twine. An adjustable weight was located on the counter end of the pivot to keep the twine under tension. This sensor was built into a large frame to which the plant could be fixed. The observed leaf was confined by a set of nylon filaments in a way that it could not move out of the plane of movement. The firm integration into the massive frame and the tight fixation of the plant were crucial for the high temporal resolution achieved by this set up [Heckenberger, 96]. By altering the length of the pivot a temporal resolution down to a few minutes was possible.

This set up was improved for the validation of the image-based growth analysis. The sensor of the old set up could only operate linearly in a small regime since the position and the exerted force is a trigonometric function of the angle. For this reason the sensor needed regular repositioning and recalibration for the new position. These problems could be solved by replacing the lever with a twin spool. One part spools up the twine attached to the leaf, the other part spools down a twine holding the weight. This way the position is linearly related to the angular signal which makes calibration simple and the tension on the string is kept independent of the angular position.

Figure D.2: Two modes of illumination of Ricinus (left) and tobacco (right) at selected wavelength. The upper and lower samples are imaged in reflection and transmission of the light respectively (see text for further details).

3.5.2 Illumination

The selection of a light source and an appropriate illumination technique is paramount for the acquisition of image sequences. On the one hand (1) images with a high contrast and a good resolution of small features are needed. (2) The intensity of the illumination should not vary with time. On the other hand, plants respond very sensibly to radiation of certain wavelength. This is not only true for light driving photosynthetic processes, but also development processes (like flowering induction) are triggered by even very low intensities. Since it was known from previous experiments that a significant portion of growth activity occurs during the night, (3) a mode of illumination preferably not in the visual range of wavelength had to be chosen, since physiological sensitivities are mainly present in the VIS-range. For this reason we have examined the optical properties of Ricinus and tobacco in two illumination modes and at different wavelengths. In the first set up the leaf was illuminated from the same side as the camera in a slight angle to the viewing direction. In the second set up the leaf was backilluminated. In both cases a broadband lamp has been used. The wavelength selection was achieved by a variable interference filter in front of CCD objective.

In figure D.2 results of both techniques are shown for two species (Ricinus and tobacco) at selected wavelengths. Between species it can be seen that Ricinus exhibits more and finer structures than tobacco. This makes Ricinus a good candidate for the motion analysis because fine features of good contrast are needed for a good spatial resolution. If the images from transmission and reflection are compared, it is striking that in reflection the veins appear dark whereas in transmission they appear light. For the near infrared this can be explained by the structure of the leaf: The reflected light is basically back-scattered from the various phase transitions in the sponge parenchyma. Since the material of the veins is denser with less cavities, less light is scattered and the light it transmitted better. A detailed analysis of light capture by leaves can be found in [Vogelmann *et al.*, 96]. This hypothesis is further supported by the fact that the reflection in the near IR has only a small portion of specular reflection (data not shown here). In conclusion, illumination in the near IR exhibits all the properties required: (1) a good contrast of the image in reflection, (2) it is physiologically inactive (3) it is reflected diffusely. The latter will become even more important when the leaf is observed from different viewing angles, as will be the case in the 3D analysis.

To take advantage of the physiological inactivity of the near IR, it is important to use a narrow band IR light source. Fortunately such a source is available in the form of IR-LED. Therefore, in the optimised set up the leaf was illuminated from the same side as the camera by two IR-LED arrays of 100 LEDs each. The LEDs have a narrow emission peak at 940nm. This technique has previously been developed in project B. No physiological sensitivity to this wavelength is known and absorption of radiation of this wavelength is small [Larcher, 80]. On the other hand, the CCD-cameras are still sensitive at that range of wavelength. The measurements were taken in a growth chamber equipped with mercury-vapour-

Figure D.3: Optical leaf growth analysis set up: (1) the leaf under observation (2) rigid frame of X-95 profiles (3) small lever for the fixation of the base of the leaf (4) standard CCD camera (5) rotary position transducer for the classical length measurement.

lamps, which emit significant radiation in the near infrared range. This led to significant changes of brightness of the images between day and night. To suppress the contribution of ambient light a IR pass filter (Schott RG830) was placed in front of the camera. A further significant improvement for further discrimination of ambient light and LED-illumination is envisaged, by using the LED arrays in a flashed mode, thus attaining a more homogenous level of illumination in the day-night transition.

3.5.3 Mechanical Design

For the first optical set up used in a preliminary experiments, a standard CCD camera and an IR-LED array were supported by a laboratory stand and a *Ricinus communis* plant was fixed to a second one. During this experiment, 1 frame was taken every 5 minutes over a period of approx. 80 hours. Evaluation of the sequence revealed that it was of limited usefulness, due to motion discontinuities. The resolution of rapid changes is very dependent on a method to suppress displacement of the camera, relative to the leaf. A good resolution requires a stability of the set up down to the tens of microns. High temporal resolution is needed especially in studies concerning growth responses in the range of minutes. Since very small displacements have to be detected, it is necessary to fix the camera relative to the leaf. For the sake of comparison to the classical length measurements, the fixation was done relative to the leaf base, and the main axis of growth was clamped to the focal plane. Integration of estimated growth rates along this axis could then be used to evaluate the method. The filaments holding the entire leaf blade in the focal plane had to be removed since they caused significant disturbance of the motion analysis.

Additional improvement was achieved, when the set up was transferred on heavy stands (X-95 profiles) so that it became more rigid, easier to modify and significantly more compact than the previous set up (figure D.3). This is a significant improvement, since the set up must be mobile enough to be transferred between growth cabinets with different growing conditions. At the same time it will be necessary for routine analysis to run several systems in parallel so that compact systems are wanted.

However, the removal of the nylon filaments led to a new problem, as wind-induced shaking of the leaf occurred now. The frequency of the leaf shaking is about 1 Hz and is therefore subsampled at an acquisition rate of 1 frame/min or less. This can severely flaw the measured displacement vectors. Since wind is required for the climatisation of the growth cabinet and cannot be turned off, the problem had to be solved on the software side of the acquisition system. Since the shaking movement of the leaf is rapid, it is possible to sample a sequence of a few seconds at normal video rate (30 frames/sec). When images of this sequence are summed up, the resulting image is an image of the mean position during that sequence, and brings the additional advantage of a reduced signal-to-noise-ratio. The summation of 81 frames therefore stabilised motion analysis and makes evaluation at low light levels feasible. Sequences could now be acquired with the same aperture during night and day measurement without having to change the illumination. Smearing of the contours by the summation did not cause significant problems. A comparison of the two approaches (single shot image, integrated image) can be seen in Figure D.4.

3.6 Development and Implementation of the Algorithms

3.6.1 Structure tensor

The core technique of the 2D growth analysis is a low level motion analysis. The motion is estimated by the so called "structure tensor" approach in an implementation by Dr. Haussecker of project A.

The properties of interest for the local orientation analysis can be fully described mathematically by the structure tensor. Orientation is then retained by an eigenvalue analysis of this tensor and divergence vector fields are equivalent to local growth rates. For a more detailed description of the structure tensor see progress report of Project A.

The first version of the structure tensor was implemented already at the beginning of this project. Motion analysis was performed for the central image of a 7 frame sequence by the structure tensor algorithm. In the first implementation the only measure of confidence was the sum of all eigenvalues from the tensor analysis. This value is strongly dependent on the local contrast and brightness of the image. This makes it difficult to find a global threshold to select pixels that hold valid information for the motion analysis. As a response to these problems in our application, Dr. Haussecker introduced normalised values for confidence (coherence) and type (edge, corner) (see report from project A for more details). The new confidence measure compensates automatically for different levels of brightness. Basically a confidence measure of 1 means ideal orientation and 0 that a statement cannot be made. Experience from our image sequences shows that a confidence level of 0.8 (all pixel with confidence measure ≥ 0.8 are taken into account) yield good results in our application. This improvement of the algorithm allowed us to use the same algorithms without alteration of the parameters for the evaluation of sequences acquired under day time illumination and night time illumination.

If optical growth analysis is to be used in routine analysis or as an online measurement prior to biochemical probing, the speed of the algorithm becomes important. Therefore it was another important contribution from project A to this application that in the first step of calculating the structure tensor its size could be reduced by a factor of 4, meaning a gain in speed of the same factor for all subsequent operations. If the smoothing mask is big enough it is possible to subsample the data in the same step thus achieving another reduction of a factor of 2 in the spatial directions. Calculation speed was greatly enhanced due to the reduction of the number of calculations on the structure tensor. Further, due to the reduced size of the results, the data all fitted into 64 MB of memory and no sectioning of the data was needed. This allowed us to run the same algorithm on a computer with less RAM.

3.6.2 Normalised Convolution

Motion analysis by the structure tensor depends on local grey value structures. In previous techniques landmarks were artificially placed on the leaf surface. This technique has limitations, because only a small number of landmarks can be applied without significant disturbance of the physiology of the plant. We therefore aimed to use natural structures on the leaves as the base for image sequence analysis. These structures mainly are determined by the venation of the leaf. The most relevant motion data are delivered by point-like structures like branching points of the veins. This is due to the aperture problem, which determines that linear structures in an imaged frame can only reveal motion estimates in the direction perpendicular to the structural orientation.

Local differences in structural density and in their relevance for motion analysis caused the divergence vector field to be filled sparsely and uneven. Normalised convolution in a pyramidal data

structure was used as an interpolation technique. Normalised convolution is a technique that allows a weighting of the grey values of each pixel, which contributes to the final growth map. The input to the algorithm is the image itself and an image that holds weighting factor for each pixel, e.g. 0 or 1 (pixel is valid or not). The image is then multiplied by the weights and both the image and the weighing mask are smoothed. Then, the smoothed and weighted image is divided by the smoothed mask. In the resulting image each pixel is a weighted average of the neighbouring pixels. If smoothing with large masks is required the plain convolution becomes very time consuming. Therefore it is convenient to use the fact that a certain degree of smoothing makes it possible to subsample the image, for example, the size can be reduced by taking into account every second pixel only. This reduction is referred to as a pyramid and has been used in the implementation of the normalised convolution. In the case of growth analysis a Gaussian pyramid was build (this is smoothing pyramid in which binomial smoothing is applied on each level) to the 4th level in order to get stable results.

There was significant interaction between project C and D in this context. It is typical for both applications that the sparsity of the data from satellites and from divergence vector fields is not uniformly distributed over the image. When an interpolation of all missing pixels is the aim of the normalised convolution, a significant smoothing is often required that affects even the areas of high information density. To take the information density into account some work was done in collaboration with project C. The approach involves looking whether at the different levels of the weight pyramid information has been recovered, i. e. whether the respective weighting factor is not equal to zero. The actual pixel value is then deduced from the corresponding pyramid level.

3.6.3 Masking of the Area of Interest

In our application motion discontinuity is obviously occurring at the margins of the leaf. This causes significant errors in the interpolation of the vector fields. Initially, a global threshold was tested to discriminate the background because the leaf is usually brighter than the background. However, this approach selected bright features in the background as well. The interim solution has been to select the largest labelled object, and this has worked well so far. Nevertheless, a more general approach will be needed in the future. It is planned to enhance masking by applying techniques like adaptive contour models, which will be needed for the modelling of the leaf in the 3D-approach as well.

3.6.4 Description of the User Interface

The software for growth analysis has been split into three functional units for convenience, and reasons of efficient memory management:

1. The acquisition module is designed for the easy acquisition of image sequences and the corresponding calibration images. It is designed to be a piece of software, which can be used universally in sampling image sequences for leaf and root growth studies.
2. The evaluation module is used for calculating the divergence of the motion field from the image sequence. It contains the core routines for motion field analysis, which were developed in the central project. For the botanical user it is only necessary to adapt a few variables as source names, result names, source and destination paths, and the basic time step for the evaluation.
3. The visualisation module holds a collection of routines for the display and presentation of the results. This includes the preparation of image sequences showing the distribution of growth rate over the leaf area, which can then be combined to form e.g. MPEG sequences illustrating the output of the analysis by colour-coding. For the ease of the user, a colour coding scheme has been implemented that realises a superposition of a pseudo colour image to the original image. Alternatively, growth distribution can be visualised by a x-t-plot of the divergence (figure D.8). These plots are constructed by taking individual lines from the calculated sequence of divergence, hence growth distribution. An example can be seen in figure D.8 where the line parallel to the main growth axis is sampled through all images of the sequence and lined up in temporal direction.

3.7 Validation and First Results

3.7.1 Stability of the 2D-Analysis

For all evaluation sequences a sampling rate of 1 frame/min was chosen in order to investigate the stability of motion estimation based on different time steps. In the current set up with a spatial res-

Figure D.4: Comparison of the two acquisition techniques. Data was sampled at a rate of 1/2 frame/min. For each sample a sequence of 81 images at video rate (30 frames/sec) was recorded. The 40th image was taken as input for the single image evaluation and the sum of the sequence for the integrated sequence approach. It can be seen that most noise on the single image data is due to the subsampled wind induced shaking.

Figure D.5: Optical growth rates calculated from the same sequence with different time steps.

olution of 20 pixel/mm and a velocity at the tip of the leaf of 2 mm/h, the maximal displacement is 0.6 pixel/frame when every frame is evaluated. Doing the analysis with different time steps shows whether the data is consistent over time and whether small displacements are detected correctly. Figure D.5 shows the relative growth rate calculated with 1 min and 2 min time steps on the basis of a night time sequence of Ricinus leaves. Comparison of the two curves proves the good stability of the set up and the motion analysis.

3.7.2 Validation against Previous Techniques

To validate the new optical technique, sequences were sampled from Ricinus communis leaves in parallel to online length detection with the previous set up (continuous length measurement). The motion field for each image of the sequence was calculated and the velocity of the tip of the leaf was compared to the time derivative of the length measured with the previously used technique. Since the base of the leaf is fixed the two quantities should be equal. Figure D.6 shows the optical growth rate and the signal from the classical length sensor. The graph shows good agreement between the two techniques. The optical technique exhibits a smoother curve. Further, a huge oscillation in the derivation of the length data by the mechanical set up can be seen (i.e. around the 500th frame). This oscillation is an artefact, due to the adjustment of the plant that needs to be done every once in a while to compensate for the

Figure D.6: Comparison of the velocity data at the tip of the leaf obtained from optical analysis to classical on-line length detection.

stem and the petiole. It is inherent to the mathematics of the velocity estimation that such singular events add very little perturbation to the signal in optical leaf growth analysis.

Additional evaluation is currently been carried out to validate the spatial resolution of growth rates by comparison with analysis of the distortion of artificially introduced landmarks.

3.7.3 Estimation of the Distribution of Growth Rate in a Diurnal Course

The proposal lists a set of experimental conditions, in which the growth analysis will be applied (drought, nutrient stress, transgenic plants). These measurements are presently done. To begin with, growth analysis was performed during several diurnal courses resulting in maps of growth distribution (figure D.7). In order to analyse the local change of growth rate during a diurnal course a x-t-plot of the divergence was constructed for the line along the major axis of growth (figure D.8, right). Growth rates were colour-coded in the same way as in the original image sequence. The shown sequence starts at 8:10 pm when light is turned off and ends at 6:30 am shortly before the light is turned on again. It can clearly be seen that there is little growth at the beginning of the dark period. In the morning hours the leaf starts growing strongly in distinct areas near the base of the leaf. A second region of higher growth activity was observed towards the tip of the leaf. It is currently under investigation if this region is regularly observed. This would be the first report on such uneven distribution of growth - a result, which was not possible to obtain with methods used previously.

Figure D.7: A typical example of a growth map from a *Ricinus* series. The relative growth values are colour coded and superposed to the original image. The leaf is slightly pulled to the right by a string that holds the leaf in position and is used for an online length detection. You can see an area with a high relative growth rate (almost 100). The image dimensions are about 80x60 mm.

Figure D.8: x-t plots of the velocity and the growth (divergence) of the *Ricinus* night time sequence. The line parallel to the main growth axis was sampled. This line is sampled through all images of the sequence and lined up in temporal direction. The sequences start at the top and end at the bottom. The leaf base is to the left and leaf tip to the right. The images are pseudo colour coded growth/velocity maps.

Figure D.9: The swinging camera set up: (1) standard CCD camera (or other) (2) arm of the swinging mount (3) plant under observation (4) counter weight for the swinging mount.

3.8 Experiments in Preparation for Follow-Up Techniques

On the basis of the experience, which we gained during the first phase of the project, the decision was taken that (1) further improvement of the 2D-method is needed to generalise the method and transfer it to model plants of modern plant molecular biology like tobacco and Arabidopsis and (2) that a 3D-method would abolish some of the restrictions, which were already realised in the 2D-approach. Some effort has been taken to support this future task.

3.8.1 Adaptation of Method for Tobacco Leaves

A number of image sequences were taken with growing tobacco leaves. The images had less contrast than in Ricinus leaves and this burdened the analysis. However, significant improvement is expected from a systematic analysis of the optical properties of tobacco and other species in the near IR-range (see below).

3.8.2 3D-Set Up

A structure-from-motion approach will be used to sample 3D-information of growing leaves as a basis for mapping growth. The advantage of this technique against structure-from-stereo, which has already been evaluated in a previous diploma thesis [Schmundt, 95], is that the correspondence problem is reduced to the determination of local motion features in the image, hence the same set of algorithms can be used as in the 2D growth analysis. Anyhow the 3D reconstruction will have to be stored in a parametrised way that allows comparison of consecutive representations, e.g. a modified version of Kalman snakes. Adaptation needed to match the representation of the veinal system in consecutive images can be interpreted as growth-related motion.

In preparation of the extension to 3D, a swinging camera mount was designed. The swing consists of a single X-95 profile with a counter weight attached. At the top end a second profile provides space

for the camera to be attached. This way the arm with the camera can swing freely like a pendulum. The oscillation can be driven by a motor so that continuous observation is possible. The radius of the swing is approximately 1 m and with the motor engaged the amplitude of the motion is in the range of 400 mm. This can be regarded as a reasonable stereo base if comparison of the structure-from-motion approach to a stereo technique is wanted (see figure D.9).

The massive build for the swinging mount was selected in view of future multichannel acquisition systems, i. e. the swing was dimensioned to hold any camera available in the research unit including even the Amber Radiance 1 IR-camera system. This feature has already been useful for the measurement of angular distribution of IR-reflectivity in project B. Project A has already started to use this set up for calibration of motion and for retrieval of the 3D information.

4 Root Growth Analysis

4.1 Botanical Objectives

Root growth exemplifies a linear arrangement of growth organisation. The root grows only at the very tip. The expansion zone extends usually for the first 6 to 12 millimetres of the root depending on the plant species. Root growth studies are the basis of much of the knowledge about growth physiology in plants. Nevertheless the temporal and spatial resolution of classical methods are not sufficient to study short term responses of roots. Due to the redefinition of the aims in response to the reviewing of the research unit, less priority was given to root growth analysis and the work on root growth during the first phase concentrated on optimising the set up for image sequence acquisition to prepare future work.

4.2 Set Up for Root Growth Analysis

A significant difference between root tips and leaves for visualisation of growth is that roots lack natural landmarks on the root surface, which could be used in motion analysis. Therefore particles have to be attached artificially. Previous experiments revealed that graphite dust was suited to be adsorbed at the root surface without significant loss of particles, even in nutrient solution.

Roots depict negative phototropism (grow away from light). Therefore the set up again required illumination at wavelengths where no physiological activity was to be expected. From the previous positive experience using near infrared radiation, the use of a similar set up for root growth observation appeared feasible.

Another basic requirement is the supply of nutrients and water to the root. Since the root has no cuticle, it must be held at almost 100% humidity. Since we aim for measuring the response to short-term variations of nutrients the possibility of a fast and efficient change of nutrient conditions had to be ensured.

Two different set ups were designed and are presently under investigation:

1. An aeroponic system, in which nutrient solution is sprayed on the roots and which is optimised for exact supply of nutrients was modified to allow additional observation of growing root tips. The main component of this system is a vertical tube in which the nutrient solution is sprayed on the root growing freely in the air. This system guarantees a very good supply and exchangeability of nutrients at the root since the turbulent flux keeps the boundary layer on the root surface at a minimum. For visualisation a flat window of acrylic glass was inserted at one side of the tube. Modes of fixation of the root still have to be evaluated.
2. A hydroponic system consisting of two glass plates with a small gap in between has been set up. The gap is continuously flushed by the nutrient solution, which is circulated by a small pump, which allows the volume of the nutrient solution to be small. The plants are mounted in holder of acrylic glass at the top of the two glass plates. This confines them in 2 dimensions hence providing a good base for the image processing. First experiments have shown that the position of the root is stable and flushing of the nutrient solution does not disturb the analysis.

Current work is done on finding a suitable marking technique for the root. The set up is currently being optimised for the density of particles used for growth analysis. This is done in close collaboration with project A, which provides the algorithms suited for the analysis. The interaction between the application project and the central project is crucial, since a variety of algorithms for tracking particles are available, differing in the required features of the image sequences.

5 Infrared Imaging

5.1 Botanical Objectives

The objective of the entire project is the set up of a multi-channel approach to follow physiological and biochemical function in growing plants. In the proposal we named several aspects, which we will approach in the medium term. During the first phase of the project we aimed to analyse spatial and temporal aspects of transpiration by thermography.

The major gas flux out of a leaf is transpiration. Water flux leaving the leaf via transpiration is a significant percentage of the entire water present in the leaf. However transpiration is not only relevant for the water relations, but also for the nutrient relations of a leaf, since nutrients are carried passively in the mass flux from the soil to the leaf. Transpiration rate is determined by two parameters, namely (1) the difference in water concentration between the internal of the leaf and the atmosphere and (2) the resistance for the gaseous diffusion. The latter can be split in the stomatal resistance, which the plant can control dynamically by opening and closing the stomatal pores, the cuticular resistance being rather high under normal circumstances, and the boundary layer resistance.

Significant local and dynamic variations of stomatal aperture have been investigated in recent literature by rather indirect measures like e.g. chlorophyll fluorescence imaging [Siebke and Weis, 92] and infiltration techniques [Beyschlag, 96]. Temperature relations per se are important for the plant, since metabolic activity is significantly influenced by temperature. Thermography provides a potent tool to study transpiration, water and temperature relations of plants. Experiences with this technique in project B have significantly contributed to the successful application to our botanical objects.

5.2 Background of the Set Up

The leaf is subjected to a selection of energy fluxes determining its temperature. In the general case the energy fluxes at the leaf are given by

$$j = j_{sol} + j_{ir}^{surr} + j_{ir}^{sky} + j_{ir}^l + j_{sen} + j_{lat} + j_{chem} + j_{ws} \quad (D.1)$$

with

j	total absorbed or emitted flux density,
j_{sol}	absorbed energy flux density from the solar irradiance,
j_{ir}^{surr}	absorbed energy flux density from the infrared radiation of the surroundings,
j_{ir}^{sky}	absorbed energy flux density from the sky, which is not necessary in a climate cabinet,
j_{ir}^l	emitted black body radiation by the leaf,
j_{sen}	sensible heat flux density,
j_{lat}	latent heat flux density,
j_{chem}	stored chemical energy by the leaf,
j_{ws}	heat influx by water with a different temperature than the leaf.

The solar flux can either be given by the solar radiation in field experiments or glasshouse experiments or by the illumination of the growth chamber. This factor needs to be evaluated separately for each individual experimental situation since intensity and spectrum of the irradiation have significant influence on the heat balance. In our experiments fluorescent light sources were used, which emit light mainly in the visible range. Heat flux from external sources other than the direct illumination can also contribute considerably. Since the radiant exitance is dependent on T^4 the influence of this factor is very much dependent on the temperature of the surroundings. Quantitative analysis of the energy fluxes has to take into account reflection, transmission, emission and absorption. These quantities depend very much on the wavelength of the irradiance. In the sensitivity range of the IR camera the optical properties of the leaves are governed by the high water content. Sensible heat transfer significantly contributes in turbulent situations. However temperature exchange over the boundary layer is determined by the molecular diffusion term. Chemical heat flux in the leaf is mainly the energy flux due to assimilation of CO_2 and was estimated to be up to 10% of the incoming radiation in our experimental set up [Dauwe, 97].

The determination of the latent heat flux plays a major role in this project, since it is determined by the evaporation of water during transpiration. Infrared imaging has the potential as a tool for studying the transpiration of plants [Hashimoto, 84], since evaporation of water is accompanied by a loss to latent heat. As the latent heat of water is about 600 times its heat capacity even minor transpiration

Figure D.10: Temperature of intercostal area and vein area with time

causes a significant cooling of the evaporating surface. This principle has been applied successfully to the ocean surface in project B. The experience with this technique in project B contributed significantly to the progress of the work in this project. However, the leaf is a more complex structure than the sea surface:

1. Contrary to an open water surface, the leaf is covered by the cuticula, a small waxy layer, which is a major resistance for water loss from the leaf. The cuticula is almost impermeable to gases like H_2O and CO_2 such that the only pathways for the exchange of these gases are the so-called stomata. Stomata are formed by guard cells which can be opened or closed hence allowing tuning of transpiration.
2. Another important difference between the leaf and the open water surface is the spatially varying thermal properties of the leaf. For example, veins have a higher heat capacity than the intercostal areas (see below). Additionally lateral heat diffusion coefficients vary locally. Turbulent water flow is not very common in plant leaves. These features make it impossible to transfer quantitative methods directly from the models developed for the open sea surface to the leaf, since they are obtained under the assumption of statistical homogeneity and isotropy [Haußecker, 96] of the observed object.

The aim of phase I of this project was to find out under which conditions it is possible to obtain a quantitative relation between transpiration and infrared images.

5.3 Preliminary Experiments

All experiments were done in a temperature and humidity controlled growth cabinet. During the first measurements image sequences were acquired from tobacco leaves by the Amber Radiance 1 IR-camera. Two important features are obvious from these initial measurements (Figure D.10):

1. Oscillations of the surface temperature of the leaf by almost two degrees were observed. This effect was due to the temperature control of the climate chamber, which could stabilise the temperature to $\pm 1^\circ C$ (values reasonable for cabinets of that size). As this is an intrinsic feature of any feedback control it can not be avoided.
2. The phase of the temperature oscillation of the vein was slightly shifted relative to the phase of the intercostal area. This fact was attributed to the different heat capacity of these structures (see 5.5 for the time constants). Absorption differences are very unlikely, because of the nature of the processes that impose the oscillation (probably sensitive heat transfer from the air in the chamber and black body radiation from the cuvette walls).

These observations clearly showed that

Figure D.11: View of the gas exchange cuvette modified for IR-imaging: (1) control unit (2) cover with window of hostaflon (3) black body reference (4) cuvette (5) IR-camera system.

The image in the monitor is an original image from this set up (the temperature difference of the leaf blade to the background is approx. 2°C).

1. a thermal reference point is needed, which follows passively the radiation variations. The difference between this passive body and the leaf temperature can then be related to transpiration.
2. For the evaluation of transient states, i.e. change of temperature, the local heat capacity has to be taken into account. Obviously regions of great heat capacity per unit area change temperature more slowly than areas of low heat capacity.

On the basis of these experiments two methods needed to be established: (1) Passive thermography with reference points to determine transpiration related changes in surface temperature and (2) active thermography to analyse local differences in heat capacity of the leaf. These two techniques need to be combined in the future work to obtain space-resolved maps of the transpiration rate.

5.4 Passive Thermography

5.4.1 Improvements in the Set Up

Further experiments were done with *Ricinus communis*. The first enhancement was to introduce a standard gas exchange system to the set up, which allows to control air temperature, air humidity and gas composition more accurately than the growth cabinet. This system also allowed to quantitatively measure the H₂O and CO₂-fluxes integrated over the leaf. Cuvettes of such systems are usually made from acrylic glass, a material, which significantly absorbs in the range of wavelength sensed by the IR camera system. A thin hostaflon window had to be introduced into the top of the cuvette allowing direct observation of the leaf by the IR-camera system in a gas-tight set up, which allows quantitative gas exchange measurements (figure D.11). Reflections at this foil severely disturb in the image sequences. Substitution of hostaflon by a less absorbing material would significantly enhance the image quality.

The stringent control of temperature inside the cuvette reduced the impact of sensible heat on the leaf temperature, however changes in the temperatures of the surrounding growth cabinet were still transferred into temperature changes of the leaf. To reduce this impact additional measurements were performed without climate control of the growth cabinet. This resulted in a gradual shift of temperatures, but no oscillations disturbing the measurements. Small brass plates covered with Tetenal - a black varnish that makes a fairly good black body ($\geq 98\%$ emissivity) - were used as reference points inside the cuvette. If the signal from the black body reference is subtracted from the rest of the image, the difference will be due to the transpiration effect of the leaf. Another advantage is that the effect of

Figure D.12: Top: Temperatures measured by the gas exchange cuvette and Amber Radiance 1 IR camera. Bottom: Temperature difference (black body reference - leaf temperature) measured by camera and ΔH_2O (proportional to transpiration) measured by gas exchange cuvette (right axis). Between both plots is a time gap of 10 minutes.

the reflections at the hostafilon can be reduced by the internal reference points. By relating the transpiration rate and the temperature variation it is possible to determine the transfer velocity of heat through the boundary layer of the leaf.

5.4.2 First Measurements with Passive Thermography

In a first set of experiments, environmental parameters were varied, which are known to cause changes in stomatal aperture, hence in transpiration rate. Variation of carbon dioxide concentration. Since water loss occurs through the same pores as CO_2 -uptake into the leaf, stomata optimise their aperture in order to release as little water as possible per gained CO_2 . Increasing CO_2 concentration (100 ppm to 350 ppm) therefore cause stomatal closure. These experiments were carried out at 3 different light intensities (maximum $150 \mu mol photons m^{-2} s^{-1}$). At low CO_2 -concentrations (100 ppm) the mean leaf blade temperature was $2^\circ C$ cooler than the surroundings.

When the leaf was subjected to 350 ppm the temperature had almost adapted to the surrounding surface temperatures 35 minutes later. The temperature difference between the leaf blade and the reference metal plates inside the gas exchange cuvette closely resembled the change in transpiration rate of the leaf (figure D.12) during the increase and decrease of the CO_2 -concentration in all light regimes. Small delays in the transpiration rate relative to the temperature difference are explained by the flush rate of the gas exchange cuvette.

Since the temperature difference ΔT is a local feature and transpiration rate is only measured as the integral over the entire leaf, individual relations between transpiration rate and ΔT are present. The correlation between ΔT and the transpiration rate is quite good, keeping in mind that this is the first experiment in which this was evaluated (figure D.13). The theoretical analysis revealed a linear relation between these two quantities in the first approximation. The heat transfer velocity could be estimated from these measurements.

Stomata open in response to light. Variation of light intensities are more difficult to study by thermography, since energy input into the leaf and stomatal aperture would change simultaneously. However, the time constant for stomatal opening is significantly larger than for the heating of the

Figure D.13: Relation between ΔH_2O and temperature difference of the metal plate and the leaf $\Delta T = T_m - T_l$. A linear fit results in an offset of 287 ± 36 ppm and a slope of 1080 ± 4 ppm/K.

brass plates and, for example, the onset of photosynthesis (Figure D.14). This can be used to avoid disturbances of the analysis.

The temperature difference rapidly increases after the onset of light due to the differences in heat capacity and absorption characteristics of the brass plates and the leaf. CO_2 -assimilation and transpiration rate also rise immediately with light. However, in contrast to the assimilation rate, the transpiration rate continues to rise after the end of the light pulse. During that phase of the experiment, temperature difference and transpiration rate again follow each other closely.

5.5 Active Thermography for the Determination of Local Heat Capacity

Local interpretation of the surface temperature requires data on the local heat capacity of the leaf. This parameter varies significantly (see below) due to the inhomogenous distribution of water in the leaf. From this point of view, IR-imaging has the potential to determine the local water content of the leaf, a measure, which might prove to be a botanically relevant property of the leaf per se, and which could not be estimated previously in a spatially and temporally resolved manner. From the systems theory point of view, the incident energy heating up a body corresponds to the input signal into the investigated system - in our case the leaf. Black body radiation can be regarded as the output signal. In this analogy, heat capacity becomes the damping factor that relates both signals. To learn about this damping factor system theory offers the constant input and the periodical input approach. The constant approach is identical to the periodical for $\omega = 0$. However for simplicity we will describe the constant input approach first.

5.5.1 Set up for Active Thermography

For simplicity, heating was done with an infrared lamp as used in medical applications (figure D.15). This is not optimal for several reasons: (1) the lamp has a broad emittance spectra. Therefore the penetration depth is not known exactly, since it depends on the wavelength. (2) Additionally to IR-radiation the lamp emits visible light. The intensity of this light, however, is low (approx. $20 \text{ mmol photons m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$). Significant improvement is expected from laser-heating.

A glass plate, diaphragms and a plate of acrylic glass were used to reduce reflections and to narrow the band width of the radiation to which the leaf was subjected. Image sequences were attained by the Amber Radiance 1. Pixelwise analysis of the time constant τ and the temperature difference before and after heating (ΔT) was done in the image sequences

Figure D.14: Response to a light pulse. Top: Measured temperatures by the cuvette and the Amber Radiance 1 IR camera. Middle: ΔCO_2 (proportional to assimilation) and $\Delta\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (proportional to transpiration) versus time. Bottom: Temperature difference (black body reference - leaf temperature) measured by camera and $\Delta\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (proportional to transpiration) measured by gas exchange cuvette (right axis).

Figure D.15: Experimental set up for active thermography.

Figure D.16: Time constant τ for a *Ricinus cotyledon*

5.5.2 Constant Heating Thermography

In the constant heating approach the leaf is heated by a step-increase of irradiance and the temperature change is analysed. It can be easily envisaged that structures with high heat capacity increase their temperature at a slower rate than those with low heat capacity. The heat capacity can be calculated from the time constant τ by

$$\tau = \frac{C}{A} \frac{1}{8\alpha_{ir}\sigma T_{surr}^3 + 2k_{heat}\rho_a c_a} \quad (D.2)$$

with

- τ time constant,
- $\frac{C}{A}$ heat capacity per unit area,
- α_{ir} absorption for infrared irradiation,
- σ Boltzmann constant,
- T_{surr} temperature of the surroundings,
- k_{heat} heat transfer velocity,
- ρ_a density of air,
- c_a heat capacity of air under constant pressure.

For evaluation of the analysis, brass plates of different thickness and hence different heat capacity, were covered with Tetanal varnish and used again as references. Analysis of the leaf revealed that the time constants of the veins were almost twice as high as for the intercostal areas, indicating the

Figure D.17: Applied rectangular signal (*t*-space, frame number) and fourier transform (frequency space). The amplitude does not vanish for odd multiples of the base frequency (1st, 3rd, 5th, ... harmonics). The absolute value declines with $1/\omega$.

higher heat capacity of the veins due to there higher water content per area (figure D.16). A significant drawback of this method, however, is that the absorption of the leaf is not known exactly due to the broad range of wavelength of the illuminating lamp.

5.5.3 Periodical Heating Thermography

Periodical heating can be used to determine the heat capacity by analysing the temperature response of the object in the Fourier space. The time constant τ can be determined from the amplitude damping and the phase shift by

$$\tau \stackrel{\omega \ll \frac{1}{\tau}}{=} -\frac{\varphi(\omega)}{\omega} \quad \text{for } \omega \neq 0 \quad (\text{D.3})$$

Exact sinusoidal heating is difficult to obtain with an IR lamp. Therefore a rectangular pulse scheme was applied. Since the rectangular signal is a mixture of various cosines functions this has additionally the advantage that simultaneously several frequencies are applied (figure D.17), which significantly reduces the time needed for the determinations.

Phase and amplitude were calculated pixelwise for the different frequencies (figure D.18). It can clearly be seen that significant smearing of the images occurs at low frequencies due to lateral diffusion of heat. Additionally the times allowed for these determinations is limited by the times, in which the leaf is expected to remain in a constant physiological status.

Figure D.18: Amplitude damping with frequency. The shown intensity is proportional to the amplitude of the temperature oscillation. Note that the scaling is different for each image.

6 Calcium Imaging

6.1 Botanical Objectives

As a second topic for visualisation of physiological processes we named calcium signalling in the proposal. In cooperation with Dr. Knight (Oxford) we envisaged to use the very elegant approach to this by the expression of the jellyfish protein Aequorin in transgenic plant [Knight *et al.*, 91]. This photo-protein emits light in response to calcium concentration. Transgenic tobacco (*Nicotiana plumbaginifolia*) expressing aequorin under the control of the constitutive 35S promotor were provided by Dr. M. Knight (Oxford). Intensified CCD cameras have been used to detect the calcium induced light emission in whole plant investigations [Knight *et al.*, 93]. Some of the investigations involve the response of the transgenic plants to cold stimuli, which involves cooling down the plant from 25 °C to a temperature as low as 2 °C. Similar responses of Ca^{++} -concentrations were obtained, when only the root system was subjected to cold. Multi channel imaging of the calcium signal and the thermal signal is particular promising to tackle the open question, if temperature itself or a different signal triggered Ca^{++} -concentration changes in this configuration. In co-operation with Dr. M. Knight we began to set up a calcium imaging system which will be employed in the second phase of the research unit when our basic approaches will be extended to multi channel acquisition. Due to the shortening of the funding period the effort put into this part of the project had to be limited.

6.2 Design of the Set Up

As an alternative acquisition system a slow scan CCD camera was selected. In the original experiments images taken at a rate of 50 Hz by an intensified CCD and integrated over a period of 10 sec and more. This brings the acquisition requirements in the range suitable for a slow scan CCD. They usually begin to perform better than intensified CCD-cameras at integration times of more than 1 second. In order to provide a uniform software interface for all image processing applications in this project we integrated the software of the slow scan CCD into our system. This will make it easier for the casual user to work with the new techniques. In further preparation for the next phase of the research unit a cooling system of two Peltier elements was built and first steps in designing an easy access light tight box for the low light experiments were taken. This approach will now also be applied for active thermography. In parallel to these efforts we started to grow transgenic tobacco from seeds we received from Dr. Knight. Initial problem in growing the plants could be overcome by treating the seed with the phytohormone Gibberellin (GA3). Further work is to be done in the next funding period.

7 Present Activities

Leaf growth A series of botanical image sequences are presently been acquired and evaluated. Masking of the leaf will be enhanced by the use of adaptive contour models. This will also give practical experience in this approach for the future 3D-analysis.

Root growth Different particle densities are tested for the usability in the various algorithms provided by the central project to determine motion fields.

Thermography Further examinations on the relation between transpiration rate and temperature differences between passive brass plates and the leaf are taken, in order to evaluate the local analysis of transpiration rate. In co-operation with a group in Darmstadt studying gas exchange characteristics in a chaos theory background measurements will be taken to evaluate the possibility that local heterogeneity is involved in these observations.

Evaluation of high-sensitivity cameras In co-operation with Project A, B and E we want to test several high-sensitivity cameras for the usability in the different applications.

References

- [1] Beyschlag, (1997) Stomatal Patchiness, Progress in Botany 59, In Press.
- [2] Dauwe, Stefan, Infrarotuntersuchungen zur Bestimmung des Wasser- und Wärmehaushaltes eines Blattes, diploma thesis, Heidelberg, 1997
- [3] Haußecker, Horst, Messung und Simulation von kleinskaligen Austauschvorgängen an der Ozeanoberfläche mittels Thermographie, PhD thesis, Heidelberg, 1996
- [4] Heckenberger, Uwe, Auswirkung von Trockenstress auf morphologische und physiologische Prozesse während der Blattentwicklung von *Ricinus communis*, PhD thesis, Heidelberg, 1996
- [5] Hashimoto, Y., dynamic analysis of water stress of sunflower leaves by means of a thermal image processing system, Plant Physiol. 76, pp 266-269, 1984
- [6] Knight, M. R., Read, N. D., Campbell, Trewavas, A. J. (1993) Imaging calcium dynamics in living plants using semi-synthetic recombinant aequorins. J. Cell Biol. 121, 83-90
- [7] Knight, M. R., Campbell, A. K., Smith, S. M., Trewavas, A. J. (1991) Transgenic plant aequorin reports the effects of touch, cold-shock and elicitors on cytoplasmic calcium. Nature 352, 524-526.
- [8] Larcher, Walter, Ökologie der Pflanzen, Ulmer Verlag, Stuttgart, 1980
- [9] Lell, Martin, Ortsaufgelöste Bestimmung von Blattwachstum durch Strukturanalyse von Bildsequenzen aus dem nahen Infrarot, diploma thesis, Heidelberg, 1996
- [10] Schmundt, Dominik, Voruntersuchung der Einsatzmöglichkeiten digitaler Bildverarbeitung zur Analyse von Transportvorgängen und Wachstumsprozessen in Pflanzen, diploma thesis, Heidelberg, 1995
- [11] Siebke, K. and Weis, E. (1995) Assimilation images of leaves from *Glechochoma hederaceae*. Analysis of non-synchronous stomata related oscillations. Planta 196, 148-165
- [12] Silk, W. (1992) Steady form from changing cells, International Journal of Plant Sciences 153, 49-58.
- [13] Vogelmann, T. C., Nishio, J. N., Smith, W. K., Leaves and light capture: light propagation and gradients of carbon fixation within leaves, trends in plant sciences, Vol. 1, No. 2, pp 65 - 70

I Publications

Note: Some of the publications are available as pdf files from our WEB page
<http://klimt.iwr.uni-heidelberg.de>

Monographs, Book Chapters, Conference Proceedings

- [1] Jähne, B., P. Geißler, H. Haußecker, and F. Hering, eds., 1996. *Mustererkennung 1996*, Tagungsband des DAGM Symposiums Mustererkennung 1996, Heidelberg, 11-13. September 1996, Reihe Informatik Aktuell, Springer, Berlin.
- [2] Jähne, B., 1997. *Practical Handbook on Digital Image Processing for Scientific Applications*, CRC-Press, Boca Raton, FL, USA.
- [3] Jähne, B., 1997. *Digitale Bildverarbeitung*, 4. komplett überarbeitete Auflage. Springer, Berlin.
- [4] Jähne, B., 1997. *Digital Image Processing — Concepts, Algorithms, and Scientific Applications*, 4th completely revised edition, Springer, Berlin, in press.
- [5] Jähne, B., and J. Klinke, 1997. Short wind waves, In *Drag at the Ocean Surface*, edited by I. Jones and Y. Toba, Cambridge University Press, in press.
- [6] Schurr, U. 1997. *Growth physiology and measurement of growth*, In: Progress in Botany, Behnke, H.-D., Luetge, U., Esser, K., Kadereit, J.W. und Runge, M. (eds.) Springer-Verlag, Berlin, in press.

Articles

- [1] Schurr, U., B. Schuberth, R. Aloni, K. S. Pradel, D. Schmundt, B. Jähne, and C. I. Ullrich, 1996. Structural and functional evidence for xylem-mediated water-transport and high transpiration in *Agrobacterium tumefaciens*-induced tumor of *Ricinus communis*. *Botanica Acta* 109, 405-411.
- [2] Münsterer, T., and B. Jähne, 1997. LIF measurements of concentration profiles in the aqueous mass boundary layer, submitted to *Experiments in Fluids*, May 1997.
- [3] Jähne, B., 1997. SIMD-Bildverarbeitungsalgorithmen mit dem Multimedia Extension-Instruktionssatz (MMX) von Intel, *Automatisierungstechnik AT*, in press.
- [4] Jähne, B., and H. Haußecker, 1998. Air-Water Gas Exchange, *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 30, in press (invited review paper).
- [5] Jähne, B., and J. Klinke, 1997. Wave Number Spectra of Short Wind Waves — A Comparative Study of Laboratory and Field Results, to be submitted to *J. Physical Oceanogr.*
- [6] Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, 1997. Heat as a proxy tracer for gas transfer measurements in the field: principles and results from the joint CoOP/MBL Pacific cruise, to be submitted to *J. Geophys. Res.*
- [7] Leue, C., B. Jähne, and U. Platt, 1997. An improved algorithm to retrieve trace gas concentration from GOME images, to be submitted to *J. Applied Optics*.

Contributions to Conferences and Proceedings

- [1] Schmundt, D., M. Lell, U. Schurr, B. Jähne, and M. Stitt, 1996. Local orientation in the space-time domain as a tool for growth studies in plants Int. Conf. on Spectroscopy and optical techniques in animals and plant biology Paul, R. J., Weis, E., Kamp, G. and Lauterwein, J., Münster, September 30 - October 3, 1996.
- [2] Schmundt, D., U. Schurr, B. Jähne, and M. Stitt, 1996. IR thermography - a novel approach to stomatal conductance Int. Conf. on Spectroscopy and optical techniques in animals and plant biology Paul, R. J., Weis, E., Kamp, G. and Lauterwein, J., Münster, September 30 - October 3, 1996.
- [3] Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, 1996. A tensor approach for local structure analysis in multi-dimensional images, Proc. *3D Image Analysis and Synthesis '96*, Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, November 18-19, 1996, B. Girod, H. Niemann, H.-P. Seidel (eds.), Proc. in Artificial Intelligence 3, infix, Sankt Augustin, pp. 171-178.
- [4] Jähne, B., H. Haußecker, F. Hering, G. Balschbach, J. Klinke, M. Lell, D. Schmundt, M. Schultz, U. Schurr, M. Stitt, and U. Platt, 1996. The role of active vision in exploring growth, transport, and exchange processes, Proc. *Aktives Sehen in technischen und biologischen Systemen*, Workshop der GI-Fachgruppe 1.0.4. Bildverstehen Hamburg, 3-4. December 1996, B Mertsching (Hrsg), Proc. in Artificial Intelligence 4, infix, Sankt Augustin, pp. 194-202.
- [5] Schurr, U., 1997. Acclimation to soil drying - growth processes, Meeting of the Scandinavian Society of Plant Physiologist (SPPS) Uppsala 12.-17.6.1997.
- [6] Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, 1997. A tensor approach for precise computation of dense displacement vector fields, Proc. *Mustererkennung 1997*, Braunschweig, 15-17. September 1997, E. Paulus und F. M. Wahl (Hrsg.), Informatik Aktuell, Springer, Berlin, 199-208 (the contribution received one of the DAGM awards).
- [7] Scharr, H., S. Körkel, and B. Jähne, 1997. Numerische Isotropieoptimierung von FIR-Filtern mittels Querglättung, Proc. *Mustererkennung 1997*, Braunschweig, 15-17. September 1997, E. Paulus und F. M. Wahl (Hrsg.), Informatik Aktuell, Springer, Berlin, 367-374.
- [8] B. Jähne, 1997. Performance characteristics of low-level motion estimators in spatiotemporal images, Proc. *DAGM-Workshop Performance Characteristics and Quality of Computer Vision Algorithms*, Braunschweig, September 18, 1997, W. Foerstner (ed.), Institute of Photogrammetry, Univ. Bonn.
- [9] Balschbach, G., and B. Jähne, 1997. Neigungsmessung der wellenbewegten Wasseroberfläche mittels Farbbildverarbeitung, Proc. *Workshop Farbbildverarbeitung*, Erlangen, September 25-26, 1997.
- [10] B. Jähne, 1998. Spatiotemporal structure of short wind waves as determined from wave slope image sequences, invited contribution to IUTAM Symposium *Three-Dimensional Aspects of Air-Sea Interaction*, Nice, France, May 17-21, 1998, in preparation.
- [11] Jähne, B., H. Haußecker, U. Platt, U. Schurr, and M. Stitt, 1997. The Research Unit (Forscherguppe) Image Sequence Processing to Study Dynamical Processes, paper submitted to the workshop *3D-Bildanalyse und -synthese*, Erlangen, November 17-18, 1997.
- [12] Balschbach, G., J. Klinke, and B. Jähne, 1997. Multichannel shape from shading techniques for reconstruction of specular surfaces, paper submitted to the workshop *3D-Bildanalyse und -synthese*, Erlangen, November 17-18, 1997.
- [13] B. Jähne, 1998. The Heidelberg Aelotron — new perspectives for laboratory investigations of air-sea interaction, abstract submitted to the OS07 Special Session *Laboratory Experiments in Physical Oceanography*, at the AGU Ocean Science Meeting, San Diego, USA, February 9-13, 1998.
- [14] ??, 1998. ?. Abstract submitted to the OS18 Special Session *Dynamics of the Ocean Surface Mixed Layer*, at the AGU Ocean Science Meeting, San Diego, USA, February 9-13, 1988.
- [15] ??, 1998. ?. Poster submitted to the OS26 Special Session *Recent Advances in Ocean and Fresh Water Science Instrumentation*, at the AGU Ocean Science Meeting, San Diego, USA, February 9-13, 1988.

- [16] B. Jähne and H. Haußecker, 1998. Performance characteristics and validation of low-level motion estimation in spatiotemporal images, invited contribution 9th Workshop *Theoretical Foundations of Computer Vision: Evaluation and Validation of Computer Vision Algorithms*, organized by R. Haralick, R. Klette, H. S. Stiehl, and M. Viergever, Schloß Dagstuhl, March 16–20, 1998.
- [17] Scharr, H., S. Koergel, and B. Jähne, 1998. New classes of optimized filters for spatiotemporal image processing with floating-point and integer coefficients, paper to be submitted to the *Fifth European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV'98)*, Freiburg, Germany, June 2–6, 1998.
- [18] Balschbach, G., J. Klinke, and B. Jähne, 1998. Multichannel shape from shading techniques for moving specular surfaces, paper to be submitted to the *Fifth European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV'98)*, Freiburg, Germany, June 2–6, 1998.
- [19] Jähne, B., and H. Haußecker, 1998. Study of dynamical processes with tensor-based spatiotemporal image processing techniques, paper to be submitted to the *Fifth European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV'98)*, Freiburg, Germany, June 2–6, 1998.
- [20] Jähne, B., H. Haußecker, D. Schmundt, M. Schultz, B. Kümmerlein, U. Schur, M. Stitt, 1998. Active and passive thermography to study small-scale air-sea interaction processes and plant leaf transpiration, paper to be submitted to the *Fifth European Conference on Computer Vision (ECCV'98)*, Freiburg, Germany, June 2–6, 1998.
- [21] Haußecker, H., and B. Jähne, 1998. Tensor-based image sequence processing techniques for the study of dynamical processes, invited paper, *International Symposium on Realtime Imaging and Dynamic Analysis*, Hakodate, Japan, June 2–5, 1998.
- [22] Leue, C., U. Platt, and B. Jähne, 1998. Analysis of emission plumes from multispectral image sequences of the GOME instrument of the ERS2 satellite, paper to be submitted to *International Symposium on Realtime Imaging and Dynamic Analysis*, Hakodate, Japan, June 2–5, 1998.
- [23] Jähne, B., 1998. Performance characteristics of low-level motion estimators in spatiotemporal images, paper to be submitted to the *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'98)*, Santa Barbara, June 23–25, 1998.
- [24] D. Schmundt, H. Haußecker, B. Jähne, U. Schurr, and M. Stitt, 1998. Image sequence processing techniques for plant leaf growth studies, paper to be submitted to *Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR'98)*, Santa Barbara, June 23–25, 1998.

II Theses

In the period from the start of the research unit (December 1955) until now, 5 Diploma theses and 4 Dissertations were successfully finished. Currently (August 1997) 9 Diploma theses and 7 Dissertations are in progress. Two members of the research unit are working towards their habilitation.

Diploma Theses

- [1] Martin Lell, *Ortsaufgelöste Bestimmung von Blattwachstum durch Strukturanalyse von Bildsequenzen aus dem nahen Infrarot*, 6/1996.
- [2] Uwe Schimpf, *Fourieranalyse mikroskaliger Temperaturfluktuationen der Wasseroberfläche*, 5/1996.
- [3] Richard Fitzenberger, *Lokale Transformationsmethoden zur Auswertung von Wellenneigungsbildern der Wasseroberfläche im Bereich kleinskaliger Oberflächenwellen*, 5/1997.
- [4] Holger Weiss, *Modulation von Windwellen*, 3/1997.
- [5] Michael Schultz, *Geometrische Kalibration von CCD-Kameras*, 7/1997

In Preparation

- [6] Andreas Stolz, *Bildaufnehmende differentielle IR-Absorptions-Spektroskopie zur in situ Messung von Spurengasen in Wind/Wasser-Kanälen*, since 7/1996.
- [7] Stefan Dauwe, *Aktive Thermographie zur ortsaufgelösten Bestimmung der Wärmeflußraten und der Transpiration an Pflanzenblättern*, since 8/1996.
- [8] Sven Eichkorn, *Studium des CO₂ Gasaustausches durch laserinduzierte Fluoreszenz*, since 9/1996.
- [9] Udo Sedig, *Radiometrische und spektroradiometrische Kalibrierung von CCD Kameras*, since 9/1996.
- [10] Achim Walter, *Analyse des Wachstums von Tabakblättern - Cytologie und Physiologie*, since 1/1997.
- [11] Sven Mann, *Bildfolgenanalyse zur Untersuchung von Motility Assays*, since 3/1997.
- [12] Bernd Kümmerlein, *Aktive Thermographie*, since 4/1997.
- [13] Heiko Carstens, *Lokale Methode zur Bestimmung von Wellenzahl/Frequenzspektren winderzeugter Wasserwellen*, since 9/1997.
- [14] Uli Lode, *Entwicklung eines neuartigen LIF-Verfahrens zur tiefenaufgelösten Bestimmung von Konzentrationsfeldern gelöster Gase in der viskosen Grenzschicht*, since 9/1997.

Dissertation Theses

- [1] Horst Haußecker, *Messung und Simulation von kleinskaligen Austauschvorgängen an der Ozeanoberfläche mittels Thermographie*, 5/1996.
- [2] Jochen Klinke, *Optical Measurement of Small-Scale Wind-Generated Water Surface Waves in the Laboratory and the Field*, 10/1996.
- [3] Thomas Münsterer, *LIF Investigation of the Mechanisms Controlling Air-Water Mass Transfer at a Free Interface*, 11/1996
- [4] Markus Beyer, *Skalenraumanalyse nichtlinearer Wasseroberflächenwellen*, 2/1997.

In Preparation

- [5] Günther Balschbach, *Geometrische Formen und Dynamik von kleinskaligen Windwellen*, since 7/1994.
- [6] Dominik Schmundt, *Studium des Wachstums dicotyle Blätter mittels Bildfolgenanalyse*, since 1/1996.
- [7] Jochen Dieter, *Analyse kleinskaliger Windwellen mittels Bildfolgen von Reflektionsbildern*, since 1/1996.
- [8] Uwe Schimpf, *Studium des Gasaustausches an der Meeresoberfläche mittels passiver Thermographie*, since 8/1996.
- [9] Carsten Leue, *Analysis of global gas emissions for multispectral image sequences*, since 10/1996, Award of the Studienstiftung des Deutschen Volkes.
- [10] Hanno Scharr, *Mehrgitterverfahren zur Bildfolgenanalyse im Orts-Zeit-Raum*, since 11/1996, Stipendiat im Graduiertenkolleg "Wissenschaftliches Rechnen".
- [11] Wolfgang Teichmann, *Entwicklung von 4D-Raum/Zeit-Bildfolgenanalysemethoden zur Untersuchung der dynamischen Genomorganization*, since 5/1997.

Habilitation Theses**In Preparation**

- [1] Uli Schurr, *Interaktion von Physiologie, Biochemie und Cytologie in wachsenden Pflanzen*, since 4/1992.
- [2] Horst Haußecker, *Bildfolgenanalyse zum Studium von Austausch- und Transportvorgängen*, since 6/1996.

III Invited Lectures

1996

- [1] B. Jähne, Physics Colloquium, University of Frankfurt, April 24, 1996.
- [2] B. Jähne, Industrial Vision Days, Vision'96, Stuttgart, October 10, 1996.
- [3] B. Jähne, Informatik Colloquium, University of Bremen, November 13, 1996.

1997

- [4] B. Jähne, ABW-Workshop, Technische Akademie Esslingen, January 23, 1997.
- [5] F. Hering, 24. Physikalischer Gesprächskreis Rhein-Neckar, Heidelberger Druckmaschinen AG, Heidelberg, January 30, 1997.
- [6] B. Jähne, Colloquium of the Computer Vision Research Group (Prof. Perona), California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, March 27, 1997.
- [7] B. Jähne, Colloquium of the Physical Oceanography Research Division, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, April 2, 1997.
- [8] B. Jähne, VDMA, Hannover Messe, April 16, 1997.
- [9] B. Jähne, KI 2 Seminar, Bundeskriminalamt, Wiesbaden, June 2, 1997.
- [10] B. Jähne, Naval Research Laboratory, Washington, DC, June 18, 1997.
- [11] H. Scharr, 25. Physikalischer Gesprächskreis Rhein-Neckar, Physikalisches Institut, Heidelberg, June 19, 1997.

IV Interdisciplinary Colloquium

Winter Semester 1995/96

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
23.10.95	J. Hesser, Informatik V, U Mannheim	Echtzeit Volumenvisualisierung in der Medizin
06.11.95	C. Herwig, Zentrum für Kognitionswissenschaften, U Bremen	Bildfolgenverarbeitung für Aktive Beobachter
13.11.95	R. Eils, IWR, U Heidelberg	3D - Voronoi Diagramme zur quantitativen Bildanalyse in der Zellbiologie
20.11.95	J. Weickert, Zentrum für Techno- und Wirtschaftsmathematik, U Kaiserslautern	Kopplung lokaler Strukturanalyse und anisotroper Diffusionsfilterung
27.11.95	T. Scheuermann, Fraunhofer-Institut für chemische Technologie, Pfinztal	Tiefenscharfe Auflichtmikroskopie und Mikrostrukturvermessung
04.12.95	J. Bigün, EPFL Signal Processing École Polytechnique Fédérale, Lausanne	Image sequence analysis by motion segmentation
11.12.95	P. Maaß, Institut für Mathematik, U Potsdam	Wavelet-Methoden zur Bildkompression
18.12.95	T. Wolf, Institut für Mechanische Verfahrenstechnik und Mechanik, U Karlsruhe	Optische Meßtechnik und Fuzzy Logik zur 3-D-Deformationsanalyse
15.01.96	H. Mallot, MPI für biologische Kybernetik, Tübingen	Einfache Mechanismen des menschlichen Stereosehens
22.01.96	H.-G. Maas, Institut für Geodäsie und Photogrammetrie, ETH Zürich	Digitale Photogrammetrie in der Kalibrierung von Industrierobotern
29.01.96	U. Jäger, Fachbereich Elektronik STZ Bildverarbeitung, FH Heilbronn	Bildverarbeitung in der industriellen Qualitätssicherung
05.02.96	B. Lang, MAZ Hamburg GmbH	GIPSI - Ein SIMD-Prozessorchip zur linearen und nichtlinearen lokalen Bildfilterung
12.02.96	H. Herrmann, Fernuniversität Hagen	Die Imagine HISC Rechnerarchitektur für Computer Graphik und Bildverarbeitung

Summer Semester 1996

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
29.04.96	H.-P. Meinzer, DKFZ Heidelberg	Diagnose- und Therapieunterstützung durch medizinische Bildverarbeitung
06.05.96	M. Dohmeyer, Dr. Engler, DLR Göttingen	Anwendungen von Bildverarbeitungstechniken zur Untersuchung von Strömungsphänomenen an Modellen im Windkanal
13.05.96	R. Beranek, IWR Heidelberg und Institut für Ergonomie, TU München	Bestimmung des Blickpunkts durch Verfolgung der Augenbewegung
20.05.96	T. Waschek, DKFZ Heidelberg	Ein neuer Ansatz für Zielvolumendefinition in der 3D Strahlentherapieplanung mit Hilfe von Fuzzy-Logik
03.06.96	A. Spörl, ABB Forschungszentrum Heidelberg und IWR, U Heidelberg	Verarbeitung und Beurteilung von Sensorsignalen mittels Fuzzy-Logik
10.06.96	T. Wagner, Fraunhofer Institut für Integrierte Schaltungen, Erlangen	Texturanalyse für industrielle Oberflächenprüfaufgaben
17.06.96	B. Jähne, IWR, U Heidelberg	Optimale Filteroperationen zur Bewegungsbestimmung im Orts-Zeit-Raum
24.06.96	J. Bigün, EPF Lausanne	Segmentation by Means of Motion
01.07.96	Martin Lell, IWR und Botanisches Institut, U Heidelberg	Erste Ansätze zur Vermessung des Blattwachstums mittels Bildfolgenanalyse
08.07.96	J. Hesser, Informatik V, U Mannheim	3D Echtzeitvisualisierung

Winter Semester 1996/97

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
23.09.96	R. Grigat, Technische Informatik I, TU Hamburg	Vision Chips: Intelligente CMOS-Einchipkameras für die Messtechnik und Qualitätskontrolle
04.11.96	P. Soille, École des Mines, D'Ales, LGI2P	Morphologische Bildverarbeitung in Mehrkanal- und höherdimensionalen Bildern: Grundlagen und Anwendungen
18.11.96	E. Dickmanns, Universität der Bundeswehr, München	Maschinelles Sehen in Echtzeit
02.12.96	E. Weiß, Botanisches Institut, U Münster	Bildgebende Darstellung photosynthetischer Flüsse in Blättern höherer Pflanzen durch Chlorophyll-a-Fluoreszenz Imaging
09.12.96	S. Teiwes und H. Schwarzer, Berliner Institut für Optik (BIFO)	Optische Wavelet-Filter und Matched Filter zur Detektion von Defekten in Textilgewebebildern
16.12.96	U. Köthe, Fraunhofer Institut für Graphische Datenverarbeitung, Rostock	Parameterfreie Merkmalsextraktion mittels automatischer Skalenselektion
20.01.97	B. Höfflinger, Institut für Mikroelektronik, U Stuttgart	Digitale Silizium-Kameras für höchste Dynamik und Geschwindigkeit
03.02.97	C. Schnörr, Informatik, U Hamburg	Variationsansätze zur Segmentation und Merkmalsgewinnung aus Bildern und Bildfolgen
10.02.97	R. Mester, Institut für Angewandte Physik, U Frankfurt	Die Nutzung stochastischer Modelle in der Bildsequenzanalyse

Summer Semester 1997

Datum/Date	Redner/Speaker	Titel/Title
29.04.97	W. von Seelen, Institut für Neuroinformatik, U Bochum	Analyse visueller Szenen
06.05.97	J. Burrows, Institut für Fernerkundung, Fachbereich Physik, U Bremen	GOME und Sciamachy: Fernerkundung der Erdatmosphäre
13.05.97	V.K. Makin, Royal Dutch Meteorological Institute, De Bilt, Niederlande	Coupling of wind waves with the atmosphere
20.05.97	O. Borchers, BASF AG, Ludwigshafen und IWR, U Heidelberg	Bestimmung der Größe und Geschwindigkeit der dispersiven Phase in Gas-Flüssigkeits-Strömungen mittels Digitaler Bildverarbeitung
27.05.97	J. Ruiz-del-Solar, Fraunhofer Institut für Produktionsanlagen und Konstruktionstechnik, Berlin	Biologisch basierte Verfahren zur Objekterkennung und Texturanalyse
03.06.97	J. Hornegger, Lehrstuhl für Mustererkennung, U Erlangen	Statistische Klassifikatoren in der 3D-Bildverarbeitung
17.06.97	J. Beyerer, Institut für Mess- und Regelungstechnik, U Karlsruhe	Datenfusion zur Gewinnung hochwertiger Bilder am Beispiel der Kriminaltechnik
20.06.97	D.Dabiri, Aeronautics, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena	Sources of vorticity within a spilling breaking wave
08.07.97	R. Wuertz, Institut für Neuroinformatik, U Bochum	Objektrepräsentation und flexible Matching Methoden

V First External Workshop

Image Sequence Processing to Study Dynamical Processes, Heidelberg, June 4-6, 1997

Program

Wednesday, June 4 1997

Session I: Overview I

13.00-13.30	Welcome and Introduction
13.30-14.00	Mark Stitt, Institute for Botany, U Heidelberg: Growth processes in botany
14.00-14.30	Ulrich Platt, Institute for Environmental Physics, U Heidelberg: Atmospheric chemistry
14.30-15.00	Bernd Jähne, IWR and Institute for Environmental Physics, U Heidelberg: Small-scale air-sea interaction
15.00-15.30	Christoph Cremer, Institute for Applied Physics, U Heidelberg: Approaches to the analysis of the dynamical 3-D structure of the human genome

Session II: Overview II, Fluorescence Imaging

16.00-16.30	Rainer Fink, Institute for Physiology II, U Heidelberg: Cellular and molecular physiology of the dynamics of Ca regulation and contractility
16.30-17.00	Dietmar Uttenweiler, Institute for Physiology II, U Heidelberg: Mathematical modeling and fluorescence imaging of Ca turnover in muscels
17.00-17.30	Katharina Siebke, Institute of Botany, U Münster: Chlorophyll-imaging in plant leaves
17.30-18.00	Bernd Jähne, IWR and Institute for Environmental Physics, U Heidelberg: High-resolution concentration measurements of dissolved gases by fluorescence imaging
18.00-19.00	Free discussion and demonstrations

Thursday, June 5 1997**Session III: Visualization and Low-Level Image Sequence Processing**

9.00- 9.30	Günter Balschbach, Institute for Environmental Physics, U Heidelberg, and Jochen Klinke, Scripps Institution of Oceanography: Imaging of short wind waves in the laboratory and at sea
9.30-10.00	Hanno Scharr, IWR, U Heidelberg: Filter optimization for image sequence processing
10.00-10.30	Michael Schultz, IWR, U Heidelberg: Photogrammetric calibration of CCD cameras on the basis of image sequences
10.30-11.00	Bernhard Kalusche, Physics Institute, U Würzburg: NMR imaging in biological materials

Session IV: Multispectral image processing

11.30-11.45	Udo Sedig, IWR, U Heidelberg: Radiometric and spectrometric calibration of CCD cameras
11.45-12.15	Carsten Leue, Institute for Environmental Physics, U Heidelberg: Retrieval of atmospheric NO ₂ concentrations from the GOME satellite data
12.15-12.45	Ricarda Hoogen, Institute for Remote Sensing, U Bremen: Ozone profil retrieval from GOME data
12.45-13.00	Andreas Stolz, IWR, U Heidelberg: Imaging IR differential absorption spectroscopy for in situ measurements of CO ₂ profiles in wind/wave flumes

Session V

14.00-14.30	Horst Haussecker, IWR, U Heidelberg: A tensor approach for image sequence processing
14.30-15.00	Hans Burkhardt, Computer Science, U Freiburg: Invariants for Pattern Recognition
15.00-15.30	David Fleet, Queens University, Canada: Learning Parametrized Models of Image Motion

Session VI: Small-scale air-sea interaction

16.00-16.30	Jochen Klinke, Scripps Institution of Oceanography, and Richard Fitzenberger, IWR, U Heidelberg: Wave number spectra of short wind waves: new data and new methods
16.30-17.00	Jörg Seemann, GKSS Research Center Geesthacht: Estimation of 2-dimensional spectra from image sequences of a nautical radar
17.00-17.30	Markus Beyer, IWR, U Heidelberg: Long wave/short wave interaction
17.30-18.00	Christian M. Senet, GKSS Research Center Geesthacht: Estimation of the flow at the ocean surface from image sequences of a nautical radar
18.00-19.00	Free discussion and demonstrations

Friday, June 6 1997**Session VII: Transfer and growth processes**

9.00- 9.30	Horst Haussecker and Uwe Schimpf, IWR, U Heidelberg: Measurements of the microturbulence at the sea surface and the air-sea gas transfer rate
9.30-10.00	E. Bock, Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution: The influence of short wind waves on air-water gas transfer
10.00-10.30	Stefan Dauwe, IWR and Institute for Botany, U Heidelberg: Active IR imaging of plant leaves
10.30-11.00	Dominik Schmundt and Uli Schurr, IWR and Institute for Botany, U Heidelberg: Area-resolved plant leave growth studies

Session VIII

11.30-12.00	Bill Asher, Applied Physics Laboratory, U Washington, Seattle: Bubble mediated gas transfer in seawater and freshwater
12.00-12.30	Peter Geissler and Alexander von Busse, IWR, U Heidelberg: Imaging measurement techniques for bubble spectra and fluxes
12.30-13.00	Xin Zhang, Scripps Institution of Oceanography: Improving Particle Imaging Velocimetry (PIV) for measuring fine flow structures near the sea surface

Session IX

14.00-14.30	Frank Hering, IWR, U Heidelberg: Structure tensor and multiscale particle imaging velocimetry as velocity estimators for tracking
14.30-15.00	Joachim Weickert, U Kopenhagen: AOS Schemes: efficient and reliable scale-space methods for the regularization of N-dimensional data sets this lecture had to be cancelled due to illness
15.00-15.30	Roland Eils, IWR, U Heidelberg: Multidimensional and multichannel imaging for the analysis of the human genome
15.30-16.00	Final discussion

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